

VALKYRIES

D6.5 Landscape of emerging preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration opportunities for first aid response to multi-casualty disasters M18

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1. Executive Summary

This document is an update of the deliverable D6.1 and presents the final results from the study of the existing European landscape regarding the collaboration, education and training in the field of civil protection and crisis management concerning the professional coping capacities of first responders, first aid responders, crisis managers, and relevant humanitarian actors and volunteers. The document presents also national educational systems concerning first responders' qualifications in selected European Union (EU) Member States (MS), the thematic training courses for selected technical professionals provided by Directorate-General for European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (DG ECHO) at the EU level and educational and training activities in various European countries performed under different projects initiatives.

The general updates at the WP6 level and the specific updates at the tasks level are summarised in section 4.2 of this report.

Besides, the document summarises the results from the studies carried out in the framework of the T.6.1 Resource Federation and trusted information sharing, T6.2 Education and Training for first aid responses, T6.3 Raising practitioner and social awareness, T6.4 Civil-Military Cooperation and T6.5 Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism.

In addition, the deliverable summarises the results from the survey on first aid responders carried out in cooperation with WP4, WP5 and WP6.

Finally, the deliverable presents some conclusions and recommendations.

This deliverable is an update of the previously submitted document D6.1 - Landscape of emerging preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters - VA/1. The new content with respect to the last version submitted has been highlighted in yellow for easy review and identification.

2. Identification

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3. Project Overview

3.1. VALKYRIES Project overview

Mass casualty incidents (MCI) and multiple casualty disasters, where the number of victims far exceeds local resources and capabilities, are events that overwhelm the local health system, at least for a period of time.

The response of EMS first responders to these events often reveals insufficient resources (rescue personnel, medical personnel, facilities, etc.), communication difficulties and organizational interoperability problems, which are more acute in cross-border, cross-sector and cross-hierarchical actions.

Although the EU has evolved towards a strong capacity for joint coordination and cross-sectorial cooperation between Member States, studies such as the EU Mandate M/487 to establish EU security standards reveal that the Union is not yet at a stage where responders can interconnect information management systems from different organisations to share situation assessment or automate coordinated response procedures.

Echoing these needs, the project VALKYRIES (Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated Procedures for First Aid Vehicles Deployment on European Multi-victim Disasters) aims to analyse, improve and demonstrate infrastructures, protocols and data exchange standards to increase efficiency during deployment, intervention and local/remote coordination of first aid responders in multi-casualty disasters.

The VALKYRIES project aims to explore the impact of the emerging technologies, procedures and collaboration tools for supporting the cross-sectorial actuation of the first aid responders on cross-border disasters and major crisis situations. On these grounds, VALKYRIES will develop methodologies, adaptation tactics and decision criteria for their harmonisation according to the related pan-European ecosystems.

As the SIGRUN system, to be introduced as the result of the Valkyries project, is going to be “federated”, aka acting as the interoperability layer of existing technological systems working and parametrized to support different local workflows and procedures/ regulations or cross-border agreements, a minimum common workflow and operational procedures needs to be identified in order to support its functionality as such “federated system”.

For such harmonisation, the discovery of regulatory opportunities, validation and demonstration will be documented and analysed, reporting practical field notes and guidelines able to feed standardisation and regulation bodies and serving as a reference for further related integrations.

3.2. WP6 Work package overview

VALKYRIES work has been split into seven work packages (WPs). Three of them (WP4, WP5 and WP6) focus on the three core blocks of working streams and have been developed in parallel:

- Technologies and equipment (KARA): WP4
- Procedures and Operations (HERJA): WP5
- Collaboration and Training (EIR): WP6

The main aim of the reference integration, SIGRUN, is to provide a real use case driven implementation that allow applying the proposed normalizations on some of the discovered technological (KARA), procedural (HERJA) and collaborative and training (EIR) opportunities.

Figure 1 – Global vision of the VALKYRIES project.

VALKYRIES WP6: Cooperation, education and training for first aid responses, aims to plan, organise and implement international comparative research and analyses on the process of building a harmonisation framework for facilitating, guiding and enhancing the cooperation between vehicular first aid responders with other disaster management actors (firefighters, law enforcement agencies, civilian protection authorities, military, heterogeneous voluntary organisations, etc.). The following working streams will be conducted during its execution: Resource Federation and trusted information sharing, Education and Training for first aid responses, Raising practitioner and social awareness, Civil-Military Cooperation, Civil Protection cooperation and Aid Volunteerism.

WP6 address the following related tasks:

- **T6.1: Resource federation and trusted information sharing.** The task explores emerging collaboration opportunities focalised on resource federation and trusted information sharing, revealing their map, regulatory/normalization gaps and proposing a roadmap for their mitigation. A subset of the opportunities will be reference harmonised towards enabling the project reference integration (SIGRUN). The main aim of the task is to design and develop a framework able to build a resource federation between multiple parties and stakeholders making up the disaster scenario, enabling their cooperation in a secure and trusted fashion as well as emphasizing the demanded collaborative procedures by following a cross-sectorial, cross-border and cross-hierarchical approach. The inter-institutional collaboration requirements will be analysed thoroughly, adapting the resource federation framework with the interoperability harmonised abilities to handle the multi-domain scenario being explored in VALKYRIES
- **T6.2: Education and training for first aid responses.** The goal of this task is to plan, organise and implement thorough study and analysis of the existing capabilities,

debriefing principles for first aid relate to pan-European exercises and cross-border crises supported by recent technological and procedural tools (hyper-realistic simulations, learning analytics, shared lessons learned, etc.) in support of preparation of a framework for joint education and training for the European Emergency Medical Services. VALKYRIES will develop an advanced education and training kit, including curricula, education methodology and training materials, for first aid responders. The education and training kit will be tested against multinational, cross-sectorial and cross-hierarchical audience to support the process of interoperability building and capabilities harmonisation for first aid responders in case of cross-border and cross-hierarchical disaster situations. Besides these reference harmonized solutions, the conducted research will deliver a map of the related opportunities, the analysis of their regulatory/normalization gaps, and a roadmap for their mitigation.

- **T6.3: Raising practitioner and social awareness.** This task will review the collaborative opportunities for raising the public and practitioner awareness at disaster management situations, which will result in a map of the identified opportunities. Their normalization and regulatory gaps will be analysed, introducing a tentative roadmap for their mitigation. A subset of these opportunities will be selected for addressing the end-user requirements for the reference integration, which among others, will emphasize the digitalization capabilities on the sector, prompt sustainability and rational decision-making, and prevent the impact of secondary hazards. The task will explore synergies with crowdsourcing capabilities. It will take advantage of social media and other disruptive enablers for raising awareness actions (T5.4), so T6.3 will focalize into how to create a major impact in the audience (definition of targeted groups, interests, preparedness, communication continuum models, etc.). In contrast, T5.4 will focalize in the media and the communication channels for pure crowdsourcing and alerting purposes.
- **T6.4: Civil-Military cooperation.** The goal of this task is to explore the role of CIMIC, particularly in the case of large-scale cross-border disasters with mass casualties as a key factor for successful crisis management. The Consortium will analyse lessons learned from previous operations and will identify main interoperability gaps among different actors engaged in managing crises. Besides, as a result of the task implementation, the Consortium will suggest improvements in doctrinal/procedural, operational and tactical documents and instruments for civil-military collaboration. State-of-the-art and growing opportunities on CIMIC will be mapped and analysed, revealing regulatory/normalization needs and suggesting a tentative EU-level roadmap for their mitigation. A subset of the identified opportunities will be selected and harmonized towards serving the SIGRUN reference integration, including doctrinal/protocol amendments, extensions, etc., and/or supportive tools, their effectiveness.
- **T6.5: Civil protection and aid volunteerism.** This task will explore the current and ongoing opportunities for cross-sectorial cooperation, emphasizing the collaboration between first aid response teams with other Civilian Protection and volunteering platforms. This will reveal a map of opportunities, that once analysed will return to point out normalization and regulatory gaps. The task will also propose a roadmap for their mitigation. A subset of these opportunities will be reference harmonized for being deployed at the reference integration. VALKYRIES shall proceed to examine these opportunities and elaborate an Ontology of first responder's procedures and

techniques, more specifically in the first aid field. That shall be done to facilitate the mobility of Volunteers from one Chapter to another, without the need for extensive re-training. The task will also be deeding in the ad hoc engagement of in situ volunteers for supporting the first response teams while waiting for resources and reinforcements.

4. Introduction

4.1. Objective

As described in the project's harmonisation framework document (D2.5), the defined VALKYRIES harmonisation process has three main stages, as shown in the figure below:

Figure 2 - VALKYRIES harmonisation process

The first stage of the harmonisation process is the description and analysis of the existing state-of-the-art.

The aim of this document is to complete this first stage by exploring new opportunities through an analysis of the existing landscape considering a cross-border, cross-sectorial and cross-hierarchical situation in first aid response.

4.2. Scope

The goal of this report is to provide an overview of the current state of preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration opportunities for first aid response to multi-casualty disasters.

It combines the results from the studies carried out in the framework of the tasks T.6.1 Resource Federation and trusted information sharing, T6.2 Education and Training for first aid responses, T6.3 Raising practitioner and social awareness, T6.4 Civil-Military Cooperation and T6.5 Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism.

Besides, the WP6 partners carried out desk research to identify the State-of-the-art in the area of research: relevant existing guidelines, literature, experiences, education and training (E&T) programmes and curriculums for First Aid Responders (FARs), as well as standards, procedures and protocols for first aid responses and for collaboration between medical teams and other first responders.

The focus is on in cross-border, cross-sectorial and cross-hierarchical context.

Moreover, mapping the preparedness of the first aid response at the EU and national level was carried out in the project partner countries that are contributors to T6.2 Education and Training for first aid responses: Bulgaria, Greece, Spain, Portugal, Slovakia and Norway.

Analysis of lessons learned from previous crisis management operations were carried out to identify needs for improving main E&T, regulatory gaps and collaboration opportunities in first aid response activities/capacities, Civil Military Cooperation activities, etc.

The perceptions and needs for education, training and collaboration among the first aid responders have been identified, as well via the survey among first responders.

This final and updated version of D6.1, deliverable D6.5, differs in many aspects from the first version. The main changes and new developments are summarised in the following rows.

In the deliverable D6.5 the general updates at the WP6 level are related to the following. First, the section Future steps was deleted. Besides, a section for presentation of WP6 survey was included and the questionnaire for survey was added as an annex to the deliverable. Moreover, a section Legal barriers and ethical concerns was added. Finally, a new section WP6 conclusions was added to the deliverable which presents the distribution of identified gaps and harmonization opportunities by each task.

In the following rows the specific contribution of each task to update the content of the deliverable is presented.

Contribution from T6.1

- Improve the format of the document;
- Add references missing.

Contribution from T6.2

- Editing of the whole deliverable, improving the format
- Check of missing/wrong references and fixing the right ones;
- The table of content of D6.5 was changed and updated;
- The national case studies of E&T landscape were updated and edited.

Contribution from T6.3

- In D6.5 the table of content was changed in the whole deliverable.
- Regarding T6.3, the chapter related to Raising practitioner and social awareness, was completely changed, renamed and reviewed (chapter 5.4).
- In chapter 7.2 Task conclusions, subchapter 7.2.3, task conclusions were added with one more paragraph.

Contribution from T6.4

- Revising and editing of the whole deliverable, improving the text.
- The table of content was changed in the whole deliverable.
- The chapters related to Civil-military cooperation, was revised and edited (chapter 5.4, paragraph 7.2.4)

Contribution from T6.5

- In the D6.5 the research of information about landscape concerning the specific tool of T6.5 (Civil protection and Aid Volunteerism) has been further investigated with more careful analysis of documents and specific literature.

4.3. Methodology

This methodology is common to WP4, WP5 and WP6 and the same explanation is done for documents D4.5, D4.5 and D4.6.

This first stage by exploring opportunities through an analysis of the existing landscape of emerging preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters has followed this methodology:

Steps of the methodology:

1. Define the scope of the landscape and the document.
2. Divide the analysis into areas of knowledge limited by the scope of the tasks.
3. Identify the state of the art of each of the areas. Based on:
 - Personal experience
 - Scientific studies
 - Reference standards and guidance
 - Expert consultation
 - Etc.

There is a special methodology section on consultation strategy (see point 4.4).

4. Filter the information on the basis on:
 - The scope of the task
 - Focused mainly on VALKYRIES use cases and
 - Focused mainly on the countries involved.
5. Identify future areas of improvement, where technologies are moving forward and what the next steps in these areas will be.
6. Pre-identify the needs of end-users and responders.
7. Pre identify opportunities for improvement
8. Identifying legal barriers that may affect the development of these opportunities
9. Finally, develop conclusions to outline the next steps in terms of opportunities in each of the areas.

4.4. Consultation strategy

The VALKYRIES project is committed to analysing, improving, and developing infrastructures, and protocols and raising data exchange standardisation and harmonisation tactics that are able to increase the effectiveness and interoperability in emergency situations, such as those prevailing in operation of first aid vehicles or cross-frontier disaster response.

Three work streams will be developed in the project: First Responder Technologies and Equipment (KARA), First Responder Procedures and Operation (HERJA), and First Responder Collaboration and Training (EIR).

According to the general strategy of the VALKYRIES project, contained in the VALKYRIES D1.7 Consultation strategy, a common consultation strategy was designed for those 3 work streams of the project.

4.4.1. Objective and motivation of the WP6 consultation

- **Objective:** generation of a report describing the procedural and operational opportunities identified and assessed regarding the work streams.
- **Motivation:** transversely to the different work packages outlined in the project, acquiring the vision from external experts plays a pivotal role, as it will lead to drive the harmonization of protocols and technologies consistently with the project objectives.

4.4.2. Tools and methods

Questionnaire distributed among technical and operational managers of different EU emergency services.

Three questionnaires were defined by WP4, WP5 and WP6 researchers, oriented respectively to each of the project's work streams:

- WP4 (KARA): Technologies and Equipment for first aid responders
- WP5 (HERJA): Procedures and Operation for first aid responders
- WP6 (EIR): Collaboration and Training for first aid responders

4.4.3. Targeted WP6 questionnaire stakeholders

- First round: first responders' partners of the consortium, of the EAB and of linked projects.
- Second round: emergency services potentially involved in responding to mass casualty incidents or disasters in the EU. Each Emergency Service participating in the study would provide a single response to the WP6 questionnaire. These results, regarding the situation at the EU level, are included in this final version of deliverable D6.1 (D5.6).

4.4.4. Facilitators

Valkyries project researchers (emergency services contact and questionnaire distribution).

4.4.5. Timing

- Distribution and completion of the first round of surveys: 27 May to 6 June 2022.
- Distribution and completion of the second round of surveys: 27 October to 30 November 2022.

4.4.6. Data storage

The collected data will be cloud-stored in the general repository of the project. After the project end, the report will be stored in the project official website to be used upon request for future actions related to the project objectives.

4.4.7. Data analysis

The objective assessment was made on the basis of the information gathered from the consulted Emergency Services.

The data was analysed and evaluated by the VALKYRIES WP6 tasks leaders in order to extract policy and recommendations on the possible exploitation of VALKYRIES solution.

The results are always presented in an aggregated form, so that it will not be possible to identify the individual responses of each service.

4.4.8. Reporting

The results will be accessible for:

- VALKYRIES researchers throughout the project life cycle.
- Reporting back to the Emergency Services consulted (if they are interested).

Other related projects and third parties upon request it once the project is finished, under the terms established in the project's intellectual property agreement of VALKYRIES' s project.

5. Tasks chapters

As a result of the work of the WP6 tasks, and in order to structure the results in a clear and homogeneous way, the overview of cooperation, education and training for first aid response is presented in the following sections:

- Resource Federation and trusted information sharing, reflecting the findings of the task T6.1
- Education and Training for first aid responses, reflecting the findings of the task T6.2
- Raising practitioner and social awareness, reflecting the findings of the task T6.3
- Civil-Military Cooperation, reflecting the findings of the task T6.4
- Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism, reflecting the findings of the task T6.5

5.1. Resource Federation and trusted information sharing

Task 6.1 ensures the definition of secure protocols for information sharing in cross-sector, cross-border, and cross-hierarchical environments. This information sharing must be done quickly since, in emergency scenarios, the decisions made based on this information must be as effective and efficient as possible. In addition, considering the speed of sharing, it is necessary to preserve the security of these data so that they cannot be read or modified. However, in specific scenarios, security may have to be dispensed with in favour of obtaining the data to make a priority decision; these cases will be considered throughout this task and the current ways to resolve them.

Information sharing can be done at different levels:

1. If the actors are at the same level and may or may not belong to different organizations (cross-sectorial).
2. If the actors are at a different level, information flows vertically to positions with more responsibility (cross-hierarchical).
3. If the actors belong to different organizations and countries whose command scheme is not shared, it is necessary to find a common point for information sharing (cross-border).
4. If the actors come from same type of organisations but different countries, these must be a shared knowledge database for common purposes.

A series of techniques are collected to build and deploy a common framework to meet the different needs of each of these scenarios and future upgrades.

The different techniques currently available for information sharing and privatization are discussed below. On the one hand, several methods are dedicated to information sharing between other organizations. These techniques include single sign-on authentication such as OAuth or Shibboleth, allowing users from different organizations to authenticate and authorize systems belonging to the parallel organization. On the other hand, new methods for sending information in encrypted form are described as a fundamental pillar of security in this type of environment. In addition to maintaining the origin and privacy of the information, it is necessary to maintain the integrity and availability of the required data. To keep data integrity, techniques such as Blockchain infrastructure will be applied to provide traceability, while obtaining the

highest possible data availability, load balancing techniques and automatic network configuration are being studied.

Finally, solutions that currently exist in the form of frameworks are studied and how they can be applied to the current Valkyries environment.

5.1.1. Inter-institutional collaboration

Sharing data between different organizations **and/or countries** is necessary to handle disasters that may arise correctly. To share this information, the framework must organize the relative information of each institution through the applications used and homogenize them so that they can be obtained by any other organization that needs it. For this purpose, a metadata system will collect the different addresses where the applications store the information. In this way, there will be no data collection by the Valkyries system but a series of nodes that contain everything related to obtaining specific knowledge. In this way, the centralization of information is avoided, and a resilient data network can be created.

However, it is necessary to consider certain restrictions regarding authorization levels for accessing information. Thus, each user must be able to access only and exclusively the communication for which they have been authorized and which helps solve the problem assigned to them.

On the other hand, post-catastrophe data sharing can be an exciting point to improve the different methodologies applied or the decisions taken. More data allows the creation of automatic systems that learn from previous experiences and offer the most optimal solutions for the following situations.

Blockchain technology has the possibility of creating a distributed ledger with specific access to certain members and provide more effective collaboration between different entities. Each entity may be described by a unique ID and iterate through multiple data without tampering or altering the datasets. Each actor can have specific privileges and access points to the distributed databases and each transaction can be monitored through an open blockchain explorer. So, each recording or reset of data can be visible by all parties involved or specific IDs. In order to limit access to sensitive data and at the same time conduct better knowledge distribution and provide an open collaboration between different actors or organizations.

5.1.2. Trusted information sharing

The information sharing can be defined as the exchange of data between participants; furthermore, information sharing implies that the information leaves the controlled and secured environment in which it is stored and travel through a dynamic and unsecure environment. The information sharing is an essential pillar for security awareness and emergency actuations, and that is the reason why it is extremely important to secure these communications, particularly in the health and emergency contexts, as the information shared is personal and sensitive, and any inconvenience or delay while sharing the information could be fatal as there are lives at risk. A secure network with specific authorization policies can be enabled with the utter purpose to restrict access to certain information and data sharing. Thus, controversial data can't be reached from non-regulated third parties. A framework or policy engine should be established to prevent data from non-authorized persons and following the **EU Reg. 2016/679** on General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) obligations.

In addition to the challenge of securing communications, information sharing is strictly regulated in EU, with regulations such as the GDPR (<https://gdpr.eu/what-is-gdpr/>, s.f.) which imposes obligations to the organizations which target, collect, or share data related to EU citizens/ in EU in order to boost a responsible circulation of personal information

The Trusted Information Sharing (TIS) (2) is a complex combination of technical and legal issues, among others. Typically, the TIS is based on the following basic principles (3):

- Withholdings
- Trusted Usage
- Controlled dissemination and processing
- Transparency
- Security
- Legitimate ground
- Principle of minimisation.

5.1.3. Resource federation

The resource federation means to share information, access points and communication technology resources beyond independent organizations. By applying the resource federation, multiple aspects are optimized, not only on the physical level, but also in the communication and security levels.

Multiple initiatives are implementing federation mechanism with specific objectives, such as the FIRE initiative (4), therefore, the federation is a useful way to achieve scalable, diverse, cost-efficient and sustainable solutions.

Nevertheless, federating resources across different domains, multiple entities and federation levels involves many technical, operational and regulatory issues that have to be addressed.

To achieve a fully functional federation for ICT resources, many aspects should be addressed, such as descriptions, authorization policies, access control, identity management frameworks, legal frameworks, and available solutions with the added difficulty value of addressing all these aspects in a multi-national and multi-sectorial scenario.

Regulatory aspects of data federation mainly concern privacy and security issues to be addressed by design and by default. The paramount legislative initiative is still the EU Reg. 2016/679 on General Regulation on Data Protection (GDPR) that introduces compliance obligations for personal data processing, addressing the challenge of ensuring the so-called privacy-by-design and privacy-by-default (5) through the development of a risk assessment aimed at introducing technical and organisational safeguards in the given scenario. In case of development of AI-based tools such an assessment, currently not binding yet, shall then include further requirements aiming to protect and empower individuals and groups fundamental rights (6).

Considering the principles stated in the GDPR, we may remark that in terms of data subjects' rights, a better control of possible personal data included in the federated setup can be ensured from the decentralisation of the distributed datasets. This is particularly relevant for cross-border scenarios, like VALKYRIES, where national laws could require tailored conditions to

process sensitive data under article 9, para 4 GDPR, even if they are collected and processed as pseudonymised ones.

During the application of federated learning techniques (7) (8) (9), indeed, if the shared parameters are anonymous, it could be easier process data that are distributed in different jurisdictions to train models. Conversely, it could be more difficult to validate the developed model, if access to training datasets is not allowed to the developer. Self-regulatory tools can be useful to address this profile in case of tools to be developed and validated in such a context. Furthermore, the processing of federated data could better fulfil the principle of minimisation as the training model could better select all the data but only those that are necessary for a given purpose. At the same time, bias assessment shall take into account also the risks of model poisoning and introduce specific tests to protect the whole setup (10).

In terms of security issues, the ENISA Report on Data Protection Engineering¹ refers to Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) to protect federated setups from breaches, like unauthorised access and use, or malware attacks. A trusted execution environment (TEE) is a tamper-resistant processing environment on the main processor of a device. Running parallel to the operating system and using both hardware and software, a TEE is intended to be more secure than the traditional processing environment (11).

To summarize, federated learned techniques can be applied only after a deep assessment in terms of data protection and security of the setup, as well as in terms of trustworthiness of the developed model.

5.1.4. Data federation techniques between organizations

This section presents in depth the techniques identified above, considering the needs of the project assuming cross-sector, cross-border, and cross-hierarchy hybrid dimensions. In addition, hybrid solutions are compared among those available from the entities and actors participating in the communications. Then, it identifies and compares the options selecting the most achievable one to ensure reliable communication.

In this sense, gaps between the communication layers and taking into consideration the applications, alternatives will be identified for each in order to detect the opportunities applicable in multiple-victim scenarios. A subset of the opportunities will be harmonized enabling the project reference integration (SIGRUN).

5.1.4.1. OAuth

OAuth is an open standard from IETF used for resource authorization and federation (12). This standard allows a user sharing data from one organization (service provider) to another site (consumer) without sharing additional sensitive information. Based on that, it is widely used in scenarios where users aim to access a particular webpage and, for that, they log in with the

¹ A trusted execution environment (TEE) is a tamper-resistant processing environment on the main processor of a device. Running parallel to the operating system and using both hardware and software, a TEE is intended to be more secure than the traditional processing environment. See ENISA, *Data Protection Engineering*, 2022, p. 16, <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/data-protection-engineering>.

credentials of other organizations, such as Google, Facebook, Microsoft or Twitter. Thus, users can access the resources of the desired web without revealing their personal information, as OAuth grants this access sharing a minimum set of information about the user.

The first version of the standard, OAuth 1.0, was released in 2007. However, and since this version resulted insecure, OAuth 2.0 was released in 2012. It is relevant to note that these versions are not compatible between them, being the latest one preferred and implemented in most online services.

The OAuth was established at the architecture document (D2.8) as the reference authentication standard applicable to SIGRUN.

The standard defines different roles (13):

- Resource Owner (RO): entity able to grant access to a restricted resource (e.g., the final user)
- Resource Server (RS): server that contains the resources protected by access tokens
- Client (C): application that queries a protected resource in the name of the RO with its authorization
- Authorization Server (AS): server that emits access tokens to the client after authenticating the RO and gaining authorization

Additionally, the protocol presents several endpoints. For the authorization process, the standard defines two endpoints for the authorization server. First, the Authorization endpoint is used by C to obtain authorization from RO using a user-agent redirection (in HTTP communication). The second endpoint corresponds to the Token endpoint, which is used by C to exchange an authorization grant to get an access token, typically based on client authentication. Finally, there is a client endpoint, known as Redirection endpoint, which is used by the AS to return responses containing the authorization credentials for C using user-agent redirection.

Once presented the endpoints intervening in the process, it is relevant to present the communication flow between entities defined by the protocol:

Figure 3 - OAuth 2.0 abstract communication flow

- (A): C asks authorization from RO (directly or via AS)
- (B): C receives an authorization grant (a credential that represents the authorization from RO), expressed using a grant type
- (C): C solicits an access token, authenticating against AS and presenting the authorization grant from step (B)
- (D): AS authenticates C. If the authorization grant is valid, it emits an access token
- (E): C asks for the resource from RS and authenticates itself using the access token
- (F): RS verifies the token and, if it is valid, it serves the query

After presenting the general behaviour of the protocol, it is relevant to deepen in the different grant types defined by the standard. The first one, known as “Authorization Code”, is obtained using an AS as intermediary between C and RO. This approach is used to obtain and refresh tokens. It offers the ability to authenticate C, directly sending a token to C.

The second grant type is known as “Implicit”, which is a simplified authorization code flow, optimized for clients using a web browser. It is implicit since intermediary credentials are not generated (such as authorization codes). However, when the access token is emitted, AS does not authenticate the client. In this sense, this grant type improves client efficiency as the number of roundtrips to get the access token gets reduced.

The third type is known as “Resource Owner Password Credentials”. In this grant type, the RO credentials (e.g., user and password) can be used directly as authorization grant to obtain an access token. This approach should only be used when there is a strong trust relationship between RO and C, and when other authorization grant types are not available, as it is the case for Authorization code. Although this type requires direct access from C to RO credentials, they are only used for one query, being transmitted to get an access token.

Finally, the last grant type is “Client Credentials”, which can be used as authorization grant when the authorization scenario is limited to resources protected under the control of the client, or protected resources previously agreed with the AS.

Moreover, blockchain offers a system to authenticate users through a distributed ledger. There can be an interaction with the OAuth blockchain-based tokens so that we can record and authenticate at any given moment the user that is accessing the application and at same time we are securing in a more efficient way the data transmitted to the system.

A new framework utilizing the possibility that the tokens will be decentralised making use of the opportunities that blockchain offers.

5.1.4.2. Shibboleth

The Shibboleth protocol offers single sign-on (SSO) capabilities, offering user authentication and authorization. It is commonly used for data federation between different organizations or institutions, typically universities and public service organizations, where the users just log in once and can access different services from various institutions. This introduces the possibility for cross-domain SSO without the requirement of validating the credentials of the users each time they aim to access a resource. Shibboleth 2.0, the latest version of the project, is based on SAML 2.0.

Shibboleth can also be enabled with identity management through a layer of blockchain. Using the capabilities of smart contracts, we can identify multiple organisations and it will leverage the data transferring among the involved parties.

So, besides the Shibboleth each party can be also recorded into blockchain, and each data transferred through the application be recorded and be publicly accessible.

Shibboleth defines several main elements, subsequently presented:

- WAYF (Where Are You From): this element discovers which is the Identity Provider of the user that wants to be authenticated
- Resource: element that the user wants to access
- Identity Provider (IdP): it manages the authentication and users' attributes
- Service Provider (SP): it manages the resources

Once presented the key elements of the Shibboleth architecture, Figure 6 presents how these elements communicate:

Figure 4 - Shibboleth abstract communication flow

1. First, the user asks the Assertion Consumer Service from the SP to access a particular resource. Since the SP does not know the user or its home organization, it redirects the request to the WAYF
2. The SP redirects the request to the WAYF
3. The WAYF directly asks the user about its home organization
4. The user responds to the WAYF
5. The WAYF redirects the request to the Handle Service (HS) in the home organization
6. Since the HS does not know if the user is legitimate, it asks for authentication to the user
7. The user provides its credentials

8. The HS validates the credentials and then, it redirects the request to the target (SP), together with a handle. Since the ACS does not know about the attributes of this user, it asks the Attribute Authority (AA) of the IDP
9. The SP asks the Attribute Authority of the IdP sending the handle
10. The AA of the IdP sends the list of attributes the user has allowed to release. Then, the SP can finally grant access to the resource, based on the attributed provided by the AA.

According to the previously presented steps, the authentication process is performed by Shibboleth from steps one to eight, while steps nine and ten focus on authorization actions.

Although Shibboleth is used by several services, it still presents some downsides:

- Shibboleth requires the implementation of the WAYF, IdP and SP modules, which is not a “turnkey” solution, thus requiring dedicated implementation, sometimes from scratch.
- Maintaining the operation requires a whole set of assertions, entity IDs (and order signing keys), certificates, attribute mappings, etc, which requires a heavier effort in performing administrative/bureaucratic actions to authentication running properly.
- The integration with Web Servers is poorly supported requiring dedicated development/integration: As some examples: the Nginx has no integration module; IIS has some compatibility issues with IIS versions, similar with Windows Server. (It does work fine with Apache)
- To facilitate the sharing of session state, it is necessary to use storage plugins (like Memcache or Redis), which are 3rd-party and are very depend on the version of the Shibboleth libs used. Which also requires a lot of effort to maintain and update as newer version are released.

5.1.5. Other data federation Techniques

5.1.5.1. SAML 2.0

The Security Assertions Markup Language (SAML) (14) is an open standard based on XML for web services that allow exchanging authentication and authorization information between a service provider (SP) and an identity provider (IdP). Currently, the latest version of this protocol, published in 2005, is SAML 2.0, which works as a Single-Sign-On (SSO) scheme. It relies on the trusted relationship between identity and service providers, and the process is transparent for the users, allowing them to access the applications without providing additional credentials.

Figure 5 - SSO with SAML 2.0

In this direction, Figure 3 summarizes the functioning of SSO, composed of the following steps:

1. The user authenticates to the Identity Server
2. The Identity Server authenticates the users against the user store.
3. Whenever the users request an external service, the Access Manager produces a single use token or authentication assertion which validates the request and the session proceeds to be established.

SAML works as a hierarchical protocol, defining different components:

- Assertions (XML): information regarding authentication, attributes, and user authorization
- Protocols (XML and processing rules): requests and responses to pack the Assertions
- Bindings (HTTP and SOAP): rules to encapsulate SAML messages in transport protocols
- Profiles: Protocols, Bindings and Assertions are combined using Profiles

Particularly, Assertions can contain different types of statements:

- Authentication statements: indicates if a user has been authenticated
- Attribute statements: information about users' statements
- Authorization decision statements: indicates if the user has permission to access a certain service

Figure 6 - SAML abstract communication flow

Figure 4 presents a summary of the message exchange performed by SAML 2.0 to request a resource, composed of the following steps:

1. The user queries for a resource to SP
2. The user is redirected to the SSO Service
3. The user authenticates against the IdP of the SSO Service
4. Response containing the Authentication Statement
5. The response is sent to the Assertion Consumer Service
6. Once the Assertion is verified, the user is redirected
7. New request to the SP including the Authorization Assertion
8. The user obtains the requested resource

5.1.5.2. OpenID

OpenID (15) Connect 1.0 is an identity layer over the OAuth2.0 protocol. It works in a similar way to the standalone OpenID 2.0, but in an API-friendly way, making it usable by native and mobile applications.

Furthermore, OpenID allows to use multiple signing and encryption mechanisms, and the current versions of OpenID Connect and OAuth 2.0 capabilities are integrated with in the protocol.

The OpenID is supported on standard protocols, making it more maintainable and have a less bureaucratic configuration, supports the implementations of providers and clients in several languages, and provides a more complete solution for attribute/identity mapping.

While SAML is older, and for that reason more widely used, is also less oriented towards mobile user. OpenID, on the other hand, is newer and better support, mobile users. Another difference is that OpenID uses JWT (JSON Web Token; standard RFC7519) (16) which can be directly mapped to objects, while SAML assertions uses XML, which does not provide an embedded document to object mapping. The JWT is also better adapted for HTTP environment.

Nevertheless, OpenID is not widely used, and, because of that, this deliverable does not address this protocol in a comprehensive way, and is not as flexible in terms of authentication as pure SSO.

The recommended approach established in the architecture relies on the OAuth and OpenID.

5.1.6. Analysis of cryptography mechanisms

In recent years, communications have become indispensable to society. Mainly due to the expansion of the Internet, and more recently to the growth of mobile communications, we now have the opportunity to communicate and transmit information quickly and efficiently. The type of information being sent ranges from personal messages in e-mails or instant messages to susceptible details such as banking transactions. All this has made security and privacy in communications a point of great interest, not only for companies and governments but also for citizens.

Security in communications is achieved using cryptographic techniques. Cryptography is the study of algorithms, protocols, and systems used to protect information and make communications secure through mathematical techniques. The concept of communication security refers to the set of properties that must be guaranteed to protect data while maintaining, among others, the confidentiality, integrity, and authentication of sent data. These properties are secured using cryptographic techniques.

Cryptographic techniques for encrypting/decrypting information are classified into symmetric and asymmetric cryptography. Symmetric cryptography uses a single key to encrypt/decrypt data. This poses the problem of sending that key because it must be shared by both the sender and the receiver of the message. In contrast, asymmetric cryptography does not use a single key, the encryption and decryption keys being different. In this case, both the sender and the receiver have two keys, a public key that can be shared without any problem and a private key that is not shared. Both types of cryptography are computationally expensive, but asymmetric cryptography is much more costly. In practice, it is only used to exchange a key that will be used to encrypt communications symmetrically.

Traditionally, these cryptographic algorithms have been implemented in software. However, because they are used in many situations, processor manufacturers have started to include hardware implementations of them, thus relieving the processor from doing this work. Although software encryption/decryption is considerably cheaper since it does not require any specific hardware, hardware encryption allows for speeding up these tasks and is also more secure since the encryption/decryption process is kept separate from the rest of the machine's functions.

Modern symmetric encryption algorithms mix transposition and permutation, while public-key algorithms rely more on complex mathematical operations. Any secure transfer system based on cryptography should cover all four points mentioned above but usually does not do so in its entirety. Thus, symmetric key systems offer confidentiality but none of the other factors. In contrast, public key systems provide authenticity, integrity, confidentiality in sending and non-repudiation if associated with a digital signature.

Cryptography allows messages to be encrypted using a cryptographic method, which guarantees privacy, i.e., only the sender and the recipient(s) can access the content of the message. In

addition, a message must be capable of being subscribed, i.e., the person receiving it must be able to verify whether the sender is the person he claims to be and identify whether a message may have been modified. Current cryptographic methods are very secure and efficient and are based on one or more keys. The key is a sequence of characters, which can contain letters, digits and symbols (like a password), and which is converted into a number, used by cryptographic methods to encode and decode data, and this is a function of the activity to be carried out; since, although any algorithm works in any operation, there will always be one that is best suited to the action to be carried out. Figure 7 shows the basic data encryption flow.

To generate a secure data transmission (17), we must have a secure channel. For this, we must use techniques so that the data sent from one computer to another is guaranteed to be understood by the receiver and is identical to that sent by the sender and is encrypted to prevent it from being interpreted by people outside the communication. This process is transparent to the user, does not increase the size of the packets and can only be decrypted by those who have the key to doing so. With this, we will be ensuring:

- Authenticity of the users.
- Confidentiality.
- Integrity.
- Non-repudiation.

To understand the relevance of cryptography in digital media (Zeng, 2011), it is essential to understand its concept, methods and origins, and the scope it has acquired in computer security. The digital media on which this project focuses constitute a series of typification that need to be applied and related to data protection. Therefore, this theoretical framework aims to describe these concepts to achieve the main objective. It refers to how cryptography, which protects digital information, works by using cyphers or codes to write something secret in confidential documents and data circulating in local networks or on the Internet. Its use is as old as writing itself. The Romans used codes to hide their war planes from those who were not supposed to know about them so that only people who knew the meaning of these codes could decipher the hidden message. With the creation and evolution of computers, the encryption of information became widely spread, used and modified, and constituted with mathematical algorithms. In addition to maintaining user security, cryptography preserves the integrity of the network, user authentication, and that of the sender, the receiver and the timeliness of the message or access. Some important terms in cryptography:

- Clear text: unencrypted message or information
- Cryptogram: encrypted message
- Cryptosystem: a complete system consisting of plaintexts, cryptograms, encryption keys, and encryption-decryption algorithms.
- Cryptanalysis: a technique that attempts to compromise the security of a cryptosystem by either decrypting a text without its key or obtaining the key from a cryptographic key.

Figure 7 - Cryptographic system. Simplified functionality

There are two fundamental types of cryptosystems:

- Symmetric or private key cryptosystems: the same key is used for encryption and decryption, which must be known to the authorised parties to the communication, and only to them.
- Asymmetric or public-key cryptosystems: use a double key (K_{public} , K_{secret}) so that one encrypts and the other decrypts, and in many cases, they are interchangeable.

5.1.6.1. Symmetric cryptography

Symmetric cryptography (19) is based on specific algorithms to decrypt and encrypt (hide) documents. They are groups of different algorithms related to each other to maintain the confidential connection of the information. In this case, the encryption password is the same that is used to access the data, it is a little more insecure, but it is very functional in certain cases. Although this algorithm also allows the creation of several keys, a file can be encrypted with two or more passwords, reducing the probability of loss of information. For such an algorithm to be considered reliable, it must meet some basic requirements:

- Known cryptogram (ciphertext), neither the plaintext nor the key can be obtained.
- Once the plaintext and the ciphertext are known, it must be more expensive in time or money to decrypt the key than the possible value of the information obtained by third parties.

All classical cryptographic systems can be considered symmetric, and the main current symmetric algorithms are DES, IDEA and RC5. The main disadvantages of symmetric methods are the distribution of keys, the danger of many people having to know the same key, and the difficulty of storing and protecting many different keys.

The DES encryption algorithm works with symmetric keys, was developed in 1977 by IBM, and is based on a mono-alphabetic system, with an encryption algorithm consisting of the successive application of several permutations and substitutions. Initially, the text to be encrypted is subjected to a permutation, with an input block of 64 bits (or a multiple of 64), to be subsequently subjected to the action of two main functions, a permutation function with 8-bit input and a substitution function with 5-bit input, in a process consisting of 16 encryption stages. In general, DES uses a 64-bit symmetric key, of which 56 bits are used for encryption, while the remaining 8 bits are for parity and are used for error detection in the process.

DES is no longer standard and was cracked in January 1999 with a computing power of approximately 250 billion trials in one second.

Today, Triple-DES is used with a 128-bit key and is compatible with DES, as seen above. This new algorithm takes a 128-bit key and splits it into two 64-bit keys as follows:

- A first cypher is applied to the document to be encrypted using the first key, C1.
- Second encryption with the second key, C2, is applied to the result (called ANTIDES).
- And a third cypher with the first key, C1, is applied to the result.

RC5 this system is the successor of RC4, which consisted of XORing the message with a vector assumed to be random and derived from the key. At the same time, RC5 uses another operation, called data dependency, which applies shifts to the data to obtain the encrypted message. IDEA works with 64-bit blocks of text, continually operating on 16-bit numbers using operations such as XOR and integer addition and multiplication. The decryption algorithm is very similar to the encryption algorithm, making it easy and fast to program. So far, it has never been broken, providing strong security against brute force attacks (trial and error or dictionaries). This algorithm is freely available and is not subject to any restrictions or national permissions, so it has been widely spread in systems such as UNIX and mail encryption programs such as PGP.

Among the most widely used symmetric cryptography standards is AES, also known as Rijndael, a block cypher standard used for the encryption of electronic data established in 2001 by the US National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). It consists of a series of cyphers with different modes of operation and block sizes developed by Belgian cryptographers Vincent Rijmen and Joan Daemen. During the selection process for the future standard, these cryptographers submitted various proposals, and NIST selected three members of the Rijndael series with a block size of 128 bits but different key lengths: 128, 192 and 256 bits.

Since then, the use of AES has spread worldwide and has replaced the Data Encryption Standard (DES) published and used since 1977. The algorithm used in AES is a symmetric key algorithm, i.e., the key used for data encryption is the same as the key used for decryption. On 26 May 2002, following approval by the US Secretary of Commerce, AES, which is included in the ISO/IEC 18033-3 standard, became effective as a US government standard. AES is used in many encryption packages and is the first and only publicly available cypher used in cryptographic modules approved by the US National Security Agency (NSA) to encrypt top-secret information.

AES (Mellu, 2011) is based on the substitution-permutation lattice principle, and all operations are performed on a 4 x 4 column matrix of order greater than bytes, denoted as a state. Most computations performed in AES are performed on what is known in abstract algebra as a finite body, finite field or Galois field. AES encryption is performed by iteratively applying (transformation rounds) a series of operations that convert the input, called plaintext, into the output, called ciphertext. The number of transformation rounds is specified by the size of the key used, as shown below: 128 bits = 10 rounds of transformation, 192 bits = 12 rounds of transformation, and 256 bits = 14 rounds of transformation. The decryption process is similar, but in this case, a set of inverse transformation rounds is applied to convert the ciphertext into the original plaintext using the same key. In each transformation round, 4 types of operation are applied, which are detailed below.

- Key expansion: AES needs a different key for each round derived from the initial key. For this purpose, the AES key planner is used, which expands the original key into several other round keys. In total, AES uses several 128-bit keys equal to the number of rounds plus one more.

- Round 1: This is known as AddRoundKey, and each byte of the state is combined with a byte of the round key using the XOR operation.
- Rounds up to 9, 11 or 13 (depending on the key size): The following four operations are performed in each round:
- SubBytes: Non-linear substitution step in which each byte is replaced by another byte based on a predefined table (Rijndael S-box).
- ShiftRows: Permutation step where all but the first row of the state is shifted a certain number of times cyclically.
- MixColumns: A linear transformation operation that combines the four bytes of each column in the state columns. Multiplies each of the columns of the state matrix by a fixed polynomial like the Hill2 cypher.
- AddRoundKey: The same operation as in Round 1 is performed.
- Final stage (Round 10, 12 or 14): The SubBytes, ShiftRows and AddRoundKey operations are applied.

5.1.6.2. Asymmetric cryptography

Asymmetric cryptography, on the other hand, is more powerful. In addition to allowing confidentiality, it will enable us to provide an authentication service and ensure the integrity of messages without the need to transmit a secret key (only the public key must be known, **therefore, it** can be transmitted over an insecure channel as there is no problem if it is known). Of course, the choice of keys and the algorithms that use them for encryption and decryption in asymmetric cryptography is trivial. They **must** have particular characteristics. The secret key and the public key must be deeply related (what one encrypts, the other decrypts), yet it must be "impossible" to obtain one from the other.

Asymmetric cryptography is based on two different keys, keys that possess a fundamental property: one key can decrypt what the other has encrypted. One of the keys of the pair, called the private key, is used by the owner to encrypt messages, while the other, called the public key, is used to decrypt the message.

The public and private keys have unique mathematical characteristics in such a way that they are always generated simultaneously, in pairs, each of them being intrinsically linked to the other. While the private key must be kept secret by its owner, as it is the basis of the security of the system, the public key is disseminated so that it is available to as many people as possible. There are servers that store, manage and distribute these keys. For a public key algorithm to be considered secure, it must comply with the following points:

- Known ciphertext, it must not be possible to find the plaintext or the private key.
- Knowing the ciphertext (cryptogram) and the plaintext, it must be more expensive in time or money to decrypt the key than the possible value of the information obtained by third parties.
- Once the public key and the plaintext are known, it is not possible to generate a correct cryptogram encrypted with the private key.
- Given a text encrypted with a private key, there is only a public key capable of decrypting it, and vice versa.

The first public key system to appear was the Diffie-Hellman system in 1976, and it was the basis for the development of those that appeared later, among which the RSA (the most widely used today) is worth mentioning. This encryption algorithm by Whitfield Diffie and Martin Hellman was the starting point for asymmetric systems based on public and private keys. Its importance is mainly because it is the beginning of asymmetric systems since, in practice, it is only valid for the exchange of symmetric keys, and with this functionality, it is widely used in the different security systems implemented on the Internet, such as SSL (Secure Socket Layer) and VPN (Virtual Private Network). Mathematically, it is based on the powers of numbers and the mod function (discrete modulus). Combining these two concepts, the discrete power of a number is defined as $Y = X^a \text{ mod } q$. While discrete calculating powers is easy, obtaining their inverse function, the discrete logarithm, does not have an analytical solution for large numbers.

RSA (Somani, 2014) is the best known and most widely used of the public key systems and the fastest of them. It has all the advantages of asymmetric systems, including the digital signature, although it is more helpful in implementing confidentiality when using symmetric systems, as they are faster (Somani, 2014). It is also often used in hybrid approaches to encrypt and send the symmetric key later in encrypted communication. The RSA system is based on the mathematical fact that it is difficult to factor in huge numbers. To the factor, a number, the most logical system consists of dividing it successively by 2, 3, 4, etc., and so on, so that the result of the division is exact, i.e., with a remainder of 0, which means that we already have a divisor of the number. The calculation of these keys is done secretly on the machine where the private key will be stored. Once generated, it is advisable to protect it using a symmetric cryptographic algorithm.

PGP (Pretty Good Privacy) (22) is a project initiated by Phill Zimmerman in 1993 when there was a lack of simple but powerful tools that would allow "ordinary" users to use serious cryptography. Over time PGP has become one of the most popular mechanisms for using cryptography, both for private users and large companies. Its source code has been published, and its use is allowed free of charge for non-commercial purposes. It is already an international standard, RFC 2440, and has many applications (storage encryption, automatic encryption of TCP/IP traffic, etc.). In this text, I will explain what PGP is and its two original and most essential functions: ensuring the confidentiality of a text and the authentication of a sender vis-à-vis the receiver (digital signature).

PGP works with asymmetric cryptography (although, for efficiency reasons, it also uses symmetric cryptography), and its strong point lies in the ease with which common users can generate keys (something that, as I mentioned before, is not trivial at all) and manage them. PGP provides a "keyring", a single file where the user can store all his keys, with the facility to perform key insertion and extraction simply. It also provides a mechanism for key identification and authentication (a certification that a public key belongs to whom it says it does) to prevent "man-in-the-middle attacks". These attacks consist of a person tapping the communication channel and providing us with a false public key of the recipient to whom we wish to send the message. In this case, we would encrypt with this key, and the attacker could decrypt the information, encrypt it with the real public key that has been tapped, and send it to the recipient without anyone being aware of his presence.

PGP allows users to "sign keys" to authenticate keys so that we can trust the authenticity of a key as long as a trusted person sign it. Thus, the "certification authority" of other systems (entities that ensure the authenticity of the keys) in PGP is the users themselves. In addition, each key has a "fingerprint", which is a sequence long enough to be unique but short enough to be communicated orally or written on paper. Thus, if we want to be sure of the authenticity of a key, we only need to ask (e.g., by phone or IRC) the author of the key for the fingerprint of the key. When a secret key is compromised or replaced by a new one (e.g., because the value of the information to be protected requires a more secure algorithm or a longer key), it can be revoked by its author. You only need to generate and distribute a "revocation certificate" to inform PGP users that the key is no longer valid. Of course, to issue such a certificate, it is necessary to have a secret key.

5.1.7. Quantum cryptography

The main security objectives regarding cryptography are that the systems guarantee the following points (512, Terrestrial Trunked Radio (TETRA); Security; Security requirements analysis for modulation enhancements to TETRA):

- to prove the identity of users and networks.
- to ensure confidentiality of communication.
- to ensure integrity of communication.
- to ensure the rights of privacy of the system's users.
- to ensure the correct charging of the system's users.
- to warranty security management.

Great efforts are being made regarding standardization and legal issues related to data protection and secure communication infrastructures. This strong digital transformation of the health sector brings with it a new range of cyber threats that lead to:

- Threats and high-profile cyberattacks that are strongly targeting critical infrastructures, such as hospitals.
- Cybercriminals that are more and more experts, sometimes managing to cause great damage without even detecting the origin of the attack.
- Hybrid conflicts as new area of which there is not much information, but which are posing a problem worldwide.

Even with all the security measures and cryptographic protocols used, the communication infrastructures and critical infrastructures, have been and are every day the victim of multiple cyberattacks, such as the one that targeted the French hospital group 'GHT Coeur Grand Est' which caused GHT to disconnect its hospitals from the network (Toulas, 2022), or the ransomware attack against the "Springhill Medical Centre" that led to the death of a baby (The Wall Street Journal, 2021) due to the unavailability of diverse technical devices during the eight days that the system was shut down.

Added to this, we find that there is the threat of the arrival of quantum computers that will lead to the breakdown of the encryption mechanisms that are used today as stated in the ETSI standard EG 203 310 (26):

- “Symmetric cryptographic strength will be halved, e.g., AES with 128-bit keys giving 128-bit strength will be reduced to 64-bit strength (in other words to retain 128-bit security will require to implement 256-bit keys).
- Elliptical curve cryptography will offer no security.
- RSA based public key cryptography will offer no security.
- The Diffie-Helman-Merkle key agreement protocol will offer no security.”

This coming is increasingly close as IBM has already announced the 127-qubit Eagle processor that could outperform classical computers at simulating nature (27) or the declaration of quantum supremacy announced by China (28).

Figure 8 - (left) IBM 127-qubit Eagle processor from (17) (right) Device schematic of the Zuchongzhi quantum processor from.

In view of this scenario and the new threat posed by the quantum computer, cybercriminals are carrying out “Harvest now, decrypt later” attacks (29) for which sensitive information are being stored now under the current encryption methods and can be then decrypted when quantum computers and / or new mathematical algorithms are available.

Therefore, there is great concern about the future validity of symmetric-key cryptographic algorithms since, as in mobile communications such as Global System for Mobile (GSM) or Terrestrial Trunked Radio (TETRA), there are billions of devices in the world whose security is based on symmetric encryption with encryption keys of length 128 bits or less (30). In this framework, vulnerability analyses such as the one published by ETSI for TETRA (31) will no longer be valid as well as the current definitions of risk, impact and likelihood of an attack.

Currently, great efforts are being invested in two types of solutions that can make a system “quantum-safe”, that is, resistant to attacks perpetrated by a quantum computer using the Shor or Grover algorithms. These solutions are quantum cryptography and post-quantum cryptography (PQC). In the case of the second, PQC, the NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) since 2017 is submitting a series of (classical) cryptographic algorithms to tender in order to evaluate and standardize them (32). The algorithms that have promoted to the third round as finalists (category KEM – Classic McEliece / CRYSTALS-KYBER / NTRU / SABER; category DSA – CRYSTALS-DILITHIUM / FALCON / Rainbow) are based on lattices (except Classic McEliece which is based on codes) and, therefore, on computational assumptions. This could be

an issue since it cannot be guaranteed that an algorithm capable of breaking them will be found either with a quantum computer or with a conventional one.

Regarding the solution with quantum cryptography, which is what this proposal is based on, it is based on the sending and receiving of qubits (i.e., photons with a certain polarization) through ground (fibre optics) or open-air (satellite) channels. Therefore, unlike PQC and classical cryptography, it does not depend on the complexity of mathematical problems, but only depends on the physics of the system and the mechanic-quantum properties and behaviour of the photons. Within the scope of quantum cryptography, the Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) protocol stands out, because it has already been widely demonstrated both on the ground (Yeh, 2007), (Vicente Martin, 2018), (Momtchil Peev), (Masahide Sasaki, 2011) and via satellite (Yu-Ao Chen, 2021), (Juan Yin, 2017). QKD allows the creation of a completely random secret symmetric key between two nodes. These keys are resistant to quantum and classical computers since they do not depend on the computational complexity of a mathematical problem, as we have already mentioned. Furthermore, thanks to the quantum character of the photons (elemental light particles), during the process qubits cannot be copied because it would alter their information content (no cloning property). This allows detection of intruders in the quantum communication channel. Then, generated keys can be used in current ciphering methods (e.g., AES) and communication protocols (GSM, TETRA, Wi-Fi, MCX/LTE, etc.) and combining both encryption methods we achieve a quantum-safe system.

Although there are a large number of scientific publications referring to QKD, there are no specific researches that have focused on applications in the first responder sector. This indicates that there is still a long way to go and a lot to advance in this type of research aimed at the implementation of quantum technologies in critical communications and health services.

5.1.7.1. Quantum Key Distribution process description

Here we roughly describe the steps that make up a QKD protocol (e.g., BB84 protocol) (See Figure 9):

1. Alice generates a random sequence of bits
2. For each bit of the sequence, Alice randomly chooses a base (photon polarization) and encodes the bit giving rise to the qubit. Following the rules given in Figure 9.
 - a. Vertical and horizontal bases encode bit 0 as $|0\rangle$ (horizontal polarization) and 1 as $|1\rangle$ (vertical polarization)
 - b. Diagonal bases encode bit 0 as $|+\rangle$ (polarization 45°) and 1 as $|-\rangle$ (polarization -45°)

Figure 9 - Qubits encoding

3. Alice sends the qubit to Bob, through a quantum channel
4. When Bob receives each photon, he measures by randomly choosing the base. About half the time Bob will choose the same base as Alice and the other half he will choose the opposite base to the one Alice used
5. Base Reconciliation process. Bob makes public the bases in which they have measured (but not the value of the obtained bit) and Alice tells him the positions in which she has used the same base. So, they can locate and remove the bits where the measurements do not match
6. Key Distillation process. They perform a series of classical post-processing processes for error correction and privacy amplification of the key.
7. After the key distillation process, they obtain the final secret symmetric key.

Figure 10 - High level Quantum Key Distribution protocol description

5.1.7.2. Key transmission in a network

Finally, we describe in greater detail the functional process of the key distribution from when a user (or cryptographic application) requests to establish a secure communication with another user of the quantum network until the secret key is received by both users (applications cryptographic).

There are several approaches for transmitting a cryptographic key from user A to user B through N intermediate nodes.

The first method is based on generating QKD keys between contiguous pairs of nodes on the network and transmitting the encryption key using intermediate generated keys from one node to another until it reaches its final destination. In this case, it is a requirement that all intermediate nodes are trusted, since they have knowledge of the encryption key to secure communication. The process of this method has been outlined in Figure 11.

- User A performs a QKD protocol with the next node on the network (1), with which it shares a key k_{A1} . This key will be the one used at the end of the process by users A and B to encrypt their communications.
- Node 1 performs a QKD protocol with the next node on the network (2), with which it shares a k_{12} key
- Node 1 retransmits the k_{A1} key to node 2, encrypting it using an OTP (One Time Path) or XOR protocol with the k_{12} key.

- Node 2 decrypts the key using k_{12} (as shown in the equation below). Now 2 knows k_{A1}

$$(k_{A1} \oplus k_{12}) \oplus k_{12} = k_{A1}$$

- Node 2 performs a QKD protocol with the next node on the network (3), with which it shares a k_{23} key
- Node 2 retransmits the k_{A1} key to node 3, encrypting it using a XOR protocol with the k_{23} key.
- Node 3 decrypts the key using k_{23} . Now 3 knows k_{A1}
- This process is repeated with all the nodes of the network until k_{A1} reaches B

Figure 11 - Transmission of a key generated by QKD through N trusted nodes on a network

The second method is based on generating QKD keys between contiguous pairs of nodes on the network, but in this case the encryption key is transmitted directly to B, without going through the intermediate nodes. In this case, the intermediate nodes no longer have to be trusted, except for the first node with which user A has communication. The process of this method has been outlined in Figure 12.

- User A performs a QKD protocol with the next node on the network (1), with which it shares a key k_{A1} . This key will be the one used at the end of the process by users A and B.
- Node 1 performs a QKD protocol with the next node on the network (2), with which it shares a k_{12} key
- And so on, all the nodes of the network establish key pairs among themselves.
- Node 1 transfers the k_{A1} key to user B, encrypting it using a XOR protocol with the k_{12} key.
- Node 2 passes the XOR of k_{12} and k_{23} to user B.
- And so, on
- Finally, user B decrypts the key k_{A1} as shown in the equation below

$$(k_{A1} \oplus k_{12}) \oplus (k_{12} \oplus k_{23}) \oplus \dots \oplus (k_{(N-1)N} \oplus k_{NB}) = k_{A1}$$

Figure 12 - Transmission of a key generated by QKD through N nodes on a network without all of them being trusted

Currently, terrestrial networks follow the approach of trusted nodes (method 1), where the key passes in plain text through each of the intermediate nodes.

5.1.8. Mechanisms to provide resource integrity

5.1.8.1. Blockchain

About 4 decades after the birth of the Internet, and more specifically on January 3, 2009, the first block with 50 Bitcoins was presented by Satoshi Nakamoto (39). Bitcoin is the first decentralized digital currency. More precisely, Bitcoin is a cryptocurrency, as its creation utilizes encryption techniques to verify transactions and secure the production network. Bitcoin was created to address some of the major shortcomings of the traditional trading systems, such as vulnerabilities, inadequacies, complexity, and unnecessary additional costs, often imposed by intermediaries. The decentralized nature of Bitcoin ensures that the currency does not have a permanent administrator or a central authority to control it.

All the above require a technical infrastructure so that they can operate smoothly and efficiently. The algorithmic framework for cryptocurrencies is a peer-to-peer network called Blockchain. Blockchain is a digital, distributed ledger in which timestamped transactions of digitized information are recorded. And although as a transaction we tend to consider the transfer of money (fiat or digital) from one wallet or account to another, it is important to keep that in the Blockchain world we refer to any data transaction that takes place within the network and meets its requirements, either these refer to values or other kinds of information. The philosophy behind its creation is based on the following triptych of characteristics:

- **Decentralization** is the transfer of procedures, activities, responsibilities, or powers from one central body to more than one peripheral body. In the case of Blockchain, the decentralization can be complete, with all peers being equal and sharing the same set of data at the same time, with each having their own valid copy. In an analogy of the physical world, it can be compared to a ledger or other log whose distribution is made to everyone involved and updated at the same time. Blockchain as a technology is a type of distributed computing system, which is why it falls under the Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) category.
- **Immutability** is Blockchain's feature that gives it a competitive advantage. All data stored on a Blockchain network cannot be modified. A transaction, once completed, can only be cancelled with a new, reverse one. For example, if a person accidentally transfers more money than intended to a recipient, then the only way to correct that error is to process a new transaction, from recipient to sender, where the excess is refunded. Any attempts to alter the transactions become unsuccessful because

Blockchain has mechanisms based on its decentralized structure for their recovery. This can be illustrated by the following example: We consider that in a transaction two traders are involved as well as a third person with the role of the neutral witness. A copy of triplicate receipt of this transaction is distributed to each person involved. In case one of the three falsifies his or her copy, then it is compared with the other two and its invalidity is ascertained. In such a case, the Blockchain network replaces the invalid copy with a valid one. This is where the democracy of Blockchain technology comes into play, as the majority prevails.

- **Traceability** through the decentralized Blockchain network, the data is stored timestamped and may contain additional traceability information about the origin of a transaction. Combined with the immutability of the data and the timing they receive when stored in a Blockchain environment, an irrefutable series of transactions is automatically created that can be traced up to the first block of the Chain.

It becomes clear that the triptych of the features of Blockchain technology, ultimately offers **Integrity** and **Transparency**, thus establishing a digital regime of mutual trust resulting from a chain of immutable and irrefutable data.

In the certain scenarios where there is a fragile balance between data transfer speed and security, the opportunity cost between the two should very carefully be calculated. In almost all cases, sacrifices or at least compromises should be made.

Understanding how information was derived is the first step in determining its provenance. This includes specialized procedures for ingesting raw data and a series of processes that execute on one or more computation nodes to generate a final result. A workflow can incorporate a variety of raw data sources as well as a variety of operations. In a multi-actor use-case, the outputs frequently differ and may be incompatible. In situations like these, it's necessary to create a collaborative environment that allows all parties to communicate with one another, in an interoperable manner. Another issue that arises from such environments is that the information needs to be securely stored and remain intact until it is needed.

Blockchain technology can provide a solution to both of the above concerns. At first, it can support transparent collaborative environments of mutual trust, as the information that is store within remains immutable. In addition, data are stored timestamped and may also contain additional traceability information about their origin Combined with the immutability feature of blockchain, an irrefutable series of data records is created and can be traced up to the first record. In that manner, data integrity is assured as it cannot get erased, or even modified, accidentally or not.

Another key benefit of adopting a suitable blockchain-enabled solution, is the versatility of smart contracts. Although they are nothing more but functional pieces of executable code that run in a blockchain environment and perform specific processes, they can be programmed to be a dynamic entity that directly adapts its behaviour to existing conditions. Thus, for example, its temporal power may not be constant but may change, always conditionally, and if this has been pre-agreed by the parties involved, before being translated into code. Since smart contracts run on blockchain, they are also resilient to alterations. This means that by utilizing blockchain, not only the integrity of trafficked data is ensured but also all the processes that have been realised as smart contracts, instead of traditional programs.

5.1.8.2. *Cryptography techniques for integrity*

Techniques to ensure the availability of collaboration

Once the requirements that need to be solved have been identified, as well as the solutions that are currently applied for these types of issues, possible opportunities for collaboration and harmonization that can be provided to these scenarios will be reviewed. For this purpose, technologies and techniques will be reviewed at a technological and learning level to solve the different problems related to the requirements.

On the other hand, design and develop a framework able to build a resource federation between multiple parties and stakeholders with focus on cross-sectorial, cross-border and cross-hierarchical approach.

In order to ensure better collaboration, especially in resource federated environments, it is of utmost importance to adopt technologies that have high uptimes and promote interoperability between different actors and their systems. These technologies should be widely and mutually trusted by all involved stakeholders, in order to establish smoother collaboration, reduce friction and eliminate potential conflicts and disputes, or at least resolve them before they erupt.

Techniques to ensure redundancy

Data redundancy is based on storing multiple copies of data in different locations. This technique can be beneficial for organizations to prevent data corruption from leading to a total loss. However, this also brings some issues that must be taken into account. For example, if the data is frequently modified and consulted, it must be kept constantly updated since an inconsistency between them can lead to multiple values for the same information.

The advantages of data redundancy are, for example, to improve data security using backup copies that are stored as a backup. In addition, this data redundancy can improve system performance by speeding up access to this data. Multiple data access points allow various users to perform queries simultaneously.

On the other hand, some of the disadvantages of these systems are, on the one hand, the need to keep the data up to date, as mentioned above. In addition, the increase in the number of systems where this data is stored increases the likelihood that some of these systems will become corrupted and provide inconsistent data. Likewise, the maintenance of these systems increases the cost of these systems. Finally, the cost of computation and storage increases exponentially as an increase in data causes an increase in all the systems that store it.

The most common way to create such a system is based on RAID systems (Long, 1994). RAID arrays are designed to provide better performance and reliability than what is possible using a single disk. RAID refers to a series of tiered-based architectures. Not all RAID tiers offer data redundancy, but most of them do. Thus, RAID 1 would be an exact copy that functions as a backup.

Figure 13 – RAID 1 redundancy scheme

RAID 5 provides redundancy through the use of parity. Data is striped across all the disks in the array in a way that spans fewer data across multiple disks. Each disk also contains parity information that can keep the variety working in a disk failure. When a failed disk is replaced, the parity information is used to reconstruct the contents of the failed disk onto the new disk.

Figure 14 – RAID 5 redundancy scheme

Some of the most common RAID levels are shown in the following table:

RAID level	Method	Minimum Disks	Common usage	Pros	Cons
JBOD	Spanning	2	Increase Capacity	Cost-Effective Storage	No security benefits
0	Striping	2	Heavy read operations	High performance	Data is lost if one disk fails
1	Mirroring	2	Standard app servers	Fault tolerance, high read performance	Lag for write ops, reduced storage

RAID level	Method	Minimum Disks	Common usage	Pros	Cons
5	Striping & parity	3	Normal file storage	Speed + Fault Tolerance	Lag for write, reduced storage
6	Striping & Double Parity	4	Large file storage	Extra level of redundancy	Low write performance
10	Striping & Mirroring	4	Highly utilized database servers	Write performance, strong fault tolerance	Reduced storage, limited scalability

Table 1 – RAID levels

Other alternatives to RAID systems allow data redundancy to be maintained, such as backups. Backups restore a system to a previous state. The aim is to ensure fast and reliable data recovery in case of need. Another possible system is the CDP. CDP products work by initially replicating data in a disk-based backup, block by block. The software then monitors the data for changes to the stored blocks or the creation of new partnerships. When a block is created or modified, it is backed up. Finally, snapshot systems and image-based systems are available. Snapshots never generate a copy of the data. Instead, they create a partial image of a virtual machine, file, or application at a given point in time. Snapshots allow an organization to roll back data to an earlier point if something goes wrong.

Load balancing strategies

Load Balancing refers to the ability to manage and distribute the network traffic, application demands or access to data, thought different servers, within a network, in order to prevent that the servers’ operational limit is not reached or that the load request does not affect the performance of the systems. The load balancing runs application more responsive, data exchange with less latency and user experience runs more fluid and friendly. In a network, we can depict the low balancing as follows:

Figure 15 - Load Balancing

To ensure the reliability of the system is required a redundancy of the elements in the network, preventing failover in case on the network element crash due to overload.

So, load needs to be distributed while ensuring redundancy of the elements in the network. Also important is to avoid single point of failure in the network.

Several load balancing strategies can be used according to the profile of the network, applications, and data volumes of the system, and even more relevant in case of a federation of systems where the interaction requirements and interoperability requirements add extra complexity, processing and inter-application messaging to coordinate the federation.

In the case of VALKYRIES scenario, we can find network technologies that support low data rates, where high availability of the services is required to operate in an environment of potential networks interference or disruption, due to the natural incident. This scenario increases the relevance of the load balancing.

There are several different ways to balance the load using different algorithms and different strategies.

Algorithms:

- Least Connection: assigns the traffic to the server with fewest number of active connections.
- Least Response Time: assigns the traffic to the server with the fewest number of active connections and with lowest response time.
- Round Robin: assigns the traffic to the first available server in the queue and moves that server to the bottom of the queue.
- IP Hash: the IP address of the client determines which server receives the request (assign table)
- Weighted balancing

Load balancing can be implemented on dedicated hardware or via software, as can be seen in the following table.

Implementation	Pros	Cons
SOFTWARE	Flexibility to adjust for changing needs. Ability to scale beyond initial capacity by adding more software instances. Lower cost than purchasing and maintaining physical machines. Software can run on any standard device, which tends to be cheaper. Allows for load balancing in the cloud, which provides a managed, off-site solution that can draw resources from an elastic network of servers. Cloud computing also allows for the flexibility of hybrid hosted and in-house solutions. The main load balancer could be in-house while the backup is a cloud load balancer.	When scaling beyond initial capacity, there can be some delay while configuring load balancer software. Ongoing costs for upgrades.

Implementation	Pros	Cons
HARDWARE	Fast throughput due to software running on specialized processors. Increased security since only the organization can access the servers physically. Fixed cost once purchased.	Require more staff and expertise to configure and program the physical machines. Inability to scale when the set limit on number of connections has been made. Connections are refused or service degraded until additional machines are purchased and installed. Higher cost for purchase and maintenance of physical network load balancer. Owning a hardware load balancer may also require paying for consultants to manage it.

Table 2 – Load balancing implementation (41)

The option to select a software or hardware balancing depends on the context and performances needed. In VALKYRIES scenarios, the deployability of the systems is a key factor, as critical events require a fast response and low logistics. Another factor is the scalability and adaptability of the federated systems required to operate in a dynamic scenario, where assets may enter or exit the SIGRUN network.

Balancing data types, file and streaming

Another element to consider refers to the nature of the data to be balanced, meaning that the load balancer strategy should also consider the type of communication data.

- UDP Load balancing (Streaming video or audio): Typically uses UDP because speed is more critical and error control less needed, as the data transmitted shortly becomes obsolete and overwritten.
- TCP Load balancing (For transactional data): TCP is usually a more widely used protocol with a strong error checking and warranty of delivery, or signalling when not.
- SDN Load Balancing: This approach is used internally for the dynamic management of the network aiming to optimize the resources and avoid congestion in the data transmission.

These types of data have different loads requirements, while streaming can be quite demanding on bandwidth, balancing multiple streams is more challenging. So, depending on the protocol, the load balancing shall consider which protocols is under use and how to prioritize them.

5.1.8.3. Dynamic network management

For several decades, managing communications networks was synonymous with expensive work. All routers and switches involved in the process had to be manually configured, one by one, to meet the needs. And as the infrastructure scaled vertically or horizontally, making changes took a proportional toll on time or service availability. This aspect is accentuated by the

drastic changes in communication networks in recent decades, forcing a reconsideration of the architecture of traditional networks (42). Among the most influential factors, we can highlight

- Increasing demand. Concepts such as Cloud computing, Big data, The Internet of Things (IoT) or the rise of mobile devices as an extension of us have driven the massive use of network infrastructures.
- Complex traffic patterns. Traffic is becoming much more complex and dynamic, making it very difficult to deal with congestion. This is a product of the continuous advances found in large network infrastructures.
 - Voice, data and video transfer generate traffic that is very difficult to predict.
 - Client/server applications need to communicate with each other (horizontal) and with other clients/servers (vertical).
 - The popularisation of cloud services has shifted a large amount of traffic, usually local, to the outside.
 - Quality of Service, QoS, requires thinking about traffic flows, something that clashes with the datagrams of traditional networks.
 - Inconsistent policies. A network policy requires managing devices through different mechanisms and tools. A critical change in specific infrastructures can take days to reconfigure Access Control Lists (ACLs) across the entire infrastructure. Vendor dependency. Solutions to the various problems involve dependence on a vendor and its equipment and are limited to the relatively slow product cycles of the vendor's equipment. For all these reasons, there is a growing need to approach the problem of modern networks from a different perspective. Software-Defined Networking (SDN) (43) is a paradigm that aims to revolutionise this field, facilitating the implementation and deployment of network services in a deterministic, dynamic and scalable way, preventing the network administrator from managing these services at a low level.

Software-Defined Networking (SDN) technology is a network management approach that enables dynamic and programmatically efficient network configuration to improve network performance and management. SDN attempts to centralise network intelligence in a network component by decoupling the network packet forwarding process (data plane) from the routing process (control plane). The control plane is composed of one or more controllers, which are considered the brain of the network. The controller sends data, configures and manages the network devices through different protocols such as OpenFlow or OpenFlow. The data plane comprises the network devices (routers, switches, access points, etc.), which decide what action to take with a packet arriving at one of their input interfaces. These devices are managed by one or more SDN controllers (44)

The fundamental idea of SDN is clear: move the control plane of the data plane into the physical devices (routers and switches) by unifying it into a single element external to the physical network, the controller. Instead of using distributed protocols such as OSPF or BGP, the controller is the standard software component in charge of deciding the forwarding and building the routing tables of the network devices (making them more straightforward than the current ones), as well as controlling the network from a single point, which means also being able to configure all types of equipment (routers, switches, network address translators NATs or

firewalls) through standard management software, without a manufacturer, making the network become an open system. In addition, there is a complete view, as information is constantly exchanged between the different layers of the architecture: application, control and infrastructure, as shown in Figure 16 and detailed below.

Figure 16 - SDN architecture overview. Separation into control and data layer

5.1.9. Frameworks offering data federation capabilities

5.1.9.1. INSARAG

INSARAG (International Search and Rescue Advisory Group) (45) is a global network of more than 90 countries and organizations which depends by the United Nations and was chosen by UN to facilitate international participation and coordination. INSARAG has the aim of establishing minimum international standards for urban search and rescue teams and a methodology for international coordination of response to earthquakes, tidal waves and other natural disasters and to the field operational coordination, for that reason it was developed the INSARAG Guidelines which describe a concept for an On-Site Operations Coordination Centre to improve the coordination of international assistance in support of the Government of an affected country by any disaster.

5.1.9.2. Virtual OSOCC

Virtual OSOCC (On-Site Operations Coordination Centre) (46) is a real time coordination tool which permits exchange information early in any emergency. Virtual OSOCC is part of the Global Disaster and Coordination System (GDACS), a cooperative framework that provides new real-time alerts and information, under the United Nations Office for Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA). Information sharing can be defined within the broader context of coordination. This concept of coordination could include communication, collaboration and cooperation.

The screenshot shows the GDACS virtual OSOCC interface. At the top, it states: "GDACS is a cooperation framework between the United Nations, the European Commission and disaster managers worldwide to improve alerts, information exchange and coordination in the first phase after major sudden-onset disasters." Below this, there are three main sections:

- Virtual OSOCC Login:** Includes fields for Username and Password, a Login button, and links for "Forgot your password" and "Sign up (create account)".
- Ongoing disasters:** Features a "CURRENT GDACS ALERTS" section with a table of recent alerts:

Alert Description	Date/Time
Green earthquake alert (Magnitude 6.2M, Depth:49km) in Timor-Leste 27/05/2022 02:36 UTC, 220 thousand in 100km.	Fri, 27 May 2022 02:59:23 GMT
Green earthquake alert (Magnitude 5.5M, Depth:38.99km) in Peru 27/05/2022 01:07 UTC, 390 thousand in 100km.	Fri, 27 May 2022 01:29:02 GMT
Green earthquake alert (Magnitude 6.2M,	Thu, 26 May
- News and upcoming events:** Contains sections for "TRAINING COURSES" (listing an OSOCC e-learning Awareness Course), "DISCUSSIONS" (Virtual OSOCC online help for relief teams), and "GUIDELINES" (Virtual OSOCC handbook, UNDAC teams, USAR teams, and Foreign Medical Teams).

Figure 17 – GDACS virtual OSOCC (47)

5.1.9.3. GAIA-X

GAIA-X (Federation Services, 2022) is a common European project, initiated by “Europe for Europe and beyond”. GAIA-X aims to develop a software framework of control and governance, implementing common policies and rules to be applied between multiple participants and organizations. This framework is meant to be deployed over any existing cloud platform.

This framework promoted federation; a model of cloud data exchange based on a decentralized scheme. Many federated use cases are being explored, such as health data analysis (BMWK, 2022), a medical data ecosystem (BMWK, s.f.), digital translational medical records (BMWK, s.f.) and healthcare with smart wearables (BMWK, s.f.).

The organization is built on three pillars: the association, the national hubs and the community. Within these, the GAIA-X hubs are the central contact points, and the aim is to set up one national hub in each participating country. Currently, 15 hubs are available, including Spain, Portugal and Greece, between others.

5.1.9.4. SIRFTI

The Security incident Response Trust Framework for Federates Identity (SIRFTI) (53) framework is an initiative of the Research and Educational Federations group (REFEDS), which aims to enable the coordination of incident response across multiple organizations. It has been active since 2014, combining expertise from the REFEDS community.

This framework is supported by the H2020 AARC Project.

5.1.9.5. BEACON

The BEACON framework (54) is based on OpenDayLight, and enables the provision and management of cross-site virtual networks for federated cloud infrastructures, enabling multi-tenancy, federated network orchestration and computing and storage of multi-cloud applications.

The BEACON project was supported by the European Union’s H2020 and ended in 2017.

5.1.9.6. Oracle UIM federation framework

The Oracle Communications Unified Inventory Management (UIM) federation framework (55) enables to work with multiple systems, such as the Oracle’s Communications INAM or Communications MetaSolv Solution and others external systems using different communication protocols.

This federation framework supports different types of external arrangements: federated, leased in, leased out and shared, and the federation can be transaction based or order-based:

- Transaction based: point-to-point integration between UIM and the external system, typically revolves around simple resources.
- Order-based: schema based on the integration between UIM and external order management systems, and typically revolves around multi-phased designs and delivery process.

5.1.9.7. Micro Focus Federation framework

The Micro Focus Federation framework (56) enables the federation via API to retrieve information from the federated resources. This framework offers three main capabilities:

- Federation on the fly: All queries are run over original data repositories and results are built on the fly
- Population: populates data to the Configuration Management Data Base (CMDB) from an external data source
- Data push: pushes data from the local CMDB to a remote data source

Every repository involved requires an adapter to offer these capabilities.

5.2. Education and training for first aid responses

5.2.1. Collaboration opportunities and preparedness for first Aid response

This part of the deliverable presents and analyses the organisation of first aid services, as well as existing education and training programmes and curriculums for First Aid Responders.

It presents the results from the study and analysis of the existing Education and Training (E&T) capabilities, debriefing principles for first aid response in support of preparation of a framework for joint education and training for the European Emergency Medical Services (EMS) carried out in the framework of task T6.2.

The analysis is structured around the following topics:

- Identification of existing education and training programmes and curriculums for First Aid Responders (FARs);
- Identification of existing standards, procedures and protocols for first aid responses and for collaboration between medical teams and other first responders;
- Identification of existing capabilities for FARs (technological, human, organisational, etc.);
- Identification of existing debriefing principles, Emergency Debriefing Guidelines, Types of Debriefing Following Disasters, Debriefing Manuals for FARs.

The first and the main body of the deliverable covers.

First aid (response) is more general term understood as a set of simple and effective measures that serve to immediately help in the event of a sudden threat to life or disability, and which can be provided anywhere, anytime and by anyone. Mostly it used related to “basic first aid” which is a set of measures or treatments that are provided to the affected person in the event of an injury or sudden illness before the arrival of specialized assistance. However, this paper discusses mainly urgent medical care provided by professionals.

Sudden onset disasters (SOD) occur with little or no warning and often cause excessive injuries far surpassing the national response capacities.

A first responder is an Emergency Management / Response Personnel. Includes Federal, State, territorial, tribal, sub state regional, and local governments, nongovernmental organizations (NGOs), private sector organizations; critical infrastructure owners and operators, and all other organizations and individuals who assume an emergency management role. Also known as emergency or first responder (USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm>).

First responders are generally trained to provide advanced first aid and basic life support.

5.2.1.1. The EU Level

Although first aid response operations abide in all mass-casualty incidents in cross-border regions of Europe, there is still little cooperation in leveraging of common first aid environment.

The World Health Organization (WHO) published in 2008 a report describing and assessing EMS systems across the European Union and their links with national crisis management systems. After the consultation it concludes that the 67% of countries in Europe follow a national approved curriculum, the 70% have international cooperation protocols in EMS and the 78% has specific training in crisis/disaster management for EMS personnel.

A key observation of the study is that the adoption by all EU countries of a common core curriculum, as the basis for an emergency medicine (EM) speciality, would be the most suitable way to meet the EU Doctor's Directive and assure free exchange of EM physicians between EU countries.

WHO provides a classification and minimum standards for Emergency Medical Teams (EMT). This classification could be taken as a base for a European classification. Actually, it has been the case for the European Medical Corps (EMC) initiative under the EU Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM), which is in line with the EMTs WHO roadmap and meet high standards, including internationally recognised ones by the WHO when they exist.

According to this classification, we could make the equivalence of the first aid responders involved in cross-border multi-casualty with the EMT – Type 1 Mobile proposed from the WHO: Outpatient initial care and referral for further investigation using mobile medical teams in multiple locations and serve hard to reach populations according to the context of the emergency (58).

The results on current education and training for disaster and emergency response from the Article “Education and Training of Emergency Medical Teams: Recommendations for a Global Operational Learning Framework” (Amat Camacho N, 2016) states that Organisations involved in emergency response comprise emergency teams from international organizations, governments or well-known NGOs, as well as police, Fire and Rescue, ambulance services or militaries. They often follow an operational approach to training, immersing their teams into contexts they will likely be exposed to once in the field. Simulations, teamwork, pre-deployment preparation and the inclusion of regional and national actors are key features of their training practices (UNDAC) (Elsharkawi H, 2010).

Some examples of emergency training and first aid courses/exercises are:

- United Nations Disaster Assessment and Coordination (UNDAC):

In preparation for a short-notice deployment working together as a team with common methodology, all UNDAC members go through the same type of training. This consists of: 1) induction course with 3 webinars followed by a two-week intensive training course 2) refresher courses during 4/5 days every two years to update and improve their operational capacity. Additionally, UNDAC members are encouraged to take other available courses from OSOCC or other entities (62).

- Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies offers first aid training (63)

Every one of their 192 Red Cross (RC) and Red Crescent Societies offers first aid training, education and services to their communities. Right now, there are more than 165,000 active Red Cross and Red Crescent first aid trainers making first aid available for all. National RC societies offers courses and training to become a certified first aider. There are free online first aid training courses available.

- INSARAG First Responder Training Programme (64)

It consists in 5 parts: 1) first responders training Course with 7 modules, 3 full working days, with each day considered to contain a minimum of 8 hours of face-to-face instruction or learning, 2) guidance notes, 3) on-line support, 4) first responder equipment cache which is a set of basic tools, protective equipment and consumables housed in a standard steel ISO container and 5) training-of-trainers module (optional).

Regarding the ambulance care and according to the report of ambulance care in Europe (65), in most European countries emergency care teams consist of a medical doctor, a nurse or ambulance co-worker, besides an ambulance driver. Non-emergency care teams consist of one or two nurses, emergency medical technicians or assistants accompanied by an ambulance driver in most countries. Medical doctors are not part of the ambulance staff in non-emergency ambulance care.

There are specific regulations for ambulances in each country.

In all countries the ambulance staffs are being specifically trained. In Croatia, Estonia and Lithuania this training is continuously. In the Czech Republic, Germany, Ireland, Latvia, the Netherlands, and the UK staff has to take courses on a yearly basis. In the Netherlands a national assessment procedure is carried out every three years. In Belgium skills are evaluated once in five years. In Hungary competency measurements are established irregular. In some countries the ambulance staff needs reregistration. In Estonia, the Netherlands and Turkey training modules and re-registration are obliged once in respectively two, three/four and five years.

EU INITIATIVES

Erasmus + provided a grant for three universities and one public service provider in four Nordic countries to work on a harmonized model curriculum for a bachelor's degree in paramedic education. The project group has now completed the first phase of the project, which was to examine what paramedic education is available in the participating countries and what laws and regulations affect both the operation of ambulance services and the education of paramedics

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European Paramedic Curriculum (EPaCur) (66)

Erasmus + provided a grant for three universities and one public service provider in four Nordic countries to work on harmonised model curriculum for a bachelor's degree in paramedic education.

Paramedic as a person trained to give emergency medical care to people who are injured or ill, typically in a setting outside a hospital. The primary role of a paramedic is to stabilize people with life-threatening injuries and transport these patients to a higher level of care.

The paramedic role is closely related to other healthcare positions, especially the emergency medical technician, with paramedics often being at a higher grade with more responsibility and autonomy following substantially greater education and training.

According to an article of this initiative "European paramedic curriculum—a call for unity in paramedic education on a European level" (67), cross-border co-operation, in, among others, major accidents and Mass Casualty Incidents (MCI), requires paramedics to have comparable knowledge bases and be able to provide equivalent services between countries.

The Education and Training (E&T) of paramedics varies within European countries. Some require a BS degree, while others have shorter coursework at a lower academic level.

There is a growing need for highly educated paramedics within European countries. One factor in response to this is to provide such education at the university level.

The article concludes that there are different forms of managerial operations, traditions in ambulance patient transport and paramedic education that need to be considered. However, a European Paramedic Curriculum (EPaCur) could potentially increase the number of nations

offering such an education at the bachelor's degree level, thus raising the level of competency of paramedic practitioners overall.

TEAMS initiative (68)

TEAMS project, funded by the European Union Humanitarian Aid and Civil Protection, aims to develop, pilot and assess a standardized, validated and cost-effective training package, focused on operational team training for EMCs/EMTs, adaptable to different types of EMCs/EMTs, and sustainable within low-income countries and resource-poor settings.

TEAMS training package is available online (69).

TEAMS 2.0 is this next and overlapping project that is aimed to create a Training of Trainers' (ToT) program to train novice and inexperienced team leaders or training managers of EMCs/EMTs organizations on how to effectively use the online TEAMS training package. The overall objective is to develop, pilot and assess a standardized, cost-effective training of trainers' program able to equip novice and inexperienced team leaders or training managers of EMCs/EMTs organizations with the necessary competencies to effectively use the online TEAMS training package.

TEAMS 3.0 is the next and complementary project proposal which aims to:

- Revise and update the TEAMS training package involving new partners, experts and EU EMT organizations;
- Develop new scenarios and exercises for the TEAMS training package (70) to train EMTs to respond to outbreaks, man-made disasters and other possible cross-border risks;
- Disseminate and deliver the updated TEAMS training package engaging four EMTs in Europe to enhance cross-border emergency management through training programmes and joint cross-border small-scale exercises.

5.2.1.2. Spain

In Spain, healthcare competencies are transferred from the state to the autonomous communities and this determines the Spanish healthcare model. There are 17 autonomous communities (regions) and 2 autonomous cities Figure 18.

Figure 18 - Ministry of Health. Institutional organisation. Autonomous regions (71)

Medical emergency teams must comply with state regulations on the staffing of road medical transport vehicles. In Spain, medical emergency services have three different professional profiles: doctors, nurses and emergency medical technicians.

On the other hand, there are three classes of ambulances according to the type of service they perform: class A, class B and class C ambulances. Each class requires certain personnel, who must meet certain training and qualification requirements.

Royal Decree 836/2012, of 25 May, establishing the technical characteristics, medical equipment and staffing of medical road transport vehicles (72).

Article four of this Royal Decree establishes the minimum staffing levels for vehicles used to provide medical transport services, depending on the type of vehicle. Thus:

- Class A1 and A2 non-assistance ambulances shall have at least one driver holding at least the certificate of professionalism in health transport provided for in Royal Decree 710/2011 of 20 May and, when the type of service so requires, another driver with the same qualification in the role of assistant.
- Class B ambulances shall have at least one driver who holds the professional training qualification of health emergency technician, as provided for in Royal Decree 1397/2007, of 29 October, or the corresponding approved or recognised foreign qualification, and another driver with at least the same qualification as an assistant.
- Class C ambulances shall have at least one driver who holds the aforementioned vocational training qualification as a health emergency technician or the corresponding approved or recognised foreign qualification, and a nurse who holds a university diploma in nursing or a degree that enables the exercise of the regulated nursing profession, or the corresponding approved or recognised foreign qualification. Likewise,

when the care to be provided so requires, there must be a doctor in possession of a university degree in Medicine or a degree that qualifies them to practise the regulated profession of doctor, or the corresponding accredited or recognised foreign qualification.

The Administrations of the Autonomous Communities may demand such other requirements and technical conditions as they deem appropriate in relation to the vehicles to be used by the companies with which they contract medical transport services, as well as the number of personnel they must have.

Requirements that are usually requested for the different profiles are the following:

- For the medical doctors:
 - Degree in Medicine and a medical speciality. Only those who graduated before 1/1/1995 are exempt from accrediting a speciality. In Spain, there is no specialty in emergency medicine for medical doctors.
 - Professional experience as a doctor must be accredited. Time variable depending on the Emergency Medical System.
 - In the Community of Madrid for both SUMMA and SAMUR it is necessary to obtain accreditation as an out-of-hospital emergency doctor through the Regional Ministry of Health, and accreditation is required every three years by presenting a number of hours of training. There is a register.
 - At national level, Royal Decree 853/1993, of 4 June 1993, on the exercise of the functions of General Practitioner in the National Health System establishes the title, certificate or diploma required to perform the duties of General Practitioner in health centres or services integrated in the National Health System. (73)
 - In the Region of Madrid there are specific training requirements for those professionals who provide their services in activities related to medical transport. These requirements are set out in Order 559/1997, of 17 March, of the Regional Ministry of Health and Social Services, which establishes the criteria to guarantee the minimum levels of training for medical and nursing staff providing services in activities related to medical transport (74).
 - An example of the training that would be necessary for medical professionals working in the Community of Madrid in the field of medical transport is the university Master's degree in emergencies, emergencies and catastrophes. This master's degree (with 60 ECTS) qualifies to work as an out-of-hospital emergency doctor (75).
- Nurses:
 - Degree in nursing, university diploma in nursing or technical health assistant.
 - Certificate accrediting having completed the course "Nurse in out-of-hospital emergencies" or a certificate accrediting its homologation.
 - Proof of professional experience
- Health emergency technicians (medical transport technicians):
 - Intermediate level vocational training qualification of health emergency technician or equivalent qualification and driving licence C. 2000 hours.

- Royal Decree 1397/2007, of 29 October, establishes the qualification of Technician in Health Emergencies and sets its minimum teaching requirements (76).
- By way of example, you can consult the curriculum of the intermediate level training cycle corresponding to the qualification of Health Emergency Technician in the Community of Madrid (77).

There are no homogeneous criteria for both undergraduate and postgraduate training, and there is considerable variability between the different Emergency Medical System. There are many heterogeneous courses (master's degree in the case of physicians and nurses) to be able to work in an emergency medical service. Each Emergency Medical System has developed the training of its professionals and participates in the training of students and other groups in different ways. For example, in Madrid the registration of doctors and nurses is mandatory to carry out medical transport and 90 hours of continuous training in emergencies and emergencies without specific content must be accredited in a period of three years to maintain this authorization.

The teaching of emergency medicine is included in the curriculum of some medical schools but it is not regulated. Nor is there a speciality, so there is a regulatory vacuum that means that in Spain there is a multitude of heterogeneous courses to be able to work in out-of-hospital care.

To summarise, one of the problems is the lack of homogeneous criteria in the curricula, as well as common accreditation standards in relation to training.

What all EMS do have is continuous training programs aimed at developing the competencies of each category according to the needs detected by those responsible for training or by the workers themselves through surveys. After the terrorist attack of 11th March 2004 in the Community of Madrid, training in MCI was mandatory for all workers of SUMMA 112 (Emergency Medical Service of Madrid). However, it is not currently mandatory but is widely available in the training offer for all SUMMA 112 professionals. Multi Casualty Incidents (MCI) drills are carried out quarterly during the working day in a real environment with actors and mannequins. All job categories participate both at the level of the Coordinating Centre and at the level of care at the scene of the incident.

In the SUMMA 112 there are continuous training courses that enable professionals internally, such as "CBRN with chemical agents" and others that are not enabling such as "Intervention in collapsed structures" and "Health Care in terrorist attacks with active shooters"

The Training in civil protection and emergencies in Spain is a shared competence between the Education, Employment and Civil Protection bodies dependent on the three levels of public administration: state, autonomous and local. These administrations are responsible for the delivery of approved Civil Protection diplomas (vocational training), certificates of professionalism and continuous training.

Regarding to vocational training, there are two professional training degrees related to civil protection and emergencies. Intermediate level "Technician in emergencies and civil protection" and higher level "Coordination of emergencies and civil protection". The qualifications are

official and have the same academic and professional validity throughout the national territory regardless of where they are taken (78).

Regarding certificates of professionalism, these are official accreditation of professional qualifications. They are official and valid throughout the national territory. Related to this field are: "Management and coordination in civil protection and emergencies"; "Health care for multiple victims and catastrophes"; "Health transport".

In relation to continuous training, the National Civil Protection School programmes an annual training plan for the different human resources of the National Civil Protection System. The aim of this training plan is to maintain and improve the capacities to manage risk and intervene in the event of an emergency (79).

5.2.1.3. Portugal

In Portugal there are courses for doctors, nurses, pre-hospital emergency technicians (TEPH) and rescue ambulance crew (TAS). For the first two to integrate the medical vehicles of Emergency and Resuscitation (VMER), a degree is required and completion of a course in National Institute of Medical Emergency (INEM) with a total of 74 hours of training, which aims to consolidate the knowledge previously acquired in the basic course, consisting of 5 modules; it is the same for doctors and nurses, where a 75% out of a possible 100% is necessary for accreditation. The 5 modules are:

- Advanced Life Support Module;
- Module of Medical Emergencies;
- Trauma Module;
- Paediatric and Obstetric Emergencies Module;
- Critical Illness Transport and Exception Situations Module.

Nurses are also required to have a course in Defensive Driving of a VMER. To have access to this course, the nurses are subject to an evaluation with the application of several psycho-technical tests, and only after this validation may they have access to the course. The course has a duration of 42 hours, with theoretical and practical sessions, where various exercises are performed in a closed circuit or in urban traffic in emergency marching. Approval in the course is also subject to a success rate above 75%.

This is a very interesting variation of the ambulance categorisation. The VMER is a pre-hospital intervention vehicle, equipped with material and drugs for advanced life support, whose purpose is the rapid transport of a team to the location where the patient is. The VMER act/are activated by the Centros de Orientação de Doentes Urgentes (CODU – Urgent Patients Assistance Centre) and are hospital based.

The main purpose of this team is to stabilize and accompany victims of accidents or sudden illnesses during transport to the hospital in emergency situations.

The Immediate Life Support Ambulances (SIV) are designed to provide differentiated health care, namely resuscitation manoeuvres, until a team capable of providing Advanced Life Support is available. Its crew consists of a Nurse and a Pre-hospital Emergency Technician (in this case the TEPH is the driver). In addition to the basic life support equipment, it has a defibrillator

monitor and several drugs for administration if necessary. The SIV equipment allows the transmission of electrocardiograms and vital signs to the regulator physician who is in the CODU, that monitoring the situation remotely. In this environment the nurse can act independently following previously established protocols, but when the situation is more complex the doctor is contacted remotely, who decides what to do with the patient, either by data transmitted by the nurse or by access to data transmitted from the environment to the doctor.

The EMTs (Emergency Medical Technician) are required to have 12 years of schooling and a course also from INEM with 910 hours of training.

The TAS courses organised by INEM are intended for elements of institutions that are integrated into the Integrated Medical Emergency System (SIEM) such as Fire Departments, Portuguese Red Cross, Health Units, among others. The access to these courses is only possible through institutional means, i.e., the institutions where the element works must be the ones to propose the participation in the courses, which can create bottlenecks in healthcare professionals' training and specialization. These courses have a duration of 210 hours which includes the use of the Automated External Defibrillation Course and the Emergency Vehicle Driving Course. In this case the courses can be taught by INEM or other accredited training entities such as the Portuguese Red Cross. As such, the leading organisations which provide training throughout Portugal are INEM and the Portuguese Red Cross; the Vacancies are proposed annually by the INEM or when there is need for training (e.g., opening of a position in a Hospital/Healthcare Entity where there were no allocated specialized positions before)

In terms of types of ambulances/displacement cars and their differences:

- VMER – this vehicle does not transport patients, only the team and equipment; this team will be further aided by another team, which can be an INEM vehicle. This mainly happens in Lisbon or Porto (metropolis) and in the rest of the country they are usually firemen ambulances with the TAS training that has already been described. The VMER team only leaves if both elements are present (driver + nurse). In Portugal, there is 1 VMER per district in low population density districts such as Évora, Beja, Portalegre. Some districts like Lisbon and Porto have 2 to 3 VMER normally, 1 for each hospital that has emergency service.
- SIV – ambulance that transports the patient; may need support from VMER in more serious cases.
- INEM helicopter - prior training in VMER, completion of a course in physiology of flight and a course on safety in heliports (INEM training); must also have experience in an intensive care environment. The team consists of pilots (the commander and a pilot) and the medical team (a physician and a nurse). The INEM has four aircrafts that are stationed in Macedo de Cavaleiros, Santa Comba Dão, Évora and Loulé. Depending on the characteristics of the aircraft, it can carry 1 or 2 patients simultaneously.
- Emergency Medical Ambulance (AEM) formerly known as basic life support ambulance - the ambulance is manned by TEHP. They can be supported by any of the above means.
- Ambulância de Socorro (AS) - manned by TAS that can be firefighters or other entities that provide help, such as the Red Cross certified by INEM.

- Medical Emergency Motorcycle - manned by a TEPH. This vehicle carries an Automated External Defibrillation device, oxygen, and equipment to evaluate vital signs. It is a Basic Life Support (SBV) unit.
- The Mobile Unit for Psychological Emergency Intervention (UMIPE) - psychological assistance to victims of accidents or sudden loss of loved ones, etc. They are activated by INEM through the CODU.
- Paediatric Inter-hospital Transportation (TIP) - transportation of new-borns and paediatric patients in critical condition between Health Units. The crew consists of a physician, a nurse, and a Pre-hospital Emergency Technician (TEPH). They are equipped with all the necessary material for the stabilization of patients from 0 to 18 years of age.
- The Disaster Intervention Vehicle (VIC) - is used in multi-victim situations. It carries various Advanced Life Support material, which allows for the assembly of an Advanced Medical Post (AMP). It is equipped with the same material as the Emergency Medical Vehicle (VMER) and allows the treatment of 8 very serious victims simultaneously. It also has a telecommunications cell, which allows the creation of a communications network between the accident site, the CODU and local hospitals.

It is also worth noting that, in Portugal, there are no paramedics per se. The professionals involved in emergency response are physicians, nurses, technicians, and others involved in the response/healthcare entities.

5.2.1.4. Slovakia

Organisation of first aid services in Slovakia

Within the Slovakia, there is recognized “event with mass disabilities” (udalosť s hromadným postihnutím osôb) which might be understood as MCI. It is based on Act no. 579/2004 Coll. on the emergency medical service. It is an event in which (one of the below mentioned options):

- There are three or more persons are at serious health risk, or have an imminent life-threatening situation, or
- There are ten or more affected by the event and at the same time at least one of them has a serious health threat or an immediate life threatening.

First aid (response) should be provided by anybody who is on the place in current time. **Urgent medical care** is provided by professionals - Emergency Medical Service (**EMS**) and in accordance with the law. EMS is one of the components of the Integrated Rescue System of the Slovak Republic (IRS).

All first aid medical responders in Slovakia perform identical work activities, regardless of completed education. Medics have one of the following professional qualifications containing first aid medical education and upgrade of qualifications for any urgent, emergency and lifesaving activities in the event of disaster and extraordinary event with mass casualties:

- Paramedic health staff support certificate
- Paramedic - qualification specialisation study
- Certified (para)medic
- Bachelor in (para)medics
- Nurse - qualification specialisation study

- Bachelor (Bc.) In the field of nursing - qualification specialisation study
- Master's degree (Mgr.) In the field of nursing - qualification specialisation study
- Doctor of Philosophy (PhDr.) In the field of nursing - qualification specialisation study
- Doctor (graduate of medical studies) without specialisation

EMS is provided by:

- Operational center of the rescue medical service one centralized dispatching e-call (Directorate and 8 regional operational centers). It is a state-subsidized organization founded by the Ministry of Health of the SR. Main goals are:
 - To ensure the reception of the emergency call of the emergency medical service, the processing of the emergency call and the implementation of the response to the emergency call, if necessary, it issues an instruction to the ambulance of the emergency medical service,
 - To manage, coordinate and evaluate the emergency medical service so as to ensure its continuity and continuity,
 - To provide training for its employees,
 - To organize first aid courses and first aid instructor courses and
 - To performs other tasks in accordance with the law.
- Medical facilities including 27 spas for any mass casualties and other events, Ambulances (Ambulance type RLP, RZP and S types – different equipment and different tasks),helicopter rescue medical service
 - Ambulance (RZP). It consists of two members consisting of a paramedic/medical staff and an ambulance driver, or two medical staff (one in the position of driver); some of these outpatient clinics are equipped with a new-born incubator.
 - Ambulance (RLP). It consists of 3 members: a doctor specializing in emergency medicine, anaesthesiology and intensive care (or with another specialization); paramedic/medical staff and ambulance driver, or doctor and two paramedics/medical staff. There are 92 such ambulances in the Slovak Republic.
 - Emergency Medical Ambulance / Mobile Intensive Care Unit (RLP / MIJ). Compared to the previous type of RLP, it is supplemented by an incubator, i.e. it is able to provide care for a new-born in a critical condition. The composition of the crew is the same.
 - Helicopter Rescue Medical Service (VZZS). It is possible to transport by air thanks to a specially equipped helicopter. The VZZS crew consists of a doctor, paramedic and pilot. There are 7 VZZS ambulances in the Slovak Republic.

Location of ambulances

- The headquarters of emergency medical ambulances are determined by legislation so that under ideal weather conditions they are available in an approximate time horizon of 15 minutes.
- Emergency medical service providers perform urgent medical care by emergency medical ambulances. Currently, there are 13 emergency medical service providers (companies, NGOs, state-owned entities) in Slovakia that operate several types of

emergency medical clinics at the headquarters of the emergency medical station. The EMS network consists of 280 stations located in the territory of the Slovak Republic in continuous operation. The EMS provider obtains a permit to operate the headquarters of the EMS station on the basis of a tender announced by the Ministry of Health of the Slovak Republic for a period of 6 years.

- There are also specialist clinics for emergency and urgent cases, in case of MCI the dispatcher shall guide the pre-hospital rescue medical “staff/vehicle” to which clinic/hospital the patient shall be delivered. Usually these urgent cases are covered by helicopter medical aid services.

Education and training First Aid Responders in Slovakia

First aid medical education is part of accredited courses, study programmes, at secondary and territorial education programmes in Slovakia. Volunteers are mainly educated via the wide spread network of Red Cross in Slovakia entities in Slovakia. Also, basic first aid can be provided by any certified medical services provider.

Education for highest medical professions:

- A medical doctor – university education (the third degree) in the doctoral study program in the study program field of general medicine. For EMS specializations of emergency medicine, anesthesiology and intensive care are relevant.
- (Para)Medic – there are three possibilities: (1) university education of the first degree in the bachelor's study program in the study program emergency medical department care, (2) higher professional education in the field of study of a certified paramedic, or (3) complete secondary vocational education in the field of study paramedic.

Healthcare professionals with the qualification of medics/paramedic perform work in the following areas:

- Emergency Medical Service (EMS)
- Helicopter Rescue Medical Service (VZZS)
- Operational Centre of the Rescue Medical Service of the Slovak Republic (OS ZZS SR)
- Accident admission clinics of hospital facilities (emergency admissions)
- Mountain Rescue Service (HZS)
- Mining Rescue Service (BZS)
- Fire and Rescue Corps (HaZZ)
- Armed Forces of the Slovak Republic (OS SR)
- Police Force of the Slovak Republic (PZ SR)
- Water rescue service
- Comprehensive central rescue service

More than 3,500 medical doctors and paramedics (first aid support staff - responders) work in the components of the integrated rescue system (IRS).

Paramedics should be involved in the trade union Slovak Chamber of Paramedics. A natural person who is professionally qualified to perform the profession of paramedic and is of good character if he/she applies for registration in the list of members may become a member of the

Chamber. Membership is voluntary, but registration in the Chamber is mandatory for all health care professionals who perform the profession of a paramedic in the provision of emergency medical care.

Competences of the first aid, medical staff rescue service staff

In accordance with the Decree of the Ministry of Health of the Slovak Republic no. 334/2010 Coll., which includes all current competencies, the emergency paramedic in the emergency medical service, as a crew member of the ambulance with equipment, mobile intensive care unit, or helicopter ambulance, performs individually appointed acts either independently or on the basis of a written authorization. The written authorisation required for the independent performance of professional work activities is issued by a professional representative of the relevant emergency medical service provider or a physician authorised by him specialising in specialized fields of emergency medicine, intensive care or anaesthesiology. This authorisation is issued for a maximum of five years. In Slovakia, a person who received the appropriate education according to Act no. 578/2004 Coll. Section 40 clearly sets out all the conditions for institutions to obtain accreditation for education in a specific field of Health Care Providers, Health Professionals and Professional Associations.

Continuing education in professional first aid rescue competitions

It is the Accreditation Commission of the Ministry of Health of SR who is responsible for the accreditation, specialisation and certification of education, lifelong learning training, first aid courses and first aid instructor courses for healthcare professionals as well as for further education of health care workers. It is an advisory body of the Ministry of Health of SR in matters of education of health care workers.

- **Slovakia courses for volunteers. Target group:** Members of the Voluntary Fire Brigade, corporate fire brigades, civil protection units, civil protection technicians, fire protection students, rescue service students, crisis management
- **Course content:** Use of AED in CPR, simulation of a trip to CPR (first responder) First aid for life-threatening conditions, conditions of accident origin, emergency conditions, heat / cold, emergencies, fires, traffic accidents, transport, positioning and fixation of the affected person
- **Course location:** Our training centre is located in the centre of Trnava. We can organize and lead the course directly at your place with a sufficient number of participants and the provision of suitable premises. Find out about the options by phone.
- **Number of course participants:** The number of course participants is limited.
- **Course duration:** 33 lessons (3 days), 1 lesson = 45 minutes start of the course.
- **Confirmation:** Each participant of the course, after passing it and successfully passing the exams, will receive a "Confirmation of completion of the first aid course" **according to Act no. 578/2004 Coll. on health care providers, health care workers, professional organizations in health care and on the amendment of certain laws as amended and according to the Decree of the Ministry of Health of the Slovak Republic no. 398/2010 Coll. on minimum requirements for a first aid course and a first aid instructor course**

Formal education

To perform professional work activities, it is required to obtain:

- Higher education in the field of study emergency health care, which can be obtained in 5 universities within the Slovak Republic.
- Higher professional education in the field of study graduate paramedic
- Upper secondary vocational education in the field of study paramedic, which can be obtained in the 6 Secondary Medical Schools within the Slovak Republic.

5.2.1.5. Bulgaria

The National Health System of Bulgaria is clustered into four main categories:

The first category is Primary health care which is based on practical, scientific and social methods. These methods and technologies are widely available to each individual, their families and the society. This care is rendered with the full participation of the people due to the frame of the expanses which each country and society could afford. The primary health care is implemented on the first level of contact of the individuals, their families and the society with the national system of health care.

The basic health specialists are taking extremely important role in the community. They are first aid responders. Usually, they are family practitioners, general practitioners and nurses. According to the patient's preferences, health care, and availability of medical equipment, the patients could visit every one of these medical specialists. The general practitioners guide the patients to higher level of health care, if it is necessary. The main health care centres are taking care of a wide range of patients - people at different age, economic level, race, culture and religion, with different diseases and injuries and those who would like to maintain good health and status, receive care of primary level. Consequently, all medical specialists in the system of health care should have a wide range of knowledge. The constant care is the basic characteristic of the primary health care.

The second category covers the Secondary Health care. In the secondary health care are involved specialists who usually do not have first contact with the patients. Secondary health care includes also emergency care in cases of emergent issues, short course serious illnesses, specialized care in cases of child birth and figurative diagnoses. In specific cases the secondary health care pertains to pre-hospital care, although the fact that a lot of specialists in the field of secondary health care such as psychotherapists and physiotherapists do not work in the hospitals.

The third category covers the Tertiary health care. This type of health care is in the cases when the patient is hospitalized and he needs higher level of specialized care in the hospital. The tertiary health care requires highly specialized equipment and long - term experience. In the tertiary health care, there are procedures such as bypass of coronary artery, haemodialysis, some kind of plastic operations and neurosurgery.

Finally, the **fourth category includes the Quaternary health care.** This type of health care is a continuation of the tertiary health care. Quaternary health care is even more specialized care and exquisitely unordinary. Due to its nature, not every hospital or medical centre could offer that kind of care. Some hospitals and medical centres could offer quaternary health care only for definite medical conditions or body systems. Quaternary health care involves also

experimental procedures and practices and unordinary and specialized operations. The main difference between the Primary and Secondary, Tertiary and Quaternary Health Care is that the former is supposed to focus on prevention, while the latter on disease cure and patients' treatment. Primary Health Care is also responsible for the provision of first aid and for the conduction of the so-called triage. In case patients require further medical care, they are transferred to hospitals, which are part of the Secondary, Tertiary and Quaternary Health Care.

The activities of the Emergency Medical Centre are implemented by the following structures and actors:

1. Urgent mobile team in Centre for District Coordination, which consists of medical specialists or other specialists with the indispensable qualification.
2. Resuscitation teams, which consist of doctor, medical specialist/paramedic and driver.
3. Medical teams, which consist of a doctor and a driver.
4. Pre-medical teams, consist of medical specialist/paramedic and a driver.
5. Transportation teams, consist of driver and nurse, when it is necessary according to the specific case.

Everyday incidents requiring emergency medical interference are the subject of the urgent mobile teams/paramedics and the Emergency Medical Centre. There is also a special EMS department for cases of mass emergency, the so-called Special Department of Disasters' Medicine, which operates coordinated by the country's Civil Protection Agency.

Training and education to become First Aid Responders (FARs) are divided into two clusters, as does the role the FARs (Paramedics vs. Doctors).

A good example are the courses provided by the Military Medical Academy in Sofia. The Rescuers/paramedics are obliged to complete a two-and-a-half-year course. They go through educational courses and training for preparation and training procedures. There are four levels of professional qualification for the paramedics. The paramedics graduated this program with fully capacity of acknowledgement and clear instructions how to react in different situations with multiple victims in multi-casualty disasters. The paramedics are one of the first aid responders and their actions are extremely important in life-saving situations. During their training and education, the students acquire knowledge and skills for measuring and registration of physical indicators; doing medical operations; evaluation of the physiological and vital indicators of the injured individuals, emergency conditions, which require immediate help and behavioural algorithm, evacuation of the injured individuals from the danger zone or the place of the incident, behaviour and response in disasters of any kind.

The national curriculum of the specialty consists of lessons on the following topics:

- Anatomy;
- Physiology;
- Hygiene – Microbiology;
- Planning of Emergency Prehospital Care;
- English (terminology);
- Evaluation and Support of Vital Functions;

- Physiopathology;
- Telecommunication Tactics;
- Telecommunication Systems;
- Emergency Pathology;
- Emergency Traumatology;
- Pharmacology;
- Massive Health Loss;
- Protocols;
- Patients' Transport;
- Safe Driving Skills;
- Assistantship training (in the ER department of hospitals);
- Assistantship training (ambulance teams).
- Medical Doctors have to be graduates of the University of Medicine and may have additionally completed the postgraduate program of Emergency Pre-Hospital Medicine, in order to be more efficient in providing immediate and effective assistance to any acute health incident in the field.

First Aid responders are also trained as firefighters. The governmental authority responsible for their education and training is "DG Fire Safety and Civil Protection" of the Ministry of Interior. Through a thorough investigation and deep research of the documents received from that institution we found out the nowadays algorithm of actions and procedures in multi-casualty disasters. The main documents are based on the tasks and activities, which the law enforcements do in crises like natural disasters and emergencies. There are different ordinances, which regulate the performance of the posted tasks with the Law for Ministry of Interior and the Law for civil protection in disasters and crisis. The education and training of the employees of the mentioned above organization are made by the faculty "Fire Safety and Civil Protection" and the centre for specialization and professional preparedness for "Fire Safety and Civil Protection" in the Varna city. There are a lot of structural procedures, algorithm and action plan for first aid responders, based on long-term collection of educational materials, instructions, programs and manuals.

The state educational requirement for acquiring qualification in the profession 723030 "Paramedic" according to the appendix to the ORDINANCE № 1 of April 7, 2016 for obtaining a qualification in the profession "Paramedic" determines the requirements for acquiring the second degree of professional qualification for the specialty 7230301 "Transportation of injured and sick people and first aid", the third degree of professional qualification for the specialty 7230302 "Transportation of injured and sick people, first aid and assistance in emergency departments" and the fourth degree of professional qualification for the specialty 7230303 "Transportation of injured and sick people, first aid and assistance to the doctor in the emergency room" aid '. Qualification can be provided only by accredited training centres.

In the military is applied ORDINANCE № 11 OF FEBRUARY 8, 2019 FOR ACQUISITION OF QUALIFICATION IN THE PROFESSION "MILITARY - SANITARY INSTRUCTOR"

The state educational standard for acquiring qualification in the profession 863070 "Serviceman - sanitary instructor" according to this ordinance determines the requirements for acquiring the

fourth degree of professional qualification for the specialty 8630701 "Transportation of injured and sick people, first aid and subsequent assistance to medical doctors". Qualification again can be provided only by accredited training centres.

In the civil protection the ORDINANCE № 71 of August 9, 2012 on obtaining a qualification in the profession "Rescuer in disasters, accidents and catastrophes" determines the requirements for first responders. Although they have some medical training they are not considered as a first medical aid responder.

The state educational requirement for acquiring qualification in the profession 816020 "Rescuer in case of disasters, accidents and catastrophes" according to this ordinance determines the requirements for acquiring third degree professional qualification for the specialty 8610201 "Search, rescue and emergency response". Qualification again can be provided only by accredited training centres.

Medical doctors and nurses can be trained only by medical universities. The educational framework and curriculum are synchronized on EU level.

Since 2003 the Bulgarian Red Cross (BRC) has been training candidate-drivers in first aid.

The course was certified with EFAC certificate issued by the European Reference Centre for First Aid Education of the IFRC/RC - Paris, France in 2006. This certificate is recognized in all EU countries and is valid for a period of five years.

- Designed for: all citizens who are in procedure to obtain their initial driving license.
- Duration: 8 hours - The ratio theory/practice is 55/45%
- Training manual: 64 colour pages.
- Topics:
 - Anatomy and physiology of the vital organs and systems /respiratory, central nervous, muscular - skeletal, cardio vascular systems etc.
 - Assessment of the general condition of the casualty - by checking the vital signs - consciousness, pulse, breathing.
 - Bleeding. Shock. How to stop the bleeding. Wounds. Type of the wounds.
 - Brain, chest, abdominal and spinal trauma. Immobilization.
 - Ensuring safety on the scene. Evacuation of the casualty.
- Program
 - First part - duration 4 hours
 - Subject 1 - Short acquaintance with the anatomy and physiology of vital organs and systems of the human body- topic, function, interference.
 - Subject 2 - Main vital signs. Normal values. Recovery position. Clinical and biological death. Demonstrations on mannequins /right – wrong/. Role play.
 - Subject 3 - Bleeding. How to stop the bleeding. External - internal haemorrhage. Haemorrhagic shock. Bandages. Types of bandages. Practical exercises.
 - Subject 4 - What to do in case of head, neck or abdominal injuries. Traumatic shock.

- Subject 5 - Safety measures. Ensuring safety on the scene of the accident. Evacuation of the casualties.
- Second part - duration 4 hours
 - Practical exercise - cases of acute disorders of the respiratory and cardio-vascular systems, wounds and bleeding, bone fractures. Evaluation of the practical skills on mannequins.
- Third part – duration 30 minutes
 - Evaluation of the theoretical knowledge by completing a test with 15 questions. Successfully passed the test are those who completed at least 12 correct answers. Discussions on the test.

BRC also organizes First Aid training in the working place, First Aid training for pedagogues and parents of children up to 8 years old, advanced training in first aid.

In case of need, BRC can mobilize Water purification units (WatSan equipment) with the support of IFRC/RC Secretariat - Geneva, which have capacity to clean 100,000 liters per day. The organization has trained staff to work with for water purification equipment.

The BRC is well prepared humanitarian organization with capacity, approaches and activities to realize its mission and role as an auxiliary partner to the state in case of need in emergency situations.

Directives:

- Regulation № 81213-1006 of 24.08.2015 r. for order of the realization of fire existence and rescue activity by the authorities responsible for fire safety and civil protection
- Instruction № 81213-418 from April 5th 2021 for the conditions and order for realization of urgent emergency restorative operations, operational defence in cases of floods and operations for search and rescue, chemical, biological and radiological defence.
- Plan for defence in cases of disasters on national level (80)

5.2.1.6. Greece

The National Health System of Greece (ESY) is clustered into three main categories:

- **Primary Health Care**, which consists of 322 health centres and, moreover, of 239 local health units. Its purpose is to provide disease prevention, health education of the public and basic morbidity diagnosis and treatment.
- **Secondary Health Care**, which includes 73 hospitals with the aim to provide patients with in-hospital care.
- **Tertiary Health Care**, which includes hospitals (usually the ones in collaboration with University Medical Schools) equipped with state-of-the-art medical technologies and highly trained staff for the treatment of patients who are in need of more sophisticated and specialized care.

The main difference between the Primary and Secondary-Tertiary Health Care is that the former is supposed to focus on prevention, while the latter on disease cure and patients' treatment. Primary Health Care is also responsible for the provision of first aid and for the conduction of

the so-called triage. In case patients require further medical care, they are transferred to hospitals, which are part of the Secondary and Tertiary Health Care.

Apart from the categories mentioned above, there are also rural and regional medical centres that are governed by the health-office Regions of the Hellenic Health System, which are the following:

- 1st Health-office Region (Attica);
- 2nd Health-office Region (Peiraeus and the Aegean);
- 3rd Health-office Region (Macedonia);
- 4th Health-office Region (Macedonia and Thrace);
- 5th Health-office Region (Thessaly and Central Greece);
- 6th Health-office Region (Peloponnese, Ionian Islands, Epirus and Western Greece);
- 7th Health-office Region (Crete).

Health care

The following picture presents the distribution of the health care structures over Greece.

Figure 19 - The seven Health-office Regions of the Hellenic Health System (81)

First Aid Responders (FARs) in Greece are called Rescuers/Paramedics and Medical Doctors. They act in everyday medical incidents. FARs work for the National Centre for Emergency Care

(“EKAB” – the acronym referring to the Greek Emergency Medical Service), which operates under the supervision of the Ministry of Health.

Everyday incidents requiring emergency medical interference are the subject of the EMS and its 12 branches. There is also a special EMS department for cases of mass emergency, the so-called Special Department of Disasters’ Medicine, which operates coordinated by the country’s Civil Protection Agency.

Training and education to become a First Aid Responder are divided into two clusters, as does the role the FARs (Paramedics vs. Doctors).

Rescuers/paramedics are obliged to complete a two-and-a-half-year course in a Vocational Training Institute in Greece. They are trained (before their hiring) after finishing high school, attending one of the public or private Vocational Training Institutes, which all operate under the supervision of the General Secretariat for Lifelong Learning (a special department of the Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs). At the moment, there are 6 public centres of the kind (2 of them directly processed by the EMS) and 2 privates.

The EMS core (paramedics’) training:

- requires a professional driver’s license;
- lasts 5 semesters (1200h theoretical and 960h practical training);
- is followed by the National Examinations of Certification leading to a Level-5 degree;
- follows the ERC/BLS, ILS, ALS-PHTLS and PALS international protocols.

The national curriculum of the specialty consists of lessons on the following topics:

- Anatomy;
- Physiology;
- Hygiene – Microbiology;
- Planning of Emergency Prehospital Care;
- English (terminology);
- Evaluation and Support of Vital Functions;
- Physiopathology;
- Telecommunication Tactics;
- Telecommunication Systems;
- Emergency Pathology;
- Emergency Traumatology;
- Pharmacology;
- Massive Health Loss;
- Protocols;
- Patients’ Transport;
- Safe Driving Skills;
- Assistantship training (in the ER department of hospitals);
- Assistantship training (ambulance shifts).

Medical Doctors have to be graduates of any University Medicine School and may have additionally completed the postgraduate program of Emergency Pre-Hospital Medicine, in order to be more efficient in providing immediate and effective assistance to any acute health incident in the field. This program is organized by the training school of EMS and is a one-year course.

All FARs are charged (according to the respective Presidential Act of the EMS's establishment in 1988) with the duty to stabilize the victim's state at the scene (no matter the morbidity cause – pathological or accidental, nature of human induced) and to safely transport the patient to the closest and most appropriate health facility, providing the necessary support along the way.

5.2.1.7. Norway

In Norway training of first responders and first aid personnel is carried out according to a number of national standards. This includes police, firefighters, ambulances, airborne rescue units, mountain rescue, sea rescue, and coast guard, military and so on. In sea rescue of people, the operation is carried out by crew members from nearby boats, sea rescue services, firefighters or police in smaller or larger vessels depending on the distance from shore. In some cases, people will be picked up by helicopters also. All rescue personnel have a basic education in first aid. Rescued people are brought on shore and responsibility is taken over by an ambulance or other medical staff. At sea, all rescue sessions are coordinated by one of two Rescue control centres (Hovedredningsentraler).

A number of educations for first responders are available. From the basic level schooling of first responders in ambulances, fire brigade, police, sea rescue and similar operations. There is also more specialized education on BSc and MSc levels in crisis management and a number of other topics (some examples are given below).

There are also some special courses available for medical personnel like doctors and nurses related to sea and mountain rescue that are listed below.

- AGE 16-19 Ambulance first responder – Fagbrev (82)
- Bachelor: A part of basic training nursing (83)
- Master program example (84)
- CPD/specialization for medical doctors (mountain medicine) (85) (86)
- First aid Volunteers – Red Cross (87)
- Norwegian rescue dogs (88)

5.2.2. Identification of existing standards, procedures and protocols for first aid responses and for collaboration between medical teams and other first responders

5.2.2.1. At the European level

As described in section 5.2.1.1, WHO provides minimum standards for Emergency Medical Teams (EMT) (58).

Regarding the ambulance care and according to the report on Organization and practices of ambulance services in 14 European countries (65), in all countries under scrutiny protocols and guidelines, mostly nationwide, are being used by the ambulance care services personnel to follow their work. Medical doctors guiding ambulance transportations do follow these

guidelines too. In Ireland, Lithuania, Turkey, and the UK there are no medical doctors that are employed by ambulance services.

The following table summarises availability of national standards and protocols about ambulance care.

Country	Ambulance personnel	Emergency physician
Belgium	yes, national	no
Croatia	yes, national	yes, national
Czech Republic	yes, but not national	yes, national
Estonia	yes, national	yes, national
Germany	yes, but not national	yes, but not national
Hungary	yes, national	yes, national
Ireland	yes, national	not applicable
Latvia	yes, national	yes, national
Lithuania	yes, national	yes, but not national
The Netherlands	yes, national	yes, national
Norway	yes, but not national	yes
Portugal	Yes, national	yes
Spain	yes, but not national	yes, but not national
Turkey	yes, national	not applicable
United Kingdom	yes, but not national	not applicable

Table 3 – Protocols and standards about ambulance care (65)

Apart from standards, guidelines, issued by recognized associations, have also been developed, and they are widely adopted by First Responders' Organizations and can be implemented as best practices in emergency situations, as well as guidance instruments for the training of practitioners. One good example of the latter could be the training programme (89) developed by the International Search and Rescue Advisory Group (INSARAG) along with the support of the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies, for the enhancement of first responders' capacities.

Additionally, guidelines, widely adopted by the Fire and Rescue community in the EU, have been issued by first responders' and military organizations and agencies, while also European projects have provided significant results.

The following list includes guidelines related to the response to disasters of different nature, such as CBRN-E incidents, landscape fires and floods:

- Radioactive Accident Manual IAEA-CTIF: manual for First Responders to a Radiological Emergency by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). It provides practical guidance for those who will respond during the first few hours to a radiological emergency (referred to here as 'first responders') and for national officials who would support this early response. It provides guidance in the form of action guides, instructions, and supporting data that can be easily applied by a State to build a basic capability to respond to a radiological emergency (90)
- Tactics, command and leadership guideline: the book presents, discusses and exemplifies the experiences of municipal rescue services and the results of scientific research from many different perspectives (91)
- Guidelines for First Response to a CBRN incident by NATO: establishes procedural guidelines for strategic, operational and tactical planners responsible for CBRN preparedness and response (92)

- Hazardous Materials: operational Guidance for the Fire and Rescue service by the Fire and Rescue Service Operational Guidance of the United Kingdom: British Best Practice Guidance to help Fire and Rescue authorities to resolve incidents involving hazardous materials safely and efficiently (93)
- Forest Fire-Fighting Terms Handbook as a result of the EU “F.I.R.E. 4”: multilingual handbook for fire terms across European borders during forest fire fighting Project (94)
- CFPA-E Guideline No 1:2012 N Protection against flood by the European Fire Protection Associations (CFPA-E): This publication is intended to inform all the above target audiences in terms of flooding hazards and associated risks (Europe, 2012)
- Disability-inclusive Disaster Risk Reduction (DiDRR) by the European Disability Forum: a quick reference guide for practitioners in Europe and Central Asia (96)
- Action plan to improve public health preparedness and response in the WHO European Region 2018-2023 by the World Health Organization: action plan to improve public health preparedness and response in the WHO European Region, 2018–2023, aims to strengthen national and regional capacities to effectively prevent, prepare for, detect and respond to public health threats and emergencies and to provide support to affected countries, when necessary (97)

Furthermore, directives, issued by the Council of Europe and the European Commission, apply to the Member States of the European Union and are related to emergency response. The 2007/60/EC Directive (98) of the European Parliament and of the Council on the assessment and management of flood risks, as well as the 2012/18/EU Directive (99) of the European Parliament and of the Council for the control of major accidental hazards, involving dangerous substances, could provide good examples.

Within the EU Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM) a Knowledge Network has been created to improve prevention, preparedness, and response to disasters.

This EU Civil Protection Knowledge Network (100) connects civil protection practitioners, policy makers and researchers to share skills and good practices. It makes knowledge and expertise in Civil Protection and Disaster Risk Management grow, improving prevention, preparedness and response.

As a knowledge broker, the Knowledge Network is a tool to make relevant knowledge more accessible to the civil protection and disaster management actors, offering them a space to learn, work and grow together.

As a partnership facilitator, it connects a variety of stakeholders active at different levels, from local to international, governmental to non-governmental, and from the political to the scientific and operational, organising virtual and face-to-face events and financing joint and cross-sector initiatives.

It also acts as an innovation catalyst by stimulating research and facilitating the introduction and uptake of new technologies and processes in the field of civil protection and disaster management.

Their activities are:

- UCPM Training Programme;
- Exchange of Civil Protection Experts;
- UCPM Lessons Learnt Programme;
- Scientific advice & innovation;
- Thematic workshops & conferences;
- Awareness-raising activities;
- Community engagement;
- Partnerships facilitation opportunities;
- Civil protection exercises.

In the field of volunteering, Global First Aid Reference Centre (GFARC) acts as 'centre of excellence' of the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC) hosted by the French Red Cross. They work with National Societies to facilitate knowledge sharing between them and to promote quality first aid education at the global level. The purpose of GFARC is to serve as the IFRC's hub of technical expertise and to provide first-aid-related support to members. The platform (101) offers a range of learning materials, tools and guidance to support your National Society and their first aid training programmes.

Through extensive desktop research, a significant number of standards and widely adopted guidelines has been identified. These standards are developed either by European Standardization Bodies, e.g., European Committee for Standardization (CEN), or by international Bodies, such as International Organization for Standardization (ISO), International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) and International Telecommunication Union (ITU), among others. Furthermore, standards can be developed not only by civil, but also by military organizations, e.g., NATO. The following standards can be applied to a wide spectrum of first responders' operations and cover many different aspects of first response. Technical standards related to the equipment of medical vehicles, standards for the training of First Responders to mass Chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear substances and explosives (CBRN-E) incidents, standards for Search and Rescue operations, standards for the coordination of volunteers and for the interoperability of devices are identified among other issues. European and international standards have been taken into consideration, as well as both civil and military ones:

- EN 1846-1:2011: European Standard establishes classes and defines categories which are functions of the use and mass of the firefighting and rescue service vehicles and provides a designation system that gives the various criteria used for characterizing the vehicles (102)
- EN 1846-2:2009+A1:2013: this European Standard specifies the common requirements for safety and the (minimum) common performance requirements of firefighting and rescue service vehicles as designated in EN 1846-1 (103)
- EN 1846-3:2013: this part of this European Standard specifies the minimum requirements for safety and performance of some optional specific permanently installed equipment on firefighting and rescue service vehicles, operated by trained persons, as designated in EN 1846-1 and specified in EN 1846-2 (104)

- CEN/TR 15872:2014: this Technical Report addresses the issue of multiple identifiers that may refer to the same person. It describes the management of patient identification and cross-referencing of identities and provides some practical guidance for addressing implementation of standards, reports, guidelines, methods, etc. (105)
- EN13718-2:2015+A1:2020: this part of EN 13718 specifies the requirements for performance and equipping for air ambulances, including requirements for interfaces to medical devices used for the transport and treatment of sick or injured persons (106)
- EN 1789:2020: this European Standard specifies requirements for the design, testing, performance and equipping of road ambulances used for the transport, monitoring, treatment and care of patients (107)
- EN 1865-1:2010+A1:2015: it defines minimum requirements for the design and performance of stretchers and other patient handling equipment used in road ambulances for the handling and carrying of patients. It aims to ensure patient safety and minimize the physical effort required by staff operating the equipment (108)
- EN 1865-2:2010+A1:2015: This European Standard defines minimum requirements for the design and performance of power assisted stretchers used in road ambulances for the treatment and transportation of patients. It aims to ensure patient safety and minimize the physical effort required by staff operating the equipment (109)
- EN 1865-3:2012+A1:2015: it specifies minimum requirements for the design and performance of heavy-duty stretchers used in road ambulances for the treatment and transportation of patients. It aims to ensure patient safety and minimize the physical effort required by staff operating the equipment. (EN 1865-3:2012+A1:2015. Patient handling equipment used in road ambulances - Part 3: Heavy duty stretcher)
- EN 1865-4:2012: this European Standard defines the minimum requirements for the design and performance of foldable patient transfer chairs, which are used for the conveyance of patients to and/or from road ambulances. It aims to ensure patient safety and to minimize the physical effort required by staff operating the equipment. (111)
- EN 1865-5:2012: This European Standard specifies the minimum requirements for the design and performance of stretcher supports that are installed in road ambulances to hold the main stretcher or incubator systems in accordance with EN 1865-1, EN 1865-2 and EN 13976-2 to ensure patient and operators safety and to minimise the physical effort required by staff operating the equipment. In this European Standard reference is made to EN 1789 (112)
- ITU-T Y.4102/Y.2074 (01/2015): Requirements for Internet of things devices and operation of Internet of things applications during disasters (113)
- ISO 22319:2017: it provides guidelines for planning the involvement of spontaneous volunteers (SVs) in incident response and recovery. (114)
- NATO Standard AMedP-7.2 CBRN First Aid Handbook: provide a standardised approach to the early management of any casualty in a CBRN threat-environment¹ by non-medical personnel from point of exposure (or recognition) until handover to medical personnel at a casualty collection or exchange Point (115)
- NATO Standard AMedP-7.3 Training of medical personnel for CBRN defence: describes the training requirements for deployed medical personnel providing CBRN medical support on NATO operations (116)

- ISO 22398:2013: it recommends good practice and guidelines for an organization to plan, conduct, and improve its exercise projects which may be organized within an exercise programme (117)
- NFPA 473: this standard identifies the levels of competence required of emergency medical services (EMS) personnel who respond to incidents involving hazardous materials or weapons of mass destruction (WMD) (118)
- ASTM F2751-16: this guide establishes the minimum training requirements, including general and field knowledge, skills, and abilities, for personnel who perform land search and rescue without ropes. (119)
- ASTM F2685-14: this guide establishes the minimum training standard for Land Search Team Leaders as it relates to their general, field, and search-specific knowledge, skills, and experience. (ASTM F2685-14. Standard Guide for Training of a Land Search Team Leader (STL))

5.2.2.2. Spain

In Spain, health competencies are transferred from the state to the autonomous communities, so **there is no homogeneity in the response to incidents with multiple victims.**

Health care in these situations is included in the service portfolio of emergency medical services, but not all of these services have specific resources or procedures.

Regarding operating procedures, each region has its own procedure for the assistance to incidents with multiple victims, and there is no standard procedure at national level.

Not all regions have a multi-victim procedure or it is not public. **Operational procedures for health care in multiple casualty incidents** have been found in the following regions:

- Aragón (061-Aragón): Special plan for out-of-hospital health action in collective emergencies and catastrophes (121)
- Canarias (SUC 061): Canary Islands Health Emergency Plan (122)
- Cantabria (061 Cantabria) (123)
- Castilla y León: Disaster plan and care for multiple victims. (Manual de asistencia sanitaria en accidentes de múltiples víctimas)
- Galicia: Emergency plan (125) (126)
- Madrid (SUMMA 112): Handbook for the management of multiple casualty incidents in out-of-hospital emergency care (127)
- Madrid (SAMUR-PC) (128)

In relation to **coordination procedures** between emergency health services and other services, some regions have a procedure for joint action in road accidents.

- Andalucía (129)
- C. Madrid (130)
- C. Valenciana: Joint action plan for traffic accidents (131)

And some regions have specific procedures for **incidents in special situations**. This is the case in Galicia which does have a plan which includes protocols for action in special situations such as landslides, terrorist attacks, air, traffic or train accidents or tunnels. Or Cantabria which has

operational protocols for search and rescue in the mountains and rural areas, on the coast and beaches and in caves. Also, for emergencies in road tunnels. Additionally, in Madrid there are procedures for joint action with other agents in critical structures (airports, subway, and tunnel system).

At **international level**, the Spanish Agency for International Development Cooperation (AECID) has a Spanish Technical Team for Emergency Aid and Response (START) which includes health personnel. This team is part of the catalogue of resources available in the European Civil Protection Mechanism of the European Commission and is classified by the World Health Organisation.

There are other Spanish teams registered in the European Civil Protection Mechanism for emergency assistance such as ERICAM (INSARAG certified equipment)

Regarding procedures between **neighbouring countries**, a protocol on technical cooperation and mutual assistance in the field of civil protection exists between Spain and Portugal.

And there are European projects working on cross-border cooperation between Spain and France, such as the EGALURG and HELINET projects. Both projects aim to create a cross-border cooperation network to improve the response to collective emergencies that occur in areas bordering both countries.

In the Ariem+ European Project, cross-border exercises were carried out in which Galicia, Castilla León and the north of Portugal collaborated both in prevention and extinction of fires and in the search and rescue of victims.

In the European project HeliNET, co-financed through the Spain-France-Andorra Interregional Program (POCTEFA 2014-2020) and the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), a simulation was carried out to validate joint action guides to manage an MCI by promoting the use of helicopters between the Emergency Centres of the Basque Country, Navarra and Nouvelle Aquitaine.

5.2.2.3. Portugal

In Portugal, there are protocols for response in Basic Life Support (firefighters, first responders of the Portuguese Red Cross and pre-hospital emergency technicians of the INEM), and protocols for Advanced Life Support (SAV) teams (doctors and nurses).

These protocols are issued by the INEM, which is the state entity responsible for medical emergency in Portugal. All these protocols are based on international algorithms and guidelines. They are updated according to international regulation and the latest scientific evidence. The following are examples of some manuals:

- Basic Life Support Manual (132);
- Advanced Life Support Manual (133);
- Exception Situation Manual (134);
- Manual of Standards - Paediatric and Obstetric Emergencies (135);
- Manual of Techniques for the Extraction and Immobilization of Trauma Victims (136);

There are also basic first aid procedures implemented and followed by all entities:

- Victim Approach Manual (137)

Typically, before EMS arrive to an occurrence, the first teams to arrive and report it are the Basic Life Support (BLS) teams, because there are more of them, and they are distributed throughout the territory with less distance between them; the Advanced Life Support (ALS) teams are fewer in number and have greater distances between them.

Example: the district of Évora has only 1 Advanced Life Support vehicle and it gives support to firefighters in all municipalities (14 corporations).

Thus, these BLS teams rescue the victims according to the protocol for their competence/authority and pass the data from their assessment to the responsible entity (INEM), which decides if it sends more differentiated means to the site.

It may happen that BLS and ALS means are activated simultaneously for the same occurrence, when the person requesting help has already identified a life-threatening situation.

In terms of interoperability for different types of first responders, in Europe, a series of natural disasters and terrorist attacks have spread the concern for the repetition incidents of such kind, which despite being the responsibility of individual member states, generate concern to the European Union, which has promoted the common response to crisis and disaster management. The most common is the Community Civil Protection Mechanism, an agreement that links the member states' Civil Protection agencies and coordinates mutual assistance, in any kind of danger or disaster.

5.2.2.4. Slovakia

The Emergency Medical Service (EMS) provides urgent pre-hospital health care in critical situations that endanger the lives or health of citizens. Emergency medical services are provided by emergency medical service operating centres (line 112 or 155) and health care providers on the basis of a permit to operate an emergency medical service ambulance. It is part of the integrated rescue system (IRS) and the procedure of IRS units is mutually coordinated when providing assistance in distress.

The coordination of emergency services is provided by 112, 150, 160 and Mountain Rescue services dispatching, etc.

The integrated European-alike system 112 provides a dispatching services and communication with different rescue service responders. Concerning the first aid response, in particular urgent medical care, it is the Emergency Medical Service (EMS) who is in charge of this.

The Emergency Medical Service (EMS) provides urgent pre-hospital health care in critical situations that endanger the lives or health of citizens. Emergency medical services are provided by emergency medical service operating centres (line 112 or 155) and health care providers on the basis of a permit to operate an emergency medical service ambulance. It is part of the integrated rescue system (IRS) and the procedure of IRS units is mutually coordinated when providing assistance in distress.

- 150 medical services
- 112 IRS
- 18300 Mountain Rescue Services

- 160 Police
- 155 Fire fighters
- Helpline for children (Linka detskej istoty) – non-stop telephone service: 116 111
- Hotline for women subjected to violence – non-stop telephone service: +421 800 212 212

The basic processes of EMS ambulance and medical helicopter, other medical vehicles responses to an event

The EMS ambulance is activated by the operations centre. After activation, the ambulance is obliged to go to the intervention within 2 minutes. The task of the ambulance crew is to accept the instructions of the operating centre, to perform all actions necessary to provide emergency assistance and, if necessary, to ensure the transport of the affected person to the medical facility.

The crew of the ambulance outpatient clinic performs the following activities as part of the intervention:

- In the event of mass disabilities – follows the instructions of the commander of the medical intervention, sorts the wounded and, as the commander of the medical intervention, coordinates the rescue team.
- Obtains an anamnesis, i.e. data on the difficulties encountered necessary for a correct diagnosis. In many cases it leads directly to the diagnosis (up to 50%) or very significantly narrows the range of possible diseases, or directs further research.
- Monitors, evaluates and records vital functions using appropriate clinical and technical aids.
- Performs an assessment of a person's state of health and determines an occupational diagnosis.
- Performs the initial treatment of all injuries, including stopping bleeding.
- Performs airway cleansing, ensures airway patency with available means and techniques. Uses respiratory protection in artificial lung ventilation, provides oxygen therapy and inhalation therapy.
- Provides peripheral venous access, including intraosseous access, and provides saline to maintain venous access.
- Prepares the ECG curve and performs its assessment and evaluation.
- Performs basic neurological examination and determines the working diagnosis of stroke.
- Position and immobilize the person, taking into account the extent and nature of the injury or illness. Frees the injured if it does not endanger his life or health, immobilizes the injured parts of the person's body.
- Performs cardiopulmonary resuscitation; uses an automatic and semi-automatic external defibrillator.
- Treats pneumothorax with available means and techniques, introduces gastric probes.
- Introduces a urinary catheter in women, treats drains, peripheral vascular catheters, permanent urinary catheters, probes, cannulas and stoma.
- Takes biological material if necessary, draws capillary blood and venous blood for diagnostic purposes.

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- Heats or cools a person in case of accidents caused by low or high temperatures.
- Treats amputate suitable for replantation.
- Uses a magnet with inadequate implantable cardioverter-defibrillator function.
- Ensures the transport of a person and participates in the transport of a person from the place of the event to the ambulance service vehicle by available means and means, if it does not endanger his life or health in such a serious way.
- Continuously monitors the state of health, ensures basic vital functions and satisfies the needs of a person related to health, illness and dying.
- Maintains radio, telephone and data communication with the emergency medical service operational center and with all components of the integrated rescue system, cooperates in field navigation.
- Ensures the safety of the intervention if it does not endanger his life or health in such a serious way.
- Cooperates in the navigation of the helicopter ambulance medical service in the field.
- Provides care for the body of the dead person.

During the response Health Assessment Record (HAR) is prepared. The report looks like this:

The image shows a detailed medical form titled "ZÁZNAM O ZHODNOTENÍ ZDRAVOTNÉHO STAVU OSOBY" (Record of Assessment of the Patient's Health Status). The form is organized into several sections:

- Header:** Includes fields for "Podatelia poskytovateľa" (Provider), "Výjazd č." (Trip No.), "R. P." (Rural/Urban), "R. č." (Region No.), "MIESTO:" (Location), "Dátum:" (Date), "Príchod:" (Arrival), "Hlásiť:" (Report), "Odoslanie:" (Dispatch), "Ukončenie:" (End).
- Personal Data:** "PRIEZVISKO:" (Surname), "MENO:" (Name), "BYDLISKO:" (Residence), "MIESTO:" (Location), "DŮVOD:" (Reason), "Anamnéza (DA, LA, AA, TO): poskytnutie PP: áno/nie" (Anamnesis: PP provided: yes/no).
- Physical Examination:** A grid of checkboxes for various body systems: "Hrdlo:" (Neck), "Prsne orgány:" (Chest organs), "Srdce a krvný obeh:" (Heart and circulation), "Pľučníky:" (Lungs), "Stomáček:" (Stomach), "Obličky:" (Kidneys), "Močový mechúr:" (Urinary bladder), "Črevá:" (Intestines), "Koža:" (Skin), "Kĺby:" (Joints), "Muskulatura:" (Musculature), "Nervový systém:" (Nervous system), "Zrak:" (Vision), "Sluch:" (Hearing), "Vnútorné orgány:" (Internal organs).
- Vital Signs:** "Tlak:" (Blood pressure), "Časť:" (Pulse), "Teplota:" (Temperature), "Sýť:" (SpO2), "Časť:" (Respiration rate), "Časť:" (Heart rate).
- Diagnosis and Treatment:** "Diagnóza:" (Diagnosis), "Liečenie:" (Treatment), "Poznámky:" (Notes).
- Signature and Date:** "Podpis:" (Signature), "Dátum:" (Date).

Figure 20 - Health Assessment Record

HAR is a legal document that is kept in accordance with the provisions of Act on the Emergency Medical Service as well as the Decree of the Ministry of Health of the SR. HAR is led by a responsible person of ambulance (doctor or paramedic in case of "RZP" type). At the same time, it is official document for assessment and evaluation.

HAR is written exclusively on the prescribed form legibly, truthfully in two copies (original and copy). Part of the documentation of the trip, which may be the subject of an investigation procedure, are following documents:

- Record of receipt of the instruction by the Regional Operations Centre;
- HAR – Health Assessment Record;
- ECG recording, if it is required upon treated person's health condition;
- Recordings of communication with the Regional Operations Centre;
- Other documentation.

In case of MCI, the event can be classified for the need of mutual communication based on the number of injured and affected people as is stated in the table:

Degree	Scope
ALFA	3 – 50 injured and affected persons, from which at least 3 – 20 with serious threat to health or life.
BRAVO	51 – 100 injured and affected persons, from which at least 20 – 50 with serious threat to health or life.
CHARLIE	101 – 1000 injured and affected persons, from which at least 50 – 300 with serious threat to health or life.
DELTA	More than 1000 injured and affected persons, of which more than half are with a serious threat to health or life.

Table 4 – MCI event classification for communication needs

Especially in case of MCI, procedure of triage is applied. The rescue operation is organized in order to save as many injured as possible. Main tasks are:

- activation of EMS means
- in case of CBRN event, PPE and decontamination have to be applied
- triage of injured persons
- removal of injured persons to a designated place (nest of injured people)
- provision of urgent medical care
- removal of injured to hospitals (according to urgency)

Medical intervention management consists mainly of:

- medical intervention commander, in WHITE vest (with the inscription of the position)
- triage commander, in YELLOW vest (with the inscription of the position)
- nest of injured people commander, in RED vest (with the inscription of the position)
- removal (transport) commander, in BLUE vest (with the inscription of the position)

Cooperation on international, cross-border and cross-sectorial level.

With regards to international cooperation, Slovak forces and resources are part of UCPM and other mechanisms. Activities are managed by Ministry of Foreign Affairs of SR, Ministry of Interior of SR and Ministry of Health of SR. This topic is not detailed described in this chapter.

Slovakia has individual agreements and memoranda on mutual cooperation and support in case of extraordinary events with neighbouring countries. Similar documents exist also on the level of neighbouring regions (regions sharing state border). These agreements have proved effective, especially in the initial hours of the intervention and create the conditions for building mutual

relations, which significantly contributes to the sustainability of such cooperation. Unfortunately, recent Corona restrictions negatively affected these efforts.

Cross-sectorial cooperation is a bit issue within Slovakia. A significant part of EMS providers is private companies. Their participation in multi-agency training, exercises as well as research and development is complicated, as it represents an extra expenditure (time of the personnel, equipment blocking, financial costs). Such activities are not directly stated in particular law. This represents the great room for improvement.

5.2.2.5. Bulgaria

Through extensive research, a significant number of standards and widely adopted guidelines has been identified.

In Bulgaria there are a lot of documents concerning standards, procedures and protocols for first aid responses and for collaboration between medical teams and other first responders. But, more of them are connected with a different level of administrative structures, relate to rules and procedures within an individual municipality, ministry or organization, and include a variety of management approaches. Also, they are predominantly about common information regarding the organization for first aid process, and are not precisely developed procedures.

In short, the main documents in the field of such standards, procedures and protocols are:

Disaster and protection act (<https://www.lex.bg/laws/ldoc/2135540282>)

The law regulates public relations related to ensuring the protection of life and health of the population, protection of the environment and property in case of disasters. Disaster protection planning is carried out at the municipal, regional and national levels.

The main components of the Unified Rescue System (URS) are the General Directorate "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" of the Ministry of Interior, the regional directorates of the Ministry of Interior, the Bulgarian Red Cross and the centres for emergency medical care.

The other components of the unified rescue system provide assistance upon request under disaster protection plans. The Armed Forces will provide assistance in carrying out rescue and emergency rescue operations with the permission of the Minister of Defence on the basis of a request.

The coordination of the constituent parts of the unified rescue system is carried out through the operational centers of the General Directorate "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" of the Ministry of Interior.

Operational centers:

- Receive and evaluate information on occurred disasters;
- Notify the competent components of the unified rescue system and coordinate further activities on the basis of standard operating procedures;
- Carry out early warning and announcement of the bodies of the executive power, the constituent parts of the unified rescue system and the population in case of disasters;
- Organize the inclusion of the components of the unified rescue system provided for in the disaster protection plans, as well as of additional forces and means.

ORDINANCE № 3 of 6.10.2017 for confirmation of the medical standard "Emergency medicine"

(https://www.mh.government.bg/media/filer_public/2018/04/10/naredba_3_ot_6102017_g_za_utvyrijdavane_na_medicinski_standart_spesna_medicina.pdf)

The mentioned ordinance are described elements of the diagnostic-treatment process in the scope of medical specialist of "Emergency medicine". It is mentioned that the practice of the medical specialty "Emergency Medicine" includes the following main elements: Medical triage; Medical control; Initial (primary) assessment, stabilization and life - saving actions of emergency patient; Physical examination; Clinical emergency resolution; Transport of the emergency patient and other activities.

According to the document and regarding the procedures for first aid responders, the medical triage is a basic element and practical tool of the diagnostic and treatment process in the scope of the specialty "Emergency Medicine", the application of which all emergency patients are grouped into categories (groups) by using a standard medical triage system. **Medical triage** is a process of distribution (sorting) of patients by setting medical priority depending on the degree of urgency and the patient's necessary diagnosis, treatment or transportation within the scope of specialty "Emergency Medicine", including in cases of disasters and accidents.

Medical triage involves assessing the degree of urgency of each emergency patient by defining a triage category. Defining a triage category in an emergency patient assesses the degree of emergency (degree of urgency) and provides differences in medical priority and time frame for implementation of diagnostic and treatment actions in an emergency patient in outpatient and inpatient settings depending on the available human, instrumental and instrumental resources for the implementation of measures and actions. The categories are:

Critical emergency patient (code red - A1) - the patient is with life-threatening signs and symptoms due to illness or injury with high probability of death if not taken immediately interventions to prevent subsequent respiratory instability function, circulation and / or neurological function.

Unstable / potentially unstable emergency patient (code yellow - B2) - relative urgency - the patient is at suspected risk and potential danger to life, there are signs and symptoms due to illness or injury, which can progress in severity and lead to high complications likelihood of severe consequences for vital functions, systems or organs if treatment is not given quickly at a certain time framework in the case of relative urgency of the condition.

Stable emergency patient (code green - C3) - minimum emergency – at the patient has signs and symptoms due to illness or injury with low potential and risk of severe consequences or complications and progress to a more serious condition.

The communication among the first aid responders is carried out through these steps: telecommunication (telephone) triage, priority team triage, medical triage at the scene and transport medical triage, dispersed transport triage.

The communication activities in the outpatient structures are performed between the coordination centre and the mobile emergency teams (external), between the mobile

emergency teams themselves (external), among the members of the mobile emergency services teams (internal), between the focal point and the Ministry of healthcare with the content of the information defined in this standard flow.

Regulations for the structure and activity of the Centre for emergency medical care (<https://www.lex.bg/laws/ldoc/-12794368>)

The document regulates the structure and activity of the centre for emergency medical care. The main activities of the centre are related to:

- Providing emergency medical care to sick and injured persons;
- Provision of specialized emergency transport to patients, donors and organs, blood, blood components and equipment, republican consultants for emergency medical care;
- Training of specialists in emergency medicine and long-term qualification.
- Bulgaria's Disaster Protection Act, and especially annually developed **Disaster Protection Plans** (national, regional and local) regulate the roles and interaction between the components of the Unified Rescue System.
- **The Act on the National Emergency Call System Employing the Single European Number "112"** regulates the operation of the 112 dispatcher centres.

Roles and operating procedures of the structures involved in rescue operations are described in the specific parts of the Disaster Protection Act covering several emergency scenarios, in ordinances and instructions issued by the executive authority, which are periodically reviewed and updated.

Examples:

- Instruction No. 81213-418 of April 5, 2021 on the conditions and procedure for the implementation of emergency recovery activities, operational protection in floods and search and rescue operations, and on chemical, biological and radiation protection.
- Regulations on the structure and activity of a centre for emergency medical care, last update 5 June 2020.

In terms of education and training, medical education is provided by four medical universities and two medical faculties in other universities. The Council of Ministers determines the requirements for obtaining both higher education degrees and specialisations. Professional specialties in health provision are determined by the Ministry of Health and require a state examination by the State Examination Commission in Sofia. Continuous medical education is organised and credited by the Professional Associations in accordance with the Public Health Act.

The Ministry of Internal Affairs is the main authority which is responsible for the conditions and algorithm in cases of emergent recovery, operational protection, in cases of floods and operations for investigation and saving, for chemical, biological and radioactive protection of the civilians. The Ministry of Internal Affairs has not only strict guidelines, structure, rules and algorithm of action, but also directives for emergent situations such as natural disasters, floods, earthquakes, biological, chemical and radioactive threat.

The information in the directives is well-organized, posted and structured. There are specific details for each situation and crises that appear. The main issue that appears as an obstacle for a smooth, adequate, process with speedy reaction is the **lack of cooperation, combined skills and mutual assistance between the different participants in the First Aid providers' area**. Each institution, organization and team possess the necessary skills and has the knowledge of reaction, but do not have the right communication system and coordination to achieve the best possible results.

After revising the main documents, the **following gaps were noticed**:

- there are no uniform national standards of action for all participants - rescuers, medical teams, volunteers, firefighters, military and others;
- there are no standard operating procedures for first aid, search and rescue in the affected area and for evacuation as well;
- uniform protocols for the conduct of the individual first aid services have not been developed - medics, rescuers, firefighters, military, volunteers, the Bulgarian Red Cross, other organizations that operate together in the disaster area.

5.2.2.6. Greece

Additionally, to the EU directives and standards, agreements between cooperating countries which are not members of the EU also exist. These agreements ensure cooperation and mutual assistance between the involved countries in case of emergencies and incidents that require trans-border collaboration. The Black Sea Economic Cooperation (BSEC) has issued such an agreement (AGREEMENT among the Governments of the Participating States of the Black Sea Economic Cooperation (BSEC) on collaboration in Emergency Assistance and Emergency Response to natural and man-made Disasters), which binds Ukraine, Russia, Turkey, Georgia, Armenia, Bulgaria, Greece, Azerbaijan, Romania, Albania and Moldova, in order to provide assistance and response forces in the field of natural and man-made disasters.

- Basic First Aid Procedures
- Basic steps to be implemented before EMS arrive;
- Approaches to improve interoperability for different types of first responders (e.g., firefighters, medical responders, police, civil protection) from your country, and if you are aware at EU level.

5.2.2.7. Norway

In Norway, there are national standards for partners participating in all kinds of rescue missions including collecting oil spills, chemicals and so on below is an example of a standard developed for rescue personnel in helicopters (Airborne rescue). Such standards are also available for surface rescue, sea rescue, fire fighters, and so on. These standards are mainly in Norwegian.

Norwegian standard for rescue personnel on Helicopters (139).

5.2.3. Identification of existing capabilities for first aid responses

5.2.3.1. The European level

The existing capabilities at the European level are described in the following sections.

rescEU reserve

In 2019, the European Commission upgraded the UCPM and created rescEU (140) reserve to reinforce and strengthen components of the EU's disaster risk management.

The rescEU establishes a new European reserve of resources (the 'rescEU reserve') which includes a fleet of firefighting planes and helicopters, medical evacuation planes, as well as a stockpile of medical items and field hospitals that can respond to health emergencies.

The EU is also developing a reserve to respond to chemical, biological, radiological, and nuclear incidents.

When the scale of an emergency overwhelms the possibilities of a country to respond on its own, it can request assistance via the UCPM.

Once activated, the EU channels through the Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC) offers of assistance made available by its Member States and Participating States.

The European Civil Protection Pool

The European Civil Protection Pool (141) is a collection of emergency response teams and assets. It functions as a virtual collection of resources, which remain under the command and control of the Participating States in the UCPM.

Countries that participate in the UCPM make these resources available for collective European emergency response operations. In return, they can benefit from EU financial support.

The Pool includes resources such as urban search and rescue teams, forest fire fighting capacities, emergency medical teams, water purification equipment, high-capacity pumping units, etc.

Resources in the Pool are available for immediate deployment worldwide, following a request for assistance through the European Commission's ERCC.

The certification of resources in the European Civil Protection Pool generally follows a three-step process: a consultative visit, a table-top exercise and a field exercise.

Figure 21 - Phases and steps in the certification and registration process (142)

During the consultative visit, the responsible desk officer in the Commission verifies and discusses the information given in the application with relevant interlocutors at technical and political levels in the country concerned. A questionnaire guides this visit.

The table-top exercise serves to test the decision-making and managerial preparations associated with a deployment of the resource. A certification grid for table-top exercises guides the Commission representative and peer certifiers in this process.

The field exercise provides an opportunity to test operational aspects during the different phases of an international deployment. A certification grid for field exercises provides guidance to the certification team.

The 2018 Commission Implementing Decision Amending Decision 1313/2013/EU determined the need for re-certification at the latest after 5 years: “the certification of a module, technical assistance and support team, other response capacities, or expert should be reassessed at the latest after 5 years if the asset is submitted for reregistration into the EERC” (Article 16.8).

The European Medical Corps

The European Medical Corps (143) enables quick medical assistance and public health expertise from all EU Member States and Participating States to a health emergency inside and outside the EU. The deployment is coordinated by the EU’s ERCC, the operational hub of the UCPM. The European Medical Corps gathers all medical response capacities committed by Member States to the European Civil Protection Pool. Following a request for European assistance, medical capacities can be drawn from this Pool and from other Member States’ response capacities.

Medical capacities available:

- **Emergency medical teams (EMT)** provide direct medical care to people affected by a disaster. These teams are certified to ensure they meet quality standards by the World Health Organization (WHO). So far, Norway, Germany, Belgium, Italy, Spain, Portugal, France, Estonia, and the Czech Republic have committed such teams. The Italian, Norwegian, Portuguese, and Spanish Emergency Medical teams have been classified by the WHO, while an additional 9 other European medical teams are currently in the process of classification. In addition, Germany contributes a specialised infectious disease isolation field hospital from the German Red Cross.
- **Mobile biosafety laboratories** were developed and deployed during the 2014 Ebola crisis. Belgium has since committed its B-Life Lab (Biological Light Fieldable Laboratory for Emergencies) and Germany the European Mobile Laboratory, coordinated by the Bernhard-Nocht-Institute for Tropical Medicine.
- **Medical evacuation capacities** are key for mass casualty disasters requiring the evacuation of EU citizens, and for retrieving humanitarian and medical workers from disaster areas, if needed. Currently, Sweden provides such assets to the European Medical Corps, while Slovakia is in the process of certifying its committed capacity.

5.2.3.2. Spain

In Spain there is no homogeneity in the emergency medical services, so that the capacities for attending incidents with multiple victims vary from one autonomous community to another.

Health care in these situations is included in the service portfolio of emergency medical services, but not all of these services have specific resources.

Some regions have disaster support units with specific personnel and equipment. This equipment includes medical outposts, health care support equipment chests and logistic vehicles. We have found information on the following autonomous communities:

- Andalucía: has a collective disaster and emergency support unit with medical and support material and an advanced medical post (144), (145), (146)
- Islas Canarias: has specific resources such as a mobile disaster unit, logistical support vehicles and immediate health response teams (147)
- Cantabria: has a unit to respond to incidents with multiple victims and catastrophes made up of a field hospital, support material for medical assistance and a logistical support vehicle (148)
- Galicia: has ground vehicle chests and medical helicopters and logistical support vehicles (149)
- Madrid: has Logistic Support Vehicle (150) and different type of ambulances (151)

In the community of Madrid there is a specific department of management of catastrophes and special situations that deals with all extraordinary events that occur in the autonomous community. It is equipped with a medical coordinator and two responsible for R + D + I and special devices and international missions. There is a common Triage card between both services of emergencies in the community with backpacks of catastrophe and a protocol agreed between different institutions and official organizations.

In addition, the Community of Madrid has a special CBRN catastrophic vehicle with the capacity of a decontamination line for patients with reduced mobility and two other decontamination lines for patients with preserved mobility. On the other hand, we have a communications vehicle with 4G WIFI, two telecommunications stations and a meeting table for the advanced health command post. There are procedures for the integration of telecommunications with the Military Unit of Emergencies called TETRAPOL.

5.2.3.3. Portugal

Radio communication through SIRESP (Integrated System of Emergency and Security Networks of Portugal). It consists of a shared national infrastructure that ensures the communication needs of the response units, emergency and security services. It uses shared digital trunking technology, which, in case of emergency, allows the centralization of the command and coordination of the various forces and security services involved.

SIRESP uses TETRA technology, which allows the creation of tight conversation groups, one for each entity using the network (e.g., PSP – Public Security Police, ANEPC – Civil Protection, GNR – National Guard, INEM, etc.) with the possibility of creating subgroups or multi-groups, ensuring simultaneous conversation with several entities.

The iTTeams platform - the acronym for INEM Tool for Emergency Alert Medical System. This platform was developed by INEM and it is a tool for interactive support between the CODU and the means on the ground which, through data entry, enables the stratification of the clinical severity of occurrences and contributes to a better management of means in more serious situations. iTTeams is available in all INEM emergency services. The intention of INEM is to extend this platform to other means of SIEM (Integrated System of Medical Emergency), such as the Fire Department or the Portuguese Red Cross.

5.2.3.4. Slovakia

In Slovakia there is centralized rescue system including the emergency medical services, so that the capacities for attending incidents, including MCI, are managed from “one” place.

Forces and resources are deployed base on the need and current situation. Once it is identified, that national capacities are not sufficient to handle the event, cross-border, respectively international help is activated. As it is described above, main role in case of emergency event plays Integrated Rescue System (IRS).

The IRS is a coordinated procedure of its components with goal to ensure their readiness and performing of activities and emergency assistance measures. It is the Act no. 129/2002 Coll. which regulates the organization of the IRS, the scope and tasks of state administration bodies and rescue services within the IRS, the rights and obligations of municipalities and other legal entities, natural persons entitled to business and other natural persons in coordinating assistance activities if life is imminent, health, property or the environment. In this system operates (1) Ministry of Interior, (2) Ministry of Health, (3) District Offices, including coordination centers and (4) Rescue Services.

Rescue components of IRS are:

- BASIC Rescue services (Fire&Rescue Service, EMS providers, Control Chemical Laboratories, Mountain Rescue Service, Mining Rescue Service.)

- OTHER Rescue services (Slovak Armed Forces, municipality fire brigades, company fire brigades and corps, workplaces performing state supervision or activities according to special regulations, civil protection units, municipality police, Slovak Red Cross, other legal persons and natural persons whose object of activity is to provide assistance for the protection of life, health and property.
- Police departments.

Emergency medical service providers is an executive component of EMS. Emergency Medical Service Network consists of 328 emergency medical service stations purposefully located in the territory of the Slovak Republic in order to ensure adequate availability of urgent medical care. In continuous readiness for interventions are:

- 86 ambulances "RLP",
 - some RLP ambulances are specially equipped as "MIJ" mobile intensive care units.
- 188 ambulances of emergency medical service "RZP"
 - 47 ambulances of ambulance "RZP-S", designed especially for the so-called secondary transfers between hospitals
- 7 ambulances of the helicopter rescue medical service "VZZS".

Ambulance staffing:

- "RLP" type consists of 3 members: (1) a doctor specializing in emergency medicine, anaesthesiology or intensive care (possibly with another specialization); (2) a paramedic and (3) an ambulance driver, or doctor and two paramedics (one in the driver's position).
- "RZP" type consists of 2 members: paramedic and ambulance driver, or two paramedics (one in the driver's position).
- "VZZS" type consists of 3 members: (1) a doctor (specializing in emergency medicine, anaesthesiology and intensive care / possibly with another specialization); (2) a paramedic and (3) a pilot.

Subsequent medical facilities:

- Medical facilities: the Ministry of Health of the Slovak Republic issued a decision for 59 inpatient medical facilities, based on the Resolution of the Government of the Slovak Republic no. 474/2012. Other medical facilities may be determined by the Minister of Health of the Slovak Republic in a state of crisis by order of the Minister.
- 27 spas: combination of private and state facilities of the Ministry of Defence of the Slovak Republic and the Ministry of Interior of the Slovak Republic.

Each type of outpatient clinic must be equipped with means to provide care for life-threatening conditions (defibrillator, including pacemaker, ECG, intravenous drug delivery equipment, intravenous drug delivery equipment, etc.), respiratory and airway care (various types of airway devices, ventilator, aspirator, oxygen), equipment for immobilizing the spine and limbs in case of injuries (splints, vacuum mattress, long and short spine plate, fixation neck collars), equipment for events with mass disabilities and devices for transport. EMS crews provide mainly so-called primary trips (trips during which primary health care is provided, i.e., the EMS crew is

the first contact), but also secondary interventions, i.e., transfers between institutional medical facilities, it is mainly a transfer to a higher type workplace. Healthcare providers are responsible for the operation of a specific outpatient clinic, for its equipment, staffing and also for the establishment of a headquarters, i.e., an intervention centre.

Information support/tools:

1. The main part creates **CoordCom™** (a product of Ericsson, which is adapted to the specific requirements of the IRS in the SR). It is an integrated call and control system for emergency, telephone and security providers. CoordCom integrates functions for telephone, radio and data communication between incident reporters, the operator and seconded means, such as the police, fire and rescue services, the emergency medical service and other emergency service providers. It includes GIS layer and features.
2. For FRS units (only for them) there is also **GINA** system, which is extension of CoordCom. It runs on tablets (each rescue vehicle is equipped with one), so it allows rescuers more mobile features.
3. **MATRA** system represent personal units (terminals) for use during the rescue action. It is something between common walkie-talkie and smart phone. Units are using digital network. They are used mainly for voice transfer, which is realized by “semi-duplex” way. Units have also some more helpful functions (data transfer, localization, encrypted communication, establishment of separate small hotspots, etc.)
4. **SITNO** is the digital communication network. Network of towers with related HW and SW. Connections to the network is managed by Ministry of Interior and it subject of strict rules. SITNO is a professional digital network created on the basis of TETRAPOL technology. It operates in the frequency band 380 - 400 MHz which represents the UHF band / ultra-high frequency - ultra short waves nationwide coverage to provide voice and data communications. The system enables voice communication using a semi-duplex system. Communication via the TETRA protocol is encrypted. Parallel and serial encryption are used.
5. **Walkie-talkie(s)** are the last (but not least) tool for communication. They are used mainly on the lowest (basic) level of different responding units. MOTOROLA products are used mostly.

5.2.3.5. Bulgaria

The First Aid Responders (FARs) in Bulgaria are called urgent mobile teams/paramedics. They operate in everyday medical incidents. The FARs work for the Emergency Medical Centre or widely known as “First Aid”, which operates under the supervision of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Bulgaria. The national telephone to which every emergency incident is reported is 112.

In Bulgaria there are:

- 346 hospitals
- 2098 medical centres for pre-hospital health care
- 541 ambulances
- 363 mobile teams
- Mobile units of emergency medical attendance, staffed with two paramedics and a doctor, and highly equipped - as if small hospital ER units - equipped with advanced

airway equipment, pulse oximeters, ventilators, airway suction devices, manual defibrillators with (3-lead)-ECG-monitoring for advanced non-invasive transcutaneous pacing, intravenous access equipment and fluids, drugs and sophisticated immobilization devices

- 0 helicopters

Bulgaria is the only country in the European Union, which do not have medical helicopters. There is a plan for buying 6 medical helicopters no sooner than 2024. This is an extreme problem which could find a proper solution in a short period of time.

In Bulgaria there are:

- 263 registered voluntary formations, established by mayors of municipalities, according to article 41, paragraph 1 of the Disaster Protection Act.
- 4 voluntary formations, established by private entities, according to article 41, paragraph 1 of the Disaster Protection Act.
- 28 Voluntary teams for reaction on crises, disasters and catastrophes.
- 1 National team for reaction on crises, disasters and catastrophes.
- 1 National team flood rescue team established by Bulgarian Red Cross, according the Bulgarian Red Cross Act.
- 32 Mountain rescue teams established by the Mountain rescue service to the Bulgarian Red Cross, according the Bulgarian Red Cross Act.
- 306 emergency medical centres to the Ministry of health.
- 28 regional directorates with 265 district fire services of General Directorate "Fire Safety and Protection of the Population" – to the Ministry of Interior.

5.2.3.6. Greece

National Centres for Emergency Care, "EKAB"'s headquarters are located in the capital of Greece, Athens. There are also 11 regional offices-stations in Thessaloniki, Patras, Heraklion, Larisa, Kavala, Ioannina, Lamia, Alexandroupolis, Tripoli, Kozani, Mytilini.

Figure 22 - Map of EKAB offices/station in Greece (152)

The EMS's force is equipped with:

- 735 standard ambulance vans, staffed only with two paramedics, for basic first aid non-medical life support
- 102 Mobile Intensive Care Units (MICUs). Mobile units of emergency medical attendance, staffed with two paramedics and a doctor, and highly equipped - as if small hospital ER units - equipped with advanced airway equipment, pulse oximeters, ventilators, airway suction devices, manual defibrillators with (3-lead)-ECG-monitoring for advanced non-invasive transcutaneous pacing, intravenous access equipment and fluids, drugs and sophisticated immobilization devices
- 25 motorcycles (staffed with a highly trained paramedic and, on some occasions, a doctor too – following the NHS/LAS London model)
- 4 small vehicles (microcars/subcompact cars)
- 3 helicopters (operated by the Hellenic Air Force pilots and manned with EMS personnel and, in addition and if required, with any specialist ad hoc)
- 2 mobile coordination stations
- 2 disaster vehicles
- 350 additional ambulance vans are stationed in hospitals or health centres

Apart from “EKAB”, volunteering organizations are engaged in civil protection operations as well as in first aid response in case of emergencies. These organizations have both operational and supportive role throughout the whole circle of disaster management. Their operational engagement includes forest fire prevention and forest firefighting actions, urban firefighting actions, search and rescue and first aid actions. Regarding their support actions, the volunteering organizations are responsible to secure and sustain communications between

government agencies, other volunteering organizations and among themselves. They are also involved in psychological support, public awareness, relief and support, as well as shelter monitoring actions.

In order for a person to acquire the status of a civil protection volunteer, (s)he has to be a Greek citizen, a citizen of other Member States of the EU residing in Greece for at least three years, or a citizen of third countries with long residence in Greece, (s)he has to speak and write Greek fluently, (s)he has to be over 18 years old, (s)he must not have legal convictions of any kind, (s)he has to be in a good physical and psychological condition, as certified by the respective doctors and, finally, (s)he has to receive certified training by the School of Volunteers and Volunteering Organizations of the Civil Protection Academy. If that person meets the aforementioned preconditions, he/she is included in the registry of volunteering organizations, which is kept by the General Secretariat of Civil Protection. In any case, a volunteer cannot be a member of more than one volunteering organization. The volunteer receives supplementary training six years after his/her initial acquisition of the volunteering status.

All the above conditions apply according to Law 4662/2020 - OGG 27/A/7-2-2020. The mentioned law is in force but is not applied in its entirety. Its full application is expected in the near future.

5.2.4. Identification of existing debriefing principles, Emergency Debriefing Guidelines, Types of Debriefing Following Disasters, Debriefing Manuals for FARs

According to the VALKYRIES D2.2 – Terminology and Semantics, debrief is a critical examination of a completed operation or exercise in order to evaluate actions.

Taking time to debrief after each training / workshop creates important opportunities to notice what is working well and what can be improved in the future.

5.2.4.1. European level

Via the Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network, the EU is developing a new platform for sharing knowledge, best practices and lessons learned by civil protection experts and emergency management personnel.

Lessons learnt programme

The UCPM Lessons Learnt Programme (153) is a broad lesson-learning programme, including the development of good practices. The purpose is to enhance efficiency and effectiveness of practitioners inside the Mechanism.

The programme identifies and shares lessons and good practices from UCPM deployments and horizontal, cross-cutting activities to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the UCPM as a whole. It focuses on the whole disaster management cycle, covering prevention, preparedness and response.

Lessons from UCPM deployments provide guidance as to what lessons could be implemented in the future to continually improve the UCPM. The main UCPM Lessons Learnt Programme document is the annual report, a tool for UCPM member and participating states and the Commission to enhance the implementation of lessons and good practices.

The annual report also offers an overview of activities conducted by the Commission regarding the implementation – the learning - of lessons identified in previous years.

Exchange of experts' programme

Exchange of Experts (EoE) programme is an essential source to compile experts' feedback for best practices and knowledge.

Experts are required to **complete an evaluation form during the exchange**. The evaluation must be completed by the expert using the Expert Evaluation Form (154) on the website within one week after the completion of the exchange.

In addition, the EoE requires participants in the programme to **prepare a report within 30 days after the exchange is completed**. This report should describe the activities under-taken, the lessons learned, the results achieved and benefits of the exchange. In case of group exchanges the experts coming from the same organization are required to develop a joint Field report. As a practice, joint reports were made in the past even in case of multinational group exchanges therefore the experts are encouraged to do so.

Between 2010 and 2021 there were 242 exchanges, with a 2122 total number of experts from 48 countries involved.

Exchanges 2018 - 2020

Figure 23 - Exchanges of experts programme 2018-2020

Reports from past exchanges can be downloaded at the program's website (155).

Peer Review Programme

Managed by DG ECHO, the Peer Review programme (156) is a tool made available to civil protection authorities of Member States, Participating States, and Enlargement and Neighbourhood countries under the Civil Protection Mechanism.

The main objective is to facilitate the sharing of good practices in disaster risk management (DRM) through an independent analysis, which is carried out by a team of experts (the "peers") selected from different UCPM countries.

Benefits:

- Identifies better approaches to policy and operations;
- Facilitates mutual learning and exchange of good practice;
- Raises awareness among stakeholders involved in DRM in the reviewed country;
- Proposes concrete recommendations.

5.2.4.2. Spain

In the monthly training drills, a general informal debriefing is carried out. However, in the real MCI a follow-up is carried out in real time by the heads of the catastrophic department and a posteriori a meeting is held to see the points to improve.

INSARAG is a global network of more than 90 countries and organizations under the United Nations umbrella. INSARAG deals with urban search and rescue (USAR) related issues, aiming to establish minimum international standards for USAR teams and methodology for international coordination in earthquake response based on the INSARAG Guidelines endorsed by the United Nations General Assembly Resolution 57/150 of 2002, on “Strengthening the Effectiveness and Coordination of International Urban Search and Rescue Assistance.

The post-mission phase is the period immediately after a USAR Team has returned home. In this phase, the USAR Team is required to complete and submit a post-mission report and conduct a lessons-learned review to improve the overall effectiveness and efficiency for a response to future disasters. The post-mission phase continuously merges into the preparedness phase.

Upon the arrival of the personnel, the head of the EIS operational group will prepare a report that collects the health incidents of both ERICAM personnel and the victims of the catastrophe and dogs of the search teams, as well as the data recorded on use, loss or deterioration of material. This report must contain the proposals that the staff of the EIS operational group consider appropriate for the improvement of the team's intervention in subsequent catastrophes.

Annex B30: USAR Team Post-Mission Report Form

USAR Team Post-Mission Report Form	
<p>Post Mission Report is recommended to be completed and submitted to the INSARAG Secretariat within 45 days following every national or foreign USAR deployment. If possible, include a photographic record of the mission with the report submission.</p>	
<p>Below is an outline of the contents this report should address.</p>	
Team Name	
Mission	
Overview	
Preparation	
Mobilisation	
Operations:	
Coordination with LEMA	
Coordination with OSOCC	
Cooperation with other teams	
Base of Operations	
Team Management	
Logistics	
Search	
Rescue	
Medical	
Demobilisation	
Lessons Learned	
Recommendations	
Provider of information	
Contact Details	

United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA)
www.unocha.org

Figure 24 – USAR Team Post-Mission Report Form

5.2.4.3. Portugal

After a drill, Civil Protection and HESE conduct a formal debriefing. Representatives from the various areas involved in the drill participate, as well as external observers from each area, leading to a final report. The teams in the field, e.g., Physicians and Nurses, usually perform informal debriefing after the occurrence.

5.2.4.4. Slovakia

Debriefing after intervention is not mandatory in Slovakia. Its implementation varies from unit to unit. Debriefing is mandatory for example after realization of tactic exercise. There are also available courses on this topic. This issue is often the subject of discussions at various conferences and also after complex interventions, which is usually the case of MCI. Good/bad practice are summarized and shared with related subjects. However, there is no output regarding the proposal for improvement in future practice, even with their real application. So,

there are approaches as well as experience, but systematic process is missing. This is definitely room for improvement.

Emergency health crew activities

The emergency room is activated by the operations centre and leaves the intervention from its headquarters, or from the place where it is located in case of unfinished intervention, if the ambulance is already released and ready for intervention (for example, after handing over the affected person in hospital, when the ambulance returns to its centre). After activation, the ambulance is obliged to go to the intervention within 2 minutes.

The task of the ambulance crew is to accept the instructions of the operating centre, to perform all actions necessary to provide emergency assistance and, if necessary, to ensure the transport of the affected person to the medical facility. In pre-hospital health care conditions, it is the nearest medical facility able to provide adequate health care. The affected person has the right to refuse any of these activities, but must be informed of the possible consequences in an appropriate and proportionate manner. The crew must make a written record of such a fact, which will be signed by the affected person. If a person refuses to sign such a record, two witnesses will sign. Against the will of a person, the crew's action is possible only if the person endangers himself or his surroundings. Such a procedure is possible in cooperation with the Police Force of the Slovak Republic. The financing of the emergency medical service is paid by the person's health insurance. The EMS crew issues medical records of the intervention itself. Its form for the EMS is given by legislation as HAR (which is described in section 6.2.3. In addition to the identifiers of the affected person, it contains a record of the anamnesis and findings of the physical examination, selected auxiliary examinations, actions and performances of the crew, the administered treatment, as well as the place of transfer of the person and the condition at handover.

5.2.4.5. Bulgaria

The debriefing principles in any emergency incident in the EMS are divided into different categories, according to the type and the size of the incident.

All EMS events are followed by the completion of the Incident Card and/or the Report of Patient's Transport. The original Incident Card is handed over to the hospital, whereas a duplicate is delivered to the EMS central office, where it is kept as a proof and report of the incident. All the written data are transferred to electronic databases and at regular intervals statistics are exported.

In cases of massive health incidents, where the Special Department of Disasters' Medicine is involved and triage protocols are involved, the department gives additional report of the incident's progress and its total outcome (number of victims, number of deaths etc.) after collecting all individual reports.

5.2.4.6. Greece

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5.3. Raising practitioner and social awareness

5.3.1. Introduction

The emergency medical teams and first responders' teams providing emergency medical support need to be prepared for all kinds of situations (particularly the cross-border effect to be taken into consideration) that might cause other people to panic. Therefore, the teams take responsibility for making leadership decisions and acquiring sufficient situational awareness amidst the cross-border MCI or mass-casualty events.

Part of the success is the decision making requiring the teams' mandatory education (formal/informal), awareness, engagement and continuous training so that working efficiently is a critical issue. By putting in the training /exercises/almost real full exercises, virtual reality-support exercises the Mass Casualty Incident within the project is understood as an incident requiring emergency medical services and dealing with more people in a single event.

We can also introduce small-scale and large-scale mass casualty incidents to differentiate between resources and procedures in place. In a large-scale event, casualties can exceed the resources available to provide support.

Several resources are on-demand in cross-border MCI:

- Technology for early warning
- Technology for monitoring the situation, crowdsourcing, etc.
- Staff (different types of intervention units providing direct support or first aid rescue services)
- Equipment for rescuing life (means for transportations equipped with life-saving support tools/materials, means for fast and target transportation to respective hospitals, distribution of hospitals as per heavy and mass injuries capacities, etc.-)
- Limited number of emergency medical professionals, meaning only so many people can receive treatment at a time
- Support by other related intervention teams, volunteers
- Leadership communication for urgent and proper distribution of tasks and actions in the tense environment
- Shortage of medical professionals to treat everyone quickly
- Shortage of supplies like bandages, medication, and medical equipment.

Following the above listed limitations and opportunities, the Consortium has further developed the first aid and first respondents' repositories as follows:

- UC1: Cross-frontier fire between Spain-Portugal
- UC2: Cross-border toxic cloud assessing Slovakia-Italy
- UC3: Cross-border earthquake in neighbouring counties of Bulgaria and Greece
- UC4: Rescue of people and collection of Pollution on sea in international waters of Norway-Denmark-Sweden

Main medical and support teams/individuals shall know how to provide quick and accurate aid/rescue services in the event of an MCI, to help the injured and work efficiently with other personnel and contribute without getting in the way of other responders.

5.3.2. Phases of emergency management

Emergency management consists of the coordination and managing of resources and responsibilities leading to prevention, preparedness, response and recovery from an emergency. Prevention and preparedness present the pre-incident phase of an emergency, response present incident phase and recovery presents post-incident phase. Each phase of an emergency management cycle is of an importance, but with the scope of the VALKYRIES project, the main focus will be given to incident phase – response during MCI.

According to D2.2 Terminology and Semantics MCI (Mass Casualty Incident) is defined as an event which generates more patients at one time than locally available resources can manage using routine procedures (this definition is from WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology). Having this in mind, it is important that awareness, e.g., practitioner and social, is crucial. Either practitioners – first responders, who are first on-site need to be firstly prepared, and trained for incidents with more victims and should have an appropriate information and sources where they can gather information from; or people who are injured or families of injured people or victims or people who live in the affected area, need to be able to search for and find information necessary for saving lives, property or environment.

Awareness can be simply defined as having or showing realization, perception or knowledge about situations with respect to conditions and circumstances, relative position or combination of circumstances at a certain moment.

Awareness in relation to MCI is an overall awareness of the existence of cross-border risks of MCI and how to behave and how to respond in the event of MCI in the cross-border area. The awareness refers to all actors (either first responders or other people – public).

5.3.2.1. Pre-incident phase

Prevention

Prevention can be defined as actions that decrease the risk of a hazard or to reduce the potential negative consequences that can lead to injury/death of people or to damage of property. This phase mainly focuses on establishing concrete plans, trainings, exercises to prepare people, organisations or first responders. Emergency planning activities cover specific plans, standardized planning tools and emergency management protocols.

Prevention is done for example via journals, exercises/courses in elementary or secondary schools and also via social media accounts of first responders (firefighters, police, emergency medical services), also, non-governmental organizations can be useful and promote prevention on special awareness aid meetings.

Preparedness

Preparedness means a continuous cycle of various activities such as planning, first responders training, exercising and assessment. Preparedness and readiness need to go hand-in-hand while preparing for disaster. Preparedness is defined through plans, protocols or procedures which are designed and developed to minimize damage when MCI occurs. These activities ensure, that when an incident occurs, first responders (or emergency managers) will be able to provide the best response. The essential steps can be as follows: planning, first responders training, and table top exercises/drills. Based on experts' expertise from EU countries, exercises or training for first responders, debriefing sessions, and entity training/collaboration annual common exercises are s of the pre-incident phase. Only when first responders are in a good condition, this means physical but also mental/theoretical, then the response while MCI can be more effective. A very important part of awareness among first responders is organising training, but also collaborative trainings/exercises of first responders (medicals, firefighters, police) and also after each intervention debriefing sessions (firstly within each organisation separately and regarding MCI there is a need to organize also larger debriefing sessions which will group all first responders).

5.3.2.2. Incident phase

Response

Response means that there are many actions taken to decrease mortality and morbidity and to prevent lives, environment and property damage when the hazard or incident occurs. During the response phase preparedness plans are implemented. Response activities may be as follows: search and rescue, alert and warning, triage, acute medical care, firefighting, and sheltering victims.

5.3.2.3. Post-incident phase

Recovery

This phase can be simply defined as actions taken to return to normal life after an incident or disaster.

Once the response to an MCI has been completed (all lives have been saved or removed from danger) the incident will transition from the response to the recovery phase. During the transition from response to recovery, the emergency services will hand over coordination to the local authorities.

5.3.3. Practitioner awareness

Practitioners, e.g., first responders who are the first on-site when an incident or disaster happens, must be aware of the ongoing situation. They need to have real time information and be aware of the situation which is happening. Regarding MCI all involved first responders must be firstly trained for such kind of incident; secondly, they need to have the information about

how many victims are affected, where are they situated, which property is at risk, how the whole situation can be solved as quick as possible, how many sources (personal/financial) are needed.

In fact, they need to have a COP (Common operational picture), which is according to D2.2 Terminology and Semantics defined as follows: COP is information, tailored in terms of content and detail, geographically represented, that shows the evolution of an event along the progress of the operations merged into a common frame of reference and visualized on a screen, supporting the comprehension by the response organizations of the current view of the situation. The goal of a COP is real-time situational awareness across all levels of incident management.

Situational awareness should meet these requirements:

- Collect the data required to satisfy the decision maker's goal
- Data collected should be the attributes necessary to sufficiently describe a required piece of information
- Data must provide the ability to describe relationships between things
- Data must provide the ability to link the attributes for any give piece of information to time
- Data must be of sufficient quality to meet the decision-making and action needs of the moment: completeness, timeliness, accuracy, consistency.

5.3.4. Social awareness

Social awareness is important during all phases of the emergency management cycle. In pre-incident phase involves prevention and preparedness tasks which are described above. During incident phase plays a crucial role because it is important what kind of information is coming to and also from the public. This we understand as early warning of population, evacuation, informing disabled people, tourists, etc. Post-incident awareness highlights the necessity of managing volunteers and helping with searching for people, managing evacuated people to come back to their homes and also restore the damaged infrastructure and environments.

Social media can play important role within the MCI. Social media can on one hand provide near-real-time information for first responders who can make and take decisions through different stages of emergency management cycle, on the other hand social media can provide information without being aware of their validity or risk of misinformation.

5.3.5. Awareness and selection of innovative solutions

This part is an example from the FIRE-IN project dealing with EU-wide collaborative platform for first responders, researchers and industries to access state-of-the-art solutions answering the needs of practitioners. The solutions are technologies, standards, guides, etc., available on the market.

The public might be involved in an emergency and needs to behave safely, develop self-protection or even contribute to rescue other people affected.

Measures to ensure that include:

- Education of general public on risk awareness and self-protection,

- Training on the knowledge of risks and appropriate solutions to be aware of the implication of their own decisions,
- Division of the population into different subgroups based on vulnerability, accessibility, impact – focus especially on the most exposed and vulnerable groups,
- All phases of emergency management cycle and the different levels of risks,
- Training population as first responders,
- Provision tools to make decision easier for potential victims,
- Management of crowds and control their panic,
- Strengthening the appropriate population response, provide instructions to follow in case of a risk.

Selection of innovative solutions (technologies, guidelines, projects, programmes):

1. KATWARN, The Warning and Information System for the Public – provides warning for the current location and for severing freely selectable location favourites as well as topic-related subscriptions.
2. INA, the intervention app that makes every minute count – the communication between all stakeholders is streamlined in the intervention channel so that everyone has the same view and unnecessary communication is avoided.
3. Ofire+ is an integrated solution for the management of the static/dynamic risk due to wildland fires, targeted to facilitate the local needs of critical infrastructure which are prone to such danger.
4. G-SAPI – staff monitoring and alert system – the system makes it possible to immediately signal in real time any vehicle entering the safety zone.
5. FR-ALERT is a population alert system which provides information on the nature and location of a danger or a threat and indicated the actions and behaviours to adopt in order to protect oneself from these dangers.
6. Guide for Emergency Preparedness and Correct Action in Emergency Situations
7. RescEU – EC created RescEU to reinforce and strengthen components of the EU's disaster risk management.
8. BroadMap, BroadWay, BroadGNSS – 3 projects focusing on interoperability across borders and the next generation of broadband radio communication systems for public safety and security.
9. LINKS – Strengthening links between technologies and society for European disaster resilience.

Other solutions regarding awareness (apart from above mentioned project):

10. APELL (Awareness and preparedness for emergencies at the local level) improves community-level emergency preparedness efforts and supports governments and communities, in particular in developing countries, to minimize the occurrence and harmful effects of technological hazards and environmental emergencies. APELL methodology is aimed at creating a cohesive and resilient community to technological or natural hazards through raising awareness and agreement on the roles and

responsibilities of all community stakeholders to develop measures for preparedness and emergency response.

5.4. Civil-Military Cooperation

5.4.1. Introduction

The aim of the present study is to reveal and summarize the essence of Civil-Military Cooperation (CIMIC) in emergency situations to identify some problems and possible ways to overcome them.

Since the early 1990s, the international community has intervened in internal conflicts to an increasing degree. The new reality in interventional global policy has resulted in increased contact between international armed forces and humanitarian actors. Among other places, the missions in Bosnia, Kosovo and East Timor showed the need for these actors to work more closely together than had happened in the past. This has been described as Civil-Military Cooperation (CIMIC) and it has consequently become a key policy and operational issue for all involved actors. While recognising the need to find ways of cooperation and coordination, the different actors hold various views on how to respond to the altered conditions.

NATO's CIMIC approach is primarily based on the Military Council doctrine 411/1 (MC 411/1) and the Allied Joint Publication 9 (AJP-9). The MC 411/1 came into force in 2001 and its intention is the launch a NATO military policy on CIMIC. The AJP-9 provides the actual guiding principles and procedures for the implementation and execution of CIMIC. In 2002, the AJP-9 was approved by the NATO member states.

Europe is now a relatively safe place to live, but recent years have shown that Europe is also affected by a wide range of adverse events that cause devastation of human life, property, environment and cultural heritage. For this reason, in the EU, protecting people, property, environment and cultural heritage against multiple threats is primarily a national responsibility. However, as disasters do not respect borders, the EU can take action to complement, support and coordinate national action and to promote cross-border cooperation (Overview of natural and man-made disaster risks the European Union may face,, 2020).

We live in times of constantly emerging natural disasters, cataclysms, accidents and catastrophes caused by human activity, as well as in conditions of constantly emerging, of varying origin and intensity crises and conflicts of environmental, health, social, ethnic, religious, economic and military character. It can be argued that both natural disasters and those resulting from human activity already have a clear cascading character, do not recognize state borders, arise with increasing pulsation and are increasingly difficult to predict, manage or control. This means that such phenomena will increase in intensity, frequency and scope, and institutions, organizations and countries should build anti-crisis capabilities related to their timely detection and adequate response.

This requires more and more decisive intervention of the state institutions and more than good cooperation at all levels of the state and local administration. In this sense, there is no emergency that does not require the joint and coordinated efforts of governmental and non-governmental, civil and military, professional and voluntary, national and international structures and organizations. The military's mobility and extended geographical reach are

invaluable assets in these circumstances. And according to the recent prospect of interstate war is considered a remote possibility, governments assumed there are no problems in summoning these “idle” soldiers.

And if until recently it was thought that military structures and formations were only responsible for military security, then efforts to deal with modern emergencies bring to the fore assistance that can add to the unique capabilities of the armed forces, especially when it comes to terrible cataclysms, such as earthquakes, floods, forest fires, pandemics, nuclear accidents and pollution, etc.

In these cases, the armed forces can provide unique assistance to civilian institutions, such as the provision of military medical facilities and infrastructure, the deployment of field hospitals, the use of military transport to evacuate the wounded and sick; the use of military medical equipment and equipment in the affected area, air monitoring and assessing the extent of damage; ensuring public order and security of infrastructure and property in the disaster area, and others (158).

Nowadays, many research institutes and research organizations study the problems of Civil-Military Cooperation in natural disasters and cataclysms and look for those mechanisms and approaches related to crisis management that would support effective civilian-military activities between teams of armed forces and civilian structures, building appropriate interface and the necessary joint capabilities for adequate response and overcoming the consequences of such situations.

As a result of the present study we expect to reveal how civil-military activities and civil-military interaction can be combined within the EU Civil Protection Mechanism and in emergency situations with mass casualties to more effectively use the capabilities of military formations to support civilian institutions in the affected area.

5.4.2. CIMIC in a global perspective

Today, the focus of CIMIC activities is shifting from purely military operations and commitments to non-military emergencies - natural disasters such as floods, earthquakes, fires and tsunamis, and a number of such caused by human activity - technological accidents, catastrophes, radiation and chemical pollution, environmental changes and extreme phenomena, various pandemics and epizootics and others.

Their complex nature and interdependence constantly require increasing involvement not only of search and rescue structures, civil protection teams, emergency and fire services, medical emergency services, but also non-governmental organizations such as the Red Cross and Red Crescent, various international organizations and those to the UN and the EU, but also the efforts, resources, infrastructure, teams, forces and means of the armed forces.

At the international level, the United Nations Office for Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) developed Guidance principles for the use of foreign military and civilian defence assets in disaster relief (Oslo guidelines) in 1994 (updated in 2006 and 2007). They are aimed at creating a basic framework for formalizing and improving the efficiency and effectiveness of the use of foreign military and civilian defence assets in international operations disaster relief (natural, technological and environmental emergencies) during peacetime.

These guidelines principles are primarily intended for use by United Nations humanitarian agencies and their partners in implementation and operations. However, they can also be used by government decision makers and regional organizations when considering the use of military and civilian defensive assets to assist the civilian population in the event of natural disasters and technological or environmental emergencies in peacetime.

Subsequently, these guidelines principles have been supplemented by the OCHA Guidelines United Nations on the use of military and civilian defensive assets to support humanitarian activities United Nations in complex emergencies, including the use of military and civilian defence assets in situations of armed conflict.

In 2004, the United Nations Inter-Agency Standing Committee (IASC) also adopted the Civil-Military Guidelines and Standards for Complex Emergencies (IASC Guidelines), which promote common understanding and a coherent approach to civil-military relations in a changing institutional and operational environment. Even if the scope of these instruments differs, the rationale for civil-military cooperation remains the same.

While recognizing the complementarity of civilian and military assets, all guidelines promote and protect the principles of humanity, neutrality and impartiality inherent in humanitarian assistance. In this context, civil-military cooperation ensures effective dialogue, complementarity and effective use of the agencies of all interested parties.

It is also necessary to enact legislation providing for and facilitating international cooperation in the field of emergency response and humanitarian assistance, as well as procedures for obtaining, using and monitoring foreign military assets.

Furthermore, operations should not rely entirely on military assets, but should support the civilian nature of the response. Military assets must remain impartial and their intervention clearly limited in scope. Also, the creation of training programs and communication schemes can help to strengthen understanding between civilians and the military.

At European level, both NATO and the EU improve the allied cooperation regulated by international agreements, permanent councils and documents regulating the role, tasks and procedures for the participation of military structures in support of civilian participants, both in the response in the area of defeat and in dealing with the consequences.

For example, the NATO CIMIC Training Centre is constantly improving regulations - a new NATO policy on Civil-Military Cooperation has been developed, which has been upgraded with a new and broader concept - Civil-Military Interaction (CMI) (159). For the first time, the term is defined here, stating that "...represents a group of activities based on communication, planning and coordination, shared by all NATO military bodies and conducted with international and local non-military actors, during and in preparation for NATO operations, to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of their response to crises. "

The most important allied documents in this field are constantly supplemented and enriched - the CIMIC Doctrine, as well as the CIMIC Handbook, which expands the functions, tasks and scope of civil-military interaction and details the civil-military activities to be carried out in the framework of various humanitarian operations in emergency situations (160).

The Allied Joint Doctrine for the Military Contribution to Humanitarian Assistance has also been specially developed, which provides basic guidelines and rules for planning and conducting operations in support of civilian structures in humanitarian aid to the population (Allied Joint Doctrine for the Military Contribution to Humanitarian Assistance (AJP-3.4.3), Edition A, Version 1, Brussels, 2015.).

Within the European Union, the growing role of civil-military cooperation was also recognized and the idea of sharing civilian and military capabilities, tools and resources was adopted in the course of humanitarian efforts.

Of particular value are summaries of previous EU humanitarian and disaster response operations in various hotspots, and recommendations for better coordination of military assistance during the various stages of operations. Here we can also mention the experience of Great Britain, which, along with NATO documents, has developed a national document that regulates the planning and implementation of military assistance in the framework of a humanitarian operation to assist in disasters or emergencies abroad (162).

The crucial role of military structures in increasing the effectiveness of Civil-Military Coordination during EU-led humanitarian aid and emergency response operations is emphasized (Joint Doctrine Publication (JDP) 3-52, Disaster Relief Operations Overseas: the Military Contribution, Ministry of Defence of the UK, Development, Concepts and Doctrine Centre, 2016).

5.4.3. CIMIC in case of disasters

Peace support, humanitarian action, disaster response and complex emergencies require cooperation between sectors from different backgrounds and cultures. Both civil and the military sectors have relevant experience that can be useful to respond to emergencies. On the one hand, the military can contribute to emergency relief through their ability quickly mobilize and send unique assets and experience to distant areas.

On the other hand, civil organizations usually have longstanding community relations and are often better equipped to identify the needs of the beneficiaries. Finally, while working with military assets civilians must ensure their neutrality, impartiality, operational independence, and that the civilian character of the humanitarian assistance has not been compromised.

The main functional areas of action of CIMIC are grouped in five leading areas: public activities, civil infrastructure, humanitarian issues, economy and trade, and cultural issues, which include:

- **Public activities:** with issues such as internal order, relations with external organizations, economic projects, provision of assistance, transport and evacuation, assistance to medical teams and treatment of victims, access to hard-to-reach settlements and others;
- **Civil infrastructure:** provision of communications, support by air, land and water transport, provision of resources, forces and means for reconstruction, repair and public assistance, etc.
- **Humanitarian issues:** assistance to displaced persons and refugees, provision of food, water and property for the homeless, the sick, mothers with children, the elderly and other vulnerable groups in the affected areas, etc.;

- **Economy and trade:** support of economic development, recovery of industries, food chain, goods, products, trade, warehouses and others;
- **Cultural issues:** protection and restoration of the monuments and museums, evacuation of archives, care for religious sites and institutions, protection of cultural heritage, etc.

By their nature, these activities are complex, interconnected and cover all areas of socio-political life and the economy. In practice, they are implemented mainly in two directions - providing better opportunities for normal daily life of the population and building conditions for the establishment and strengthening of local civilian authorities, as well as supporting their efforts to establish and maintain normal life.

Moreover, these functional areas move forward underpinned by principles and fundamentals necessary for proper approach and cooperation. These principles, endorsed by NATO, should be followed by the military in any situation with civilians and are as follows:

- Understand the civil environment
- Understand the aims and objectives of all non-military actors
- Respect civilian primacy
- Act with integrity
- Integrate planning with non-military actors
- Establish effective relationships and communication with non-military actors

Participating military units must fully understand the mandate, aims and objectives, role, structure, methods and principles of non-military actors. It is also important to establish and maintain strong relationships prior to and during the moments of collaboration in order to ensure mutual understanding. Furthermore, by engaging non-military actors, commanders can encourage collaborative analysis, integrated planning and interaction, thereby supporting unity of purpose and effort.

5.4.4. CIMIC at a national level

At the national level, we will examine doctrines, legislation and procedures, related to CIMIC activities in several European countries.

We will focus mainly on the countries participating in the project, as well as their neighbours. We will look at the peculiarities of both large and small countries, countries in different parts of the continent, and countries with different administrative structure and territorial division. Thus, we believe that we will achieve greater representation and capture the differences between them.

To this end, we will look at how state structures and local authorities work in emergency situations, we will look for the powers of the governing bodies and the existing mechanisms, rules and procedures for involving military structures in this process. We will try to find the differences in the legislation, in the principles of using the forces of the army together with the other civilian participants and we will look for the gaps and those solutions that can improve the interaction between them.

5.4.4.1. CIMIC in Austria

As a federal republic, Austria is comprised of 9 independent federal states (also referred to as provinces) and 2,100 municipalities. Disaster management is a task which is shared between all levels of government.

Disaster prevention is controlled at the national level by the responsible federal ministries in cooperation with the federal states and municipalities. The main responsibility for disaster response lies with the federal states. The legal basis for response is provided by the disaster relief acts of the federal states, which determine the declaration of the state of disaster and the operational direction of response at municipal, district, and federal state level. Operational capacities are mainly provided by voluntary response organisations (fire brigades, Red Cross, mountain rescue and others), which act as governmental services in the event of a disaster. On the national level, the responsibility for disaster management coordination lies with the Ministry of the Interior. Coordination is ensured by a national coordinating committee which is chaired and managed by the Ministry of the Interior.

Austria has developed a wide range of capabilities for the prevention of natural and man-made hazards and risks. Capabilities are built on a strategic framework for national security and comprehensive legislation mainly in the areas of water management, forestry, land use planning, and construction. Austria has established a strong federal system of structural and non-structural protection against natural hazards, in particular against floods, avalanches, and landslides. Prevention against natural hazards is financed by a national fund. A standard risk management plan exists for all areas with significant flood risk.

Plans have to be based on assessments of relevant hazards in the respective territory. For nationwide risks, such as health risks or nuclear risks, there are national risk management policies governed by federal laws and regulations. In the area of natural hazards, prevention measures are planned and carried out on the basis of long-term strategies and priorities under the control of the responsible federal ministries. The provinces, municipalities, and other organisations are involved as regional and local partners in the planning and implementation process.

The responsibility for the preparedness for most types of disasters, in particular for natural disasters, lies with the federal states, the districts and municipalities. Austria has a dense network of disaster response facilities mainly at the municipal level. Most of the workforce in disaster response in Austria is voluntary. Response plans exist in all municipalities, districts and federal states. For national scenarios, there are national response and contingency plans. Exercises take place regularly at all governmental levels.

Emergency response refers to all measures taken by authorities, response organisations, enterprises, individuals and affected parties to mitigate the consequences of an emergency or disaster. The goal is to ensure public order and security, to rescue victims, to provide basic services, to protect the environment and to start early recovery measures. Disaster response encompasses all measures from the official declaration of a disaster until its end. In most cases, disaster response starts at the local or regional level.

Operational lines are usually established at the levels of the municipality, district and federal state. At the national level, coordination takes place within the framework of a coordination committee at the Ministry of the Interior.

The analysis of the disaster protection system in Austria shows that the system is highly decentralised, as the general management and methodological guidelines are implemented at the national level, but the preparation and operational management is mainly at the federal, district and municipality level. The use of structures by the armed forces is undertaken by state authorities at the national level, in close cooperation with civilian structures and organizations.

5.4.4.2. CIMIC in Bulgaria

Crises Management Process and Disaster Protection of the population in emergency situations in Bulgaria is based on the wide understanding that successful protection in case of disasters is realized through conducting preventive options, activities for protection, coordination and interaction in the conditions of an effectively functioning rescue system, action for assistance, recovery, resource provision, provision of aid. The real activities for the protection of the population in case of danger or disaster are: warning; implementation of urgent measures for reduction of the impact; disclosure; rescue operations; rendering medical aid in case of emergencies; support of humanitarian activities at national and international level - safe places for temporary accommodation of victims, activities and services in the interest of the needs of the victims, etc.

The National Disaster Management System is regulated in the Disaster Protection Act, and disaster protection is carried out at the national, regional, and municipal levels.

At the national level the Council of Ministers determines the policy for disaster protection. The Council of Ministers is assisted by the Disaster Risk Reduction Council, which acts as the national disaster risk reduction platform.

The Council includes relevant ministries, the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, universities, the municipalities association, the Bulgarian Red Cross, and other organisations working on disaster risk reduction.

At the Regional level the Regional Governors organise and manage the disaster management in the region, assisted by Regional Disaster Risk Reduction Councils.

The mayors organise and manage disaster protection within the municipalities, assisted by Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction Council.

The Disaster Risk Reduction Council develops the National disaster protection plan for the Council of Ministers. The bodies of the central executive power and the constituent parts of the unified rescue system develop disaster protection plans to implement the tasks arising from the national plan for the protection of disasters and plans at the regional and municipal levels.

According to the National Disaster Protection Plan, the Armed Forces keep rescue and emergency response teams ready to assist the population. Thus, the armed forces are assigned a secondary, supporting role in disasters or emergencies. In this manner, they cannot participate in the process of planning, preparing and coordinating preventive options, emergency response measures or in support of the first teams and first aid responders entering the affected area. By

filling this gap in the preliminary work in the field of CIMIC, the inter-institutional understanding and support is improving. At the same time, other functions of direct management and coordination of all urgent measures should not be taken away. Through planning and constant meetings (approach) with the representatives of organizations and agencies, it is possible to carry out good cooperation for the needs of joint actions that are outside the field of crisis management.

However, the analysis of the national documents shows that the concept of "Civil-Military Cooperation" is not found in them. Neither in the Updated National Security Strategy of the Republic of Bulgaria, in the Law on Defence and the Armed Forces, or in the Disaster Protection Act. Unfortunately, the CIMIC is not mentioned in the Law on Management and Functioning of the National Security Protection System (163), and also, in the Counter-Terrorism Act or in the Disaster Risk Reduction Strategy 2014-2020.

The same gap we can find in the new National Strategy for Disaster Risk Reduction 2018 – 2030, even in the document that provides practical guidelines for the development of disaster protection plans - "Guidelines for the development and readiness for implementation of disaster protection plans", issued by the Disaster Risk Reduction Council at the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Bulgaria. For this reason, it can be argued that the issues of interaction between civilian organizations and the military are not addressed in national law.

The training of Fire Safety and Civil Protection Directorate-General (DGFSCP) staff is carried out in 2 training centres. The training includes initial training for firefighters, specialised rescue training, and training for team leaders and heads of shifts.

From this point the next problem is the fact, that in Bulgaria there are no plans or programs for joint preparation of the formations of the armed forces with those of the civilian structures and organizations. In practice, joint training programs, joint training and education, exercises and others, which are the basis for building joint capabilities for coordination and interaction are neglected. It is even left to the discretion of each minister or head of department to prepare the structures as he sees fit, without a single idea, common scenarios or similar tasks to be implemented.

Another problem is a lack of regulation of the structure, composition, role, tasks, principles and mechanisms of interaction, rules and procedures for activating joint teams, basic requirements and possible joint tasks, scenarios and forms of joint training, command and control, comprehensive support and others.

To summarise, we can conclude, these are national strategic documents regulating public relations in the fields of security, defence, crisis management or disaster response. And they do not envisage, plan or regulate in any way the participation of the armed forces and their formations in supporting the efforts of civilian institutions to resolve crises and assist in emergencies.

The only documents related to the Civil-Military Cooperation activities are the departmental publications of the Ministry of Defence: "The Handbook for CIMIC Specialists" and "CIMIC Tactics, Techniques and Procedures (TTP)" from 2007, developed later "Doctrine of Civil-Military Cooperation" (NP - 3.4.9) of 2014, as well as Chapter 11 of the "Doctrine of the Armed Forces of

the Republic of Bulgaria", edition (A), November 2017. However, these publications indicate the nature, principles, functions and tasks of civil-military cooperation, regulate the procedure for conducting activities and responsibilities of personnel, without giving guidelines for joint preparation, the procedure for combining activities with those of other participants. in the disaster area. And perhaps most importantly, these documents are unknown to NGOs, the Bulgarian Red Cross, rescuers from civil protection, emergency medical teams and others.

In conclusion, the issues of civil-military cooperation are not in focus, and the only institution that has anything to do with the problem is the Ministry of Defence and in particular - the Bulgarian Army.

5.4.4.3. CIMIC in Denmark

The National Crisis Management System serves to provide government coordination of the response to incidents in Denmark or abroad. It consists of:

- The Government Security Committee, which includes the prime minister (chair) and the ministers of Foreign Affairs, Justice, and Defence.
- The Senior Officials Security Committee, which includes permanent secretaries of the 4 above-mentioned ministries and the heads of the Defence Intelligence Service (DDIS) and Security Intelligence Service (PET).
- The National Operational Staff (NOST) which includes the Danish National Police (chair), Danish Emergency Management Agency (DEMA), Danish Health Authority, Defence Command, PET, DDIS, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, and Danish Transport, Construction and Housing Authority. Other authorities may participate ad hoc.
- The International Operational Staff (IOS) which includes the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (chair), Prime Minister's Office, Ministry of Justice, Ministry of Defence, Ministry of Health, National Police, DEMMA, Danish Health Authority and Defence Command. Other authorities, travel and insurance industry representatives may participate ad hoc.
- 12 local operational staff with standing members from the police districts (chair), DEMMA, the Home Guard, the regions and the municipalities. Ad hoc participants often include providers of public transport and utilities.
- Local incident command, made up of on-scene police, fire & rescue, and health preparedness incident commanders.

Within their own areas, individual ministers must plan the retention and continuation of functions in society in the event of large accidents and disasters, including drawing up emergency plans. Each municipal and regional council must also prepare a plan for the municipalities and regions emergency management. The 24 municipal fire and rescue companies (owned by the 98 municipalities) must each maintain a plan based on local risks and conditions.

The Minister of Defence, delegated to the Danish Emergency Management Agency (DEMA), coordinates the planning, advises the authorities, and lays down guidelines for the preparation of the plans by central government authorities, regions, municipalities and municipal fire and rescue companies. The plans must be revised at least once every 4 years and submitted to DEMMA for review and commenting.

The Danish national risk assessment is carried out by the Danish Emergency Management Agency in close consultation with other authorities and organisations.

In addition to the Danish Emergency Management Act, risk management planning responsibilities are addressed in several plans, agreements, and guidelines. These include, the National Emergency Plan, the Comprehensive Preparedness Planning guidelines, and the National Strategy for Prevention of accidents and disasters.

Denmark operates with sectorial responsibilities that extend to risk communication and awareness. This means that the sector responsible for an area with public risk involved also has the responsibility to communicate about that risk.

The Danish Emergency Management Agency (DEMA) and other organisations offer a wide range of training courses. Currently, DEMA's course catalogue includes 32 courses for own personnel and other sectors, ranging from courses regarding the function as on-scene incident commander to courses in crisis communication.

Ample training opportunities also exist via numerous exercises (procedure, dilemma, crisis management and full-scale).

Early Warning Systems in Denmark are currently exclusively weather related. The Danish Emergency Management Agency maintains a warning system for nuclear and radiological emergencies. The system consists of 11 automatic online measurement stations located throughout the country. In case of increased radiation from any of the 11 sites, DEMA receives automatic alarms and can react.

In Denmark, the fundamental principle of emergency management and response is sector responsibility. This means that the authority or organisation with the daily responsibility for a certain area also has the responsibility for that area in case of an emergency. The municipal fire and rescue services are responsible for initiating immediate emergency response, while DEMA assists at larger or more complex incidents that require specialised equipment or personnel.

Despite the fact that the Minister of Defence is the leading figure in the planning and preparation of the structures involved in the emergency response, the armed forces generally do not have a leading role. They can only be used as a last resort in cases of many casualties and destruction.

From the analysis of the system and the available documents it is not clear whether there are national documents regulating civil-military cooperation, the existence of doctrines, concepts and manuals in this area. However, as a whole, the system is well balanced, highly centralized in planning and decentralized in case of a reaction.

5.4.4.4. CIMIC in Finland

In Finland, Rescue Services operate under the Rescue Act (379/2011) and other similar acts. The Department for Rescue Services at the Ministry of the Interior is in charge of the organisation of rescue services at national level, guides and directs rescue services, and coordinates the activities of various ministries and sectors in the field of rescue services and their development.

There are 22 independent regional rescue departments in Finland that provide urgent help in the event of an accident or natural hazard. When resources are insufficient, rescue departments

can ask mutual administrative support from other authorities that can provide skilled staff or equipment as required. This administrative support is regulated by law.

The main risks identified by the NRA in 2018 include information operations, terrorist attacks and disruptions caused by climate change. Risks affecting the stability of society include a serious disruption of the public economy, use of military force or large-scale immigration.

Preparedness is based on the preparedness obligation laid down in the Emergency Powers Act (1552/2011), the Rescue Act and other legislation. According to the Rescue Act, emergency preparedness planning and cooperation is the duty of the rescue services authorities. The Ministry of the Interior coordinates the preparedness of rescue services in Finland, and regional rescue departments are required to support the preparedness planning of municipalities in their area. In addition, every citizen should be prepared for all types of emergencies and disruptions as well as they can.

Civil defence shelters, an essential part of preparedness in Finland, provide protection for the population particularly against a military threat in the most densely populated areas. These shelters protect against the effects of explosions and splinters, collapse of buildings, blasts, radiation and substances hazardous to health. At present, Finland has about 45,000 civil defence shelters accommodating about 3.6 million people.

The Emergency Services Academy Finland arranges basic and advanced fire and rescue training, civil protection and preparedness training, and other training in emergency operations. It is also responsible for the execution of national exercises.

Regional rescue departments are responsible for ensuring that volunteer fire brigades or other contracting organisations have adequate training for their jobs. This training is conducted mainly by the Finnish National Rescue Association (SPEK) and regional rescue service organisations. SPEK also provides further training relating to rescue services for individuals, organizations and the authorities, as well as safety training for public bodies, central government agencies and businesses.

The Emergency Response Centre Agency provides emergency response centre services throughout Finland, except for the Åland Islands. There are 6 emergency response centres in Finland. The Emergency Response Centre Administration is an agency under the Ministry of the Interior. The Ministry is jointly responsible for the performance management of the agency together with the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health.

The data provided for Finland's emergency response system show that this is a well-established and, above all, very well-prepared system. It is noteworthy that the armed forces play an important role in preparing the country for all kinds of disasters and emergencies, including in the presence of external threats to the country's security.

The participation of both the armed forces in the emergency response and voluntary formations, civil organizations and other structures is on a good legal basis and the relevant procedural regulations.

5.4.4.5. CIMIC in Germany

Civil protection in the general sense of “protection of the population” (“Bevölkerungsschutz”) is an overarching term and comprises 2 different elements: “Katastrophenschutz” and “Zivilschutz”.

According to the Constitution, the federal states (“Länder”) are responsible for disaster management (“Katastrophenschutz”) in times of peace. They have enacted respective disaster management laws, defining - inter alia - the responsible disaster management authorities and delegating several administrative and operational tasks to the regional and local level.

In the case of defence, e.g., in times of war or armed conflict, the Federation is in charge of civil protection (“Zivilschutz”), as laid out in the Federal Civil Protection and Disaster Relief Act (ZSKG).

For some of its tasks in civil protection, the Federation draws on Länder resources and complements these if needed (integrated emergency response system). The Federation provides additional equipment, supplies and training to the Länder and may support them in case of disaster upon request (disaster assistance).

The Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community (BMI) is the superior federal government authority for civil protection. It coordinates inter-ministerial collaboration and is generally responsible for national/internal security. The BMI supervises the 2 national civil protection agencies:

- The Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance (BBK): it carries out specific tasks of the Federation concerning civil protection, such as risk management, warning of the population, information and resource management, chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear defence (CBRN) and health protection, protection of critical infrastructure and cultural property, research, international cooperation, etc. The BBK’s experts develop strategies, conduct crisis management exercises and raise awareness among the public to enhance self-protection.
- The Federal Agency for Technical Relief (THW) is a governmental non-profit organisation. As a technical and operational agency, its tasks include technical relief and assistance in a large number of emergencies, within Germany and abroad.

The operational basis at the local level relies on the volunteer potential of e.g., the fire services, local disaster management authorities and participating relief organisations and the THW. More than 1.8 million volunteers constitute the backbone of the system, which is reinforced by professional full-time staff.

Civil-military co-operation, due to the shared responsibilities in times of peace or conflict as described earlier, is particularly relevant in Germany and is carried out at all administrative levels and includes planning, training and exercises. At a national level, the BBK and the Joint Support Command of the Federal Armed Forces (Bundeswehr) coordinate civil-military activities.

Identifying risks and contributing to disaster prevention by reducing risks requires a cross-sectorial approach. Both on a national and sub-national level, preventive elements are embedded in legal and conceptual frameworks of different sectors such as environment, health,

agriculture, water management, critical infrastructure, urban planning, education, development cooperation and consumer protection, etc.

Risk management planning is a key element of disaster management. There is a close connection between risk analysis and capacity-based planning and, consequently, between risk management and crisis management.

Based on the Federal Civil Protection and Disaster Relief Act (ZSKG), the Federation supports the education of the population in self-protection by providing advice and guidance, and supports other actors in the field of civil protection. These include fire services, the Federal Agency for Technical Relief (THW), local disaster management authorities, and participating relief organisations in their duty to provide information to the population.

The Federal Academy of Civil Protection and Civil Defence (BABZ), as part of the Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance, is the central educational institution of the Federation for civil protection and crisis management. It serves as a forum for scientific exchange, both nationally and internationally.

According to the disaster management laws of the Länder, some administrative and operational tasks are delegated to the regional and local levels. Primarily, the districts are responsible for disaster management (within the multi-level system of disaster management authorities). They have to ensure that a command structure for disaster control is set up, which is adequately staffed and trained. Furthermore, they are in charge of developing disaster management plans.

In case of an incident, the fire brigades and relief organisations form the operational and tactical units for immediate technical and medical assistance at the local level.

When asked for assistance, the Federation may support the local and regional authorities and the Länder with their own operational forces (e.g., the Federal Agency for Technical Relief, the Federal Police, and, with certain limitations regarding the use of weapons, the Armed Forces) and with services provided by The Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance.

From the review of the disaster protection system in Germany, it can be concluded that the system is decentralized and very well balanced in terms of responsibilities, duties and powers of central and federal authorities. Army structures intervene only in exceptional cases, at the request of the affected province with a decision at the federal level.

5.4.4.6. CIMIC in Greece

Civil protection in Greece is organised as a coordinated resource system where national, regional and local authorities work together with local and public institutions and services. The Greek bodies responsible for the implementation of civil protection measures include the General Secretariat for Civil Protection (GSCP) and several authorities, organisations and institutions, e.g., the ministries, the fire service, the Hellenic police, the armed forces, health authorities, the decentralised administrations, the regions, and the municipalities (164).

Each ministry is responsible for prevention plans and taking preventive structural measures in the area of their competency. The General Secretariat for Civil Protection issues circulars with guidelines not only on prevention, but also in preparedness and disaster response.

The key risks identified in the national risk assessment include forest fires, earthquakes, floods, and industrial accidents.

The National Civil Protection Plan "Xenokrates" (Ministerial Decision no. 1299/2003) sets the national framework for an effective risk management planning and provides for the development of hazard-specific plans at the local, regional and national level.

Training and exercises are undertaken at national, regional, and local level by competent authorities. Greece also participates in the Union Civil Protection Mechanism training programme. Greek authorities have also organised international exercises, such as, EU EVITA 2014, EU PROMETHEUS 2014, EU POSEIDON 2011, and EU EVROS, 2010.

From the available data, it can be concluded that the armed forces play a relatively high share in resolving crises, disasters and other emergencies. This is due to the special geographical position of the country, the significant coastline and the need to attract naval forces and coast guards to search for and rescue people in need.

There is insufficient information on whether the issues of the participation of the armed forces in emergency situations are regulated in a special manual, doctrine or the relevant tactics, techniques and procedures for their activation.

5.4.4.7. CIMIC in Hungary

The National Directorate General for Disaster Management of the Ministry of Interior is a national law enforcement agency. Its main task is the official prevention of disasters; execution of rescue in civil emergencies; the organisation and management of disaster management; eliminating the consequences; implementation of restoration reconstruction. The Directorate General is responsible for fire protection and civil protection and can draw from a large asset pool to serve this purpose.

The Directorate General is responsible for civil emergency planning and defence management. It regulates and manages the fire service system, technical rescue, protection, and public information. The Directorate General collaborates with law enforcement agencies, the defence forces, and local governments. Finally, it liaises with civil and charitable organisations, educational and scientific institutions, and the media.

Emergency management planning for natural and man-made disasters analyses and interprets the risks. The planning allows for the appropriate assignment of personnel and resources. Resulting from the risk assessment procedure for a given settlement, each settlement is classified into disaster management departments.

NDGDM Defence Management Department within Civil Emergency Planning develops a professional framework for classifying settlements based on real risks into disaster management. It provides the professional support necessary to carry out risk identification and assessment through the regional bodies. It provides professional support for the preparation of emergency plans at all stages of planning to ensure adequate protection of settlements. The department monitors the preparation of municipal and territorial emergency plans, and ensures the adequate level of protection specified in the legislation.

The Inspectorate General for Fire and Civil Protection is responsible for the planning and organisation of the training of the county fire and civil defence chief inspectors and the affected personnel. They prepare guidelines for the annual preparation plan of the personnel involved in firefighting and technical rescue.

The National Directorate General for Disaster Management coordinates the activities of other authorities to prevent emergencies. The National Directorate participates in civil emergency management, planning, defence management, mobilisation of national economy, and state reserve management.

It provides information related to events by operating a duty and operation control system, and activates the forces and assets needed for liquidation. The National Directorate carries out firefighting, technical rescue, protection, information, and alerting local authorities.

The Hungarian Defence Forces (HDF) Civil-Military Cooperation and Psychological Operation Centre (HDF CMCPOC) established on 01st of July 2003 in Budapest, Hungary. The Centre is the sole provider of CIMIC and PSYOPS professional staff for the HDF, and solely responsible unit for the CIMIC and PSYOPS related training and education of the HDF assigned troops for mission deployment. The Centre provides INFO OPS related professional support taking part actively in the non-kinetic elements planning and execution attached tasks.

The Centre is considered as an active contributor for the HDF operations and missions on homeland and out of area missions as well, playing active roles and providing troops for NATO and EU readiness services. Civil-military cooperation is not found in the programs, courses schedule documents related to the legislation and the documents regulating the responsibilities of the military structures in protecting the population in case of disasters.

All this allows us to summarize that the system is highly centralized, mainly around the Ministry of Interior, and military teams are part of the overall efforts to prevent and overcome the consequences of disasters.

5.4.4.8. CIMIC in Portugal

In Portugal the Armed forces is an element and an actor of the National Emergency and Civil Protection Plan, approved by the government and updated regularly, with participation at the National Coordination and Operational Centre. The participation of the Armed Forces is requested by the ANEPC to the Estado Maior of the Armed Forces (EMFA), with to:

1. Emergency phase

- Logistically support the operational forces, namely in infrastructure, food and assembly of campaign kitchens, water, fuel and material miscellaneous (quartering material, tents for campaign, generators, water tanks, etc.);
- Collaborate in prevention actions, assistance in fighting and aftermath of fires;
- Support the evacuation of endangered populations;
- Organize and set up shelters and camps displaced;
- Promptly clear the roadways communication and relief routes;
- Water supply to populations needy;
- Carry out search and rescue operations, immediate relief and primary evacuation;

- Provide emergency health care, contributing, whenever possible, to the national effort in the hospital area, particularly in terms of the ability to hospitalization in hospitals and other units
- Carry out emergency health support, including secondary casualty evacuation, in close cooperation with the authorities of health;
- Carry out the removal of corpses;
- Reinforce and/or reactivate the networks of telecommunications;
- Provide infrastructure for the operation of air means, national or foreign, ensuring logistical support and resupply of aircraft, when feasible and previously coordinated;
- Provide naval, land and air resources for initial reconnaissance actions and assessment and for transporting personnel operational.

2. Rehabilitation phase

- Provide logistical support to operational forces, particularly in infrastructure, supply and assembly of campaign kitchens and dining halls, water, fuel and miscellaneous material (quartermaster material, campaign tents, generators, fuel tanks, water, etc);
- Collaborate in information actions and public awareness;
- Provide infrastructure for naval units, ground or air support to the areas with victims;
- Promptly clear the roadways communication and relief routes;
- Water supply to populations needy;
- Reinforce and/or reactivate the networks of telecommunications;
- Support with means of Military Engineering in cleaning and decontamination operations affected areas;
- Rehabilitate infrastructure.

The Armed Forces also play a key role in the prevention of Forest Fire, wither in surveillance with access to aerial and land vehicles to patrol the rural areas as well as in the fire combat, and coordination of the Air space in cooperation with the civil protection commander.

The coordination between civil and military is based on the National Civil Protection and Emergency plan, that settles the roles and responsibilities of each entity for the typified event. This cooperation of the entities assigned specific responsibility is made on a cooperation basis, not in a command, where the armed forces are invited to participate in the operational field, thus the armed forces are not under an operational command of the ANEPC, neither it is the Armed Forces role to command the Emergency and operations. This approach covers land and maritime context. In the maritime context the maritime authority that holds the responsibility for the safety operation at sea, again with the cooperation of the Armed Forces, in particular navy and Air force for maritime SAR operations, MEDVAC, and other similar emergency response operations.

The participation and coordination of the Armed forces into civilian context operations to support the population is well established and regulated by legislation that establish their roles and clear acting boundaries. The Armed forces are also involved in the training and live exercises which are conduct regularly.

5.4.4.9. CIMIC in Slovakia

The Ministry of Defence is providing support or technical services within the planning per type of crisis/extraordinary events. There is a catalogue of extraordinary events and the type of planned activities/material and the performance of different actors. One of those actors is Ministry of the Defence and the army. The plans are in confidentiality mode. Activities may vary from participation in delivery of support to municipalities, operative support call centres, distribution of food, water, material in case of floods and other disasters.

The coordination between civil and military is based on ad hoc and planning for each type of event. The coordination is not in the form of a Command-and-Control System, it is based on assigning tasks. Which in practice means that the structures of the armed forces can never be subordinated or under the operational command of representatives of the civilian administration.

There is a new security concept for crisis management stressing the role of cooperation between civil and military staff, however the concept is not proved by the government and though it is not in place.

According to the legislation, the army can be involved in a definite list of rescue and technical services as described above, their involvement is organised by law.

Legislation is well developed and includes a number of laws, decrees, ordinances and orders related to the protection of the population, disaster risk reduction, the definition of obligations and responsibilities and the implementation of European legislation in this area.

The problems in the field of crises management planning can be reduced to needs to perform national risk assessment, needs to cooperate with ministry of defence in delivery of common approach to risk assessment, also contingency planning, needs of assessment of the mitigation measures and etc.

Common problems or interoperability gaps are lack of coordination, lack of common protocols, lack of common indexes, lack of common database, lack of common measurable indicators, and lack of specific education. Need of cross-sectorial indicators and common data platform from all sectors would be beneficial, because the actors operate with data coming from different sectors and etc.

Education, training and joint preparedness are another problem. Education is not in place; it is a subject of private initiatives. The risk managers of the district office raise awareness of the mayors. Need comprehensive education of the crisis management staff.

The new concept for security and crisis management shall improve the cooperation by introducing common standards as per NATO, however it is not an active document.

5.4.4.10. CIMIC in Spain

In Spain, thanks to Royal Decree 1123/2000, Disaster Support Units (DSU) were created to mitigate the disaster wherever it occurred to be integrated into the emergency plan where the disaster occurred. These were teams made up of experienced volunteers with specific training from various operational services who could travel to the scene of the incident and collaborate with the following objectives:

- Analyse and evaluate the needs of intervention and support to emergency management, CBRN Risk and Logistic support and telecommunications.
- Search, rescue, rescue, and health care. Psychological support. Identification of disaster victims.
- Organization of areas of temporary shelters and social assistance. Establishment of essential services.

The DSU intervened in several catastrophes, following the strategy of International Cooperation, such as in the earthquake in Pakistan, Indonesia, Peru, Chile, etc.

Years later, thanks to the Royal Decree on the Rationalization of the Public Sector of 2013, these units were suspended on the understanding that their functions were assumed by the Military Emergency Unit created in 2005.

The Military Emergency Unit (MEU) defined, according to Royal Decree 416/2006, as "a joint force whose mission is intervention anywhere in the national territory, to contribute to the safety and well-being of citizens in cases of serious risk, catastrophe, calamity or other public needs" is formed by highly qualified personnel with the necessary resources and training to intervene immediately in situations of serious emergencies.

Royal Decree 1097/2011, of July 22, establishes the essential rules for coordination with the means of the remaining public administrations that can be mobilized depending on each emergency. In the same way, it establishes the possible situations, whether or not of national interest, in which its Activation can be requested:

- Natural hazards such as floods, floods, earthquakes, landslides, heavy snowfall, and other adverse weather events of great magnitude.
- Forest fires.
- Those derived from technological risks, and among them the chemical, nuclear, radiological, and biological risks.
- To terrorists or unlawful and violent acts, including those against critical infrastructure, dangerous facilities or with nuclear, biological, radiological or chemical agents.
- Contamination of the environment.
- Any other that the President of the Government decides.

The Autonomous Civil Protection Authorities may request the Ministry of the Interior to participate in situations of a serious nature, even if they are not of national interest. However, according to Law 17/2015, the MUE will assume the operational direction under the direction of the Minister of the Interior when the emergency is of national interest, thus strengthening the operational development of the State Emergency Plans.

In short, a very powerful set, rapidly deployed, which allows the State and the rest of the Public Administrations to have a very important support in disasters, when local capacities have been overwhelmed.

Emergencies at sea are excluded from the scope of action of the UME, without prejudice to the fact that in exceptional circumstances their intervention may be agreed, at the proposal of the Minister of Development. As a fundamental instrument of public security, the organisation,

functioning, and implementation of civil protection is carried out by the different public administrations and by other entities involved in risk management.

The Ministry of Interior is the highest authority in charge of Spanish Civil Protection. The Directorate General of Civil Protection and Emergencies (DGPCE) plays an essential role at national level (165).

The cooperation of the various entities responsible for civil protection at both national and supranational level is key for joint action in the field of prevention, planning and disaster response.

The main prevention actions under the scope of civil protection activities are based on public communication and risk awareness, and the self-protection plans developed for all dangerous activities under the regulation of the self-protection rule

In the field of civil-military cooperation, Spain has achieved a specialised model for dealing with emergencies and disasters.

Organic Law 5/2005, of 17 November, on National Defence, established as one of the missions of the Armed Forces the preservation of the security and well-being of citizens in cases of serious risk, catastrophe, calamity or other public needs, in accordance with the provisions of current legislation (166).

In accordance with the mission attributed to the Armed Forces in this law, the Military Emergency Unit (MEU) was created in 2005. This unit is made up of Armed Forces personnel, has the capacity to deploy in an orderly manner on the ground, concentrating operational resources in a short time and permanently having highly qualified personnel with specific training to intervene immediately in serious emergency situations.

This unit acts as a spearhead in support of the civilian authorities, and articulates the mobilisation of additional armed forces capabilities if necessary.

For its integration with civilian services, the regulations and instruments for coordination with the administrations responsible for the national civil protection system have been adapted.

Thus, the collaboration of the Ministry of Defence in civil protection matters is articulated either through agreements and conventions established with other bodies of the general administration or with the autonomous communities, or through the plans approved by the national civil protection commission (167).

These agreements and plans establish how coordination between the institutions involved will be carried out.

The mission of the MEU is to intervene anywhere in the national territory to contribute to the safety and well-being of citizens.

In order for it to intervene in an emergency or disaster, the competent authority must request its participation from the Ministry of the Interior, which transfers it to the Ministry of Defence. Its activation is authorised and ordered by the head of the Ministry of Defence.

With regard to the MEU's relations in the event of activation, it is established that, in the exercise of its powers, it may interact with authorities, bodies and public and private entities outside the Ministry of Defence, within the scope defined by its mission and tasks (168).

In those emergencies in which level 3 (emergency of national interest) is declared, the MEU assumes the operational management of the emergency, acting under the direction of the Minister of the Interior

As for the interaction activities of the Armed Forces with the civilian population in the area of operations, Spain has only one unit with specific combat support preparation. This is the Civil-Military Cooperation Battalion I (BCIMIC I), based in Valencia and belonging to the "Information Operations" Regiment No. 1. Thanks to its specialisation and training, the BCIMIC is frequently called upon to integrate its personnel into combat units for this type of activity.

This unit emerged after Spain's international mission in Afghanistan between 2002 and 2014, where the need for units that could interact with the local population and publicise the objectives of the international mission became apparent.

Thus, units specialised in "CIMIC" (Civil-Military Cooperation) operations emerged: distribution of aid among the population, collaboration in schools, reconstruction projects....

In summary, it can be concluded that the disaster response system in Spain is built on several hierarchical levels, with clear responsibilities and obligations for each of them. The armed forces are used in extreme cases, i.e., when a state of emergency arises at national or international level.

However, no data were found on joint exercises, exercises and other forms of building common response capabilities, as well as on the availability of special documents - doctrines, rules and procedures governing civil-military interaction and coordination of efforts between institutions.

5.4.4.11. CIMIC in Sweden

The Swedish system for disaster management is based on an all-hazards approach. The Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency (MSB) facilitates coordination of measures for prevention, preparedness and response, across sectors and levels of government. The responsibility for crisis and disaster management resides at national, regional, and local levels.

The Crisis and Emergency Management Systems are based on 3 principles. The principle of "responsibility" means that actors retain their ordinary responsibilities in situations of crisis and disaster. This principle also includes a responsibility to support other involved parties as necessary. The principle of "proximity" means that crises and disasters should be managed as close as possible to those primarily concerned. The principle of "similarity", which means that the methods and structures used in crisis and disaster management, should be as similar as possible to those used in normal circumstances. The geographical responsibility to manage an event lies with those parties most directly affected. The rescue services are organised at the local level.

Sweden has a continuous process for national risk assessment. The national risk assessment points to risks within the categories' antagonistic hazards, unintentionally manmade hazards, natural hazards and biological hazards.

A number of the risks can, in worst-case scenarios, lead to catastrophic consequences. These include a radiological event from a nuclear power plant, a dam rupture and a pandemic. Cross border assessments have been made in the past, notably the ash cloud assessment carried out jointly between the Nordic countries

All parties responsible for the protection of people, the environment or the functionality of vital societal functions, are responsible for preventing and preparing for disasters. Planning and financing of risk management is included in the budgets for public sector bodies.

The Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency (MSB) provides training and exercises for organisations, public authorities and individuals at both national and international level. There are national programmes for professional training in prevention and operations on different levels for personnel of the fire and rescue services. Courses are mainly conducted at the MSB College in Sandö and Revinge. Customised training is offered to local authorities and the private sector. MSB delivers international training programmes in close collaboration with the UN and the EU, both on strategic, tactical and operational level.

The primary early warning system is radio, TV, and the outdoor alarm system of 4,500 alarm installations using sirens. An SMS system sends warnings to mobile phones in an affected area. The fire brigades who mainly use this system and the chief in command has the mandate to use it. The police and other organisations can also use this system. Separate indoor and outdoor alarm systems operate in the inner emergency planning zone around Sweden's nuclear power stations.

In the Swedish Disaster Management System municipalities and country administrative boards have respective responsibilities within their geographical areas. On a local level, this entails a responsibility to maintain services like water distribution, schools and rescue services during crises, while the county administrative board primarily has a regional coordinating role. As a national agency, the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency's (MSB) operative assignment is to coordinate, support and facilitate involved parties in response to accidents, crises and emergencies, nationally and internationally. MSB can provide additional resources to municipalities and county administrative boards and other countries, EU and the UN in the form of materials or competency.

The above data show that the Swedish Disaster Response System is highly decentralized, with the responsibility for rescue and recovery falling mainly on local authorities.

The system is well balanced, with very good organization of training and education at all levels and in all possible scenarios, risks and threats to society.

High levels of administrative structures have a coordinating and supporting role. For this reason, the armed forces are not intended to intervene in emergencies, except in extremely complex ones, such as nuclear accidents, disasters and crises at national or international level.

5.5. Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism

5.5.1. Introduction

In this chapter we present the preliminary evaluation of the existing situation regarding the Civil Protection and aid volunteerism at European and local level.

The EU has two main instruments to provide a first response to disasters: civil protection and humanitarian aid. The Treaty of Lisbon sets out that “the Union shall encourage cooperation between Member States in order to improve the effectiveness of systems for preventing and protecting against natural or man-made disasters” (169).

5.5.2. Civil Protection at EU Level

To improve the coordination of the interventions of the European Civil Protection services in emergencies/disasters (of natural, technological, radiological, environmental or terrorist origin) in the Member States, the EU Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM) was born in 2001. This initiative realises:

- Specific training and aid teams
- Inventory of aid and intervention teams available in the Member States
- Conferences, seminars and pilot projects on the most relevant aspects of an intervention
- Create coordination and evaluation teams
- Create a Control and Information Centre (CIC) and a Common Emergency Communication and Information System (CECIS) to communicate with the contact points of the member states
- Detection and rapid alert system
- Facilitate access to material resources and means of transport available in the member and complementary states

The UCPM is an initiative of the European Commission to create a framework for cooperation in disaster preparedness, prevention and response, strengthening the cooperation between Participating States (EU countries and 6 Participating States) in the field of civil protection.

When an emergency overwhelms the response capabilities of a country, it can request assistance through the UCPM. The European Commission plays a key role in coordinating the response to disasters inside and outside the EU, contributing to at least 75% of the transport and/or operational costs of deployments.

The Mechanism also helps coordinate disaster preparedness and prevention activities of national authorities and contributes to the exchange of best practices. This facilitates the continuous development of higher common standards enabling teams to understand different approaches better and work interchangeably when a disaster strikes.

Since its inception in 2001, the UCPM has responded to over 540 requests.

Figure 25 - Operation of the UCPM (170)

Following a request for assistance through the Mechanism, the Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC) mobilises assistance or expertise.

The ERCC is the heart of the UCPM. It coordinates the delivery of assistance to disaster-stricken countries, such as relief items, expertise, civil protection teams and specialised equipment.

The ERCC monitors events around the globe 24/7 and ensures rapid deployment of emergency support through a direct link with national civil protection authorities.

The centre can also financially support the delivery of civil protection teams and assets to the affected country.

From ERCC portal (171) it is possible to access to:

- CECIS: Platform for real time exchange of information between the ERCC and the contact points of the Member States.
- CECIS Marine pollution platform: CECIS Marine Pollution Common information system in the event of accidental marine pollution in the Mediterranean. It improves the coordination of requests and offers for assistance in emergency situations.
- The European Emergency Disaster Response Information System (EDRIS): it contains real time information on ECHO, Member States' and UK contributions to Humanitarian Aid. Information found here has been encoded by Member States and UK.

To ensure compatibility and complementarity between intervention teams, the UCPM provides a training programme, offering experts from all over Europe a deeper knowledge of the requirements of European civil protection missions. The training helps experts improve their coordination and assessment skills in disaster response.

Figure 26 - UCPM Training Program (172)

The UCPM training courses (173) are a supplement to the national training (expert training and the needed basic training for international deployments) providing to the experts by their home country or organization.

DG ECHO funds several exercises annually to increase and improve the collaboration among European civil protection authorities and teams.

The exercise programme offers a variety of civil protection exercises in order to enhance prevention, preparedness and disaster response:

- **MODEX exercises**
 - **Modules Field Exercises (ModFX)** aim to provide an opportunity for testing specific response capacities, as well as the self-sufficiency, interoperability, coordination and procedures of response teams and equipment.
 - **Modules Table-Top Exercises (ModTTX)**, focus on in-depth training of modules, Technical Assistance and Support Teams and EU Civil Protection Teams key personnel.
- **Full-scale exercises**
 - **Table-top exercise (TTX)** is designed to put crisis response managers and practitioners in a situation where they must use existing plans and procedures and make decisions accordingly.
 - **Command post exercise (CPX)** is a functional exercise in which the field response and deployment is simulated, involving the headquarters and/or coordination centres that normally intervene in an emergency.

- **Full-scale exercise (FSX)** is the most complex and resource-intensive operation-based exercise. They involve multiple agencies, organisations and jurisdictions and validate many facets of preparedness. Full-scale exercises often include many international players operating under the host nation command system.
- Other exercises
 - **Plug-in exercises** create the true nature of a real deployment outside the EU in a different emergency environment in terms of structure, systems and culture and weather conditions.
 - **Host nation support table-top exercises** focus on challenges encountered by a country affected by a disaster in receiving, integrating and coordinating the international assistance in its response operations.

National Training Coordinators (NTC) (174) select and nominate participants to the UCPM training courses and exercises. They build and maintain close relations with the national civil protection authorities, civil protection experts and stakeholders, training coordinators of other UCPM Member and Participating states, civil protection training centres and the European Commission.

5.5.2.1. The Early Warning and Information Systems

The EU's early warning and information systems (175) help the Emergency Response Coordination Centre monitor hazards and events worldwide. Examples of hazards that the Centre monitors are earthquakes and tsunamis, tropical cyclones, volcanoes, droughts, floods, and forest fires.

EU early warning tools complement national public warning systems.

To that end, the EU works closely together with Member States in establishing and further developing their national public warning systems. The aim is to protect citizens from disasters.

Alerts allow the ERCC to provide a comprehensive early assessment. It also enables early action within the framework of EU civil protection inside the EU and worldwide.

Close cooperation with various research institutes facilitates the development of disaster forecasting and disaster management tools for both natural and human-induced hazards:

- Global Disaster Alert and Coordination System (176): provides alerts and estimates impacts of earthquakes, tsunamis, tropical cyclones, floods, volcanos, and droughts worldwide.
- European and Global Flood Awareness Systems (177): give notifications on floods up to 15 days in advance in Europe and worldwide.
- European and Global Forest Fire Information System (178): forecast dangerous weather conditions up to 10 days ahead and provide near-real-time information on active fires and burnt areas. The systems analyse the severity and risk that each forest fire poses for the local population and the environment. This allows informed decisions on the deployment of the rescEU firefighting capacity.

- European and Global Drought Observatories (179): give information on droughts risks in Europe and worldwide, including meteorological indicators, soil moisture anomalies, vegetation stress and river low flows.

These early warning and information systems are part of the EU's Copernicus programme.

Through the Copernicus emergency management service, the Emergency Response Coordination Centre can also produce different satellite images. The aim is to monitor events from space before they happen and assess their impact once they have hit an area.

The Copernicus satellite is essential when deployments under the UCPM take place.

In addition, a system of 24 Galileo satellites and ground stations provide geographic positioning information to Member States to broadcast alert messages.

As part of its European Scientific Partnerships initiative, the European Commission has established the European Natural Hazard Scientific Partnership. It offers 24/7 monitoring and scientific advice.

The partnership covers earthquakes, tsunamis, severe weather, floods, volcanoes, and forest fires both at European and global levels. It will be expanded to cover human-induced hazards in the future.

The EU also cooperates with other organisations such as UNESCO's Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission. An agreement with the European Mediterranean Seismological Centre has allowed earthquake detection in the Mediterranean area to be considerably quicker and more accurate.

5.5.2.2. The Emergency Support Instrument

The Emergency Support Instrument (ESI) (180) enables the European Union to support its Member States when a crisis reaches exceptional scale and impact, with wide-ranging consequences on the lives of citizens.

The ESI is a flexible tool, designed to respond to different types of evolving needs. Member States can use it when they require immediate support in addressing a crisis, as well as for crisis prevention, and during the recovery phase.

5.5.3. Civil Protection at National Level

National civil protection systems are underpinned by European solidarity in action. Under the Mechanism, countries stand ready and prepared to help each other when national resources for disaster response are overwhelmed or need to be reinforced. This section provides an introductory overview of key elements of the national disaster management system of the different countries.

The following table summarises the information related to civil protection at national level within European Union (https://civil-protection-humanitarian-aid.ec.europa.eu/what/civil-protection/national-disaster-management-system_en, s.f.).

Doc title: Landscape of emerging preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

Country	Responsible for international coordination	Bilateral agreements with other countries	Training and exercises
Austria	Austrian Federal Ministry of the Interior	Yes	Functional and full-scale exercises at the federal level. Strategic exercises are regularly performed at the national level. Austria is also engaged in European and international exercises
Bulgaria	The National Operational Centre (NOC) of the Fire Safety and Civil Protection Directorate of the Ministry of Interior	Yes	The training of Fire Safety and Civil Protection staff is carried out in two centres, the Centre for Specialization and Professional Training in Fire Safety and Rescue in the city of Varna, and the Centre for Professional Qualification in the town of Montana
Czech Republic	The Ministry of Interior is involved in engagement of the Czech Republic into international rescue operations in emergencies and in providing humanitarian assistance, in cooperation with the Ministry of Foreign Affairs	Yes	Members of the Fire Rescue Service (FRS) and other fire units are trained to provide effective help in emergencies. There is the annual training plan with annual and monthly exercises. Each fire station and each regional FRS have their own exercise plans, coordinated at national level to ensure other services (regional EMS, police, army and other bodies of the Integrated Rescue System of the Czech Republic are incorporated into these plans
Denmark	Danish Emergency Management Agency (DEMA)	Yes	DEMA and other organisations offer a wide range of training courses. Exercises are also held regularly in the context of the National Operational Staff and the 12 local operational staff
Estonia	Information and Monitoring Department of the Ministry of Interior	Yes	The Estonian Academy of Security Sciences is an educational institution in the field of internal security for the entire country. Crisis management exercises are organised. There are table top, command post, field and combined exercises. It also participates in MODEX exercises
Finland	Emergency Response Centre Administration is an agency under	yes	The Emergency Services Academy Finland arranges basic and advanced fire and rescue training, civil protection and

Country	Responsible for international coordination	Bilateral agreements with other countries	Training and exercises
	the Ministry of the Interior		<p>preparedness training, and other training in emergency operations. It is also responsible for the execution of national exercises.</p> <p>Regional rescue departments are responsible for ensuring that volunteer fire brigades or other contracting organisations have adequate training for their jobs. This training is conducted mainly by the Finnish National Rescue Association and regional rescue service organisations.</p> <p>Finland also participates actively in EU and international exercises</p>
Germany	The Bundeswehr Territorial Tasks Command (KdoTerrAufgBw) is the central coordination and control command	yes	<p>The Federal Academy of Civil Protection and Civil Defence (BABZ), as part of the Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance, is the central educational institution of the Federation for civil protection and crisis management. The Federal Agency for Technical Relief (THW) combines basic training at its local sections with additional specialist and management training and the training of experts for missions abroad at its training centres. Exercises are implemented on various levels (regional, national, international) to apply and deepen the acquired knowledge.</p> <p>Since maintenance of efficient fire services is one of the compulsory tasks of municipalities and towns, fire brigade education and training follows a primarily municipal approach and differs according to the type of fire brigade.</p> <p>The different relief organisations run their own training programs</p>
Greece	The General Secretary for Civil Protection	Yes	<p>Trainings and exercises at national, regional, and local level by competent authorities.</p> <p>Greece also participates in the UCPM training programme</p>
Hungary	The National Directorate-	Yes	The Director-General, acting under his authority in the field of disaster

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Country	Responsible for international coordination	Bilateral agreements with other countries	Training and exercises
	General for Disaster Management of the Ministry of Interior (NDGDM)		management, will determine the topics for the training and further training of professional staff and the activities of scientific researchers and approve the content of the training. The Inspectorate General for Fire and Civil Protection is responsible for the planning and organisation of the training of the county fire and civil defence chief inspectors and the affected personnel
Iceland	The Minister of Justice is the supreme authority for civil protection matters. The National Commissioner of the Icelandic Police is responsible for the National Crisis and Co-ordination Centre for Civil Protection	Yes	ICE-SAR volunteers, the Red Cross, and professional fire fighters run their own training facilities. Training for area command and on-scene command for the local level are in the hands of National Commissioner of the Icelandic Police/Department of Civil Protection and Emergency Management as well as training for the crisis centres. Experts in Civil Protection participate in training courses of the UCPM
Ireland	The decision to seek assistance from outside the region, including from Northern Ireland should be made by the lead agency, in association with the other principal response agencies	Yes	Each lead government departments are responsible for regular exercises and training plans within their remits, which are reported upon at the Governmental Task Force. In addition, at both regional and local levels, regular exercises are planned and conducted under the Major Emergency Management framework across a wide range of possible scenarios

Country	Responsible for international coordination	Bilateral agreements with other countries	Training and exercises
Italy	Civil Protection Department is the Italian Focal Point of the UCPM	Yes	<p>The Department, as coordinator and director of the National Service, plans, schedules and carries out training activities for the components and operational structures, especially for volunteers.</p> <p>The aim of these activities is to guarantee a constant update of all the resources operating in the field of civil protection, and to encourage the adoption and diffusion of common procedures. This website shows the list of training initiatives carried out by the Department, also in collaboration with competence centres, universities and other subjects operating within the National Service.</p>
Latvia	Ministry of Defence with Cabinet of Ministers 'On the Provision of Host Nation Support'	yes	<p>Types of civil protection exercise and procedures are regulated by the Cabinet of Ministers Regulation No.341. This Regulation determines exercises at four levels, where exercises to test for disaster preparedness are conducted locally (every 3 years), regionally (every 4 years) and nationally (every 4 years) exercises.</p> <p>Latvia has organised exercises in the frame UCPM, as well as various exercises in the frameworks of realised projects</p>
Luxembourg	Minister of Home Affairs with the Luxembourg Fire and Rescue Corps (Corps grand-ducal d'incendie et de secours (CGDIS))	Yes	<p>CGDIS is in charge of training and exercises with CGDIS' national rescue training institute (INFS).</p> <p>The High Commission for National Protection (HCPN) regularly organises national table top and operational inter-agency exercises involving the strategic and operational partners.</p>
Malta	The Ministry for Home Affairs, National Security and Law Enforcement with The Civil	Yes	<p>The Civil Protection Department in Malta is the leading governmental department that ensures national training and planning for national exercises is carried out as stipulated by local and EU</p>

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Country	Responsible for international coordination	Bilateral agreements with other countries	Training and exercises
	Protection Council		legislation. Training exercises at national and local level by the competent authority assisted by the Civil Protection Department. Members of the Civil Protection Department also participate in the UCPM training
Montenegro	The Rescue and Protection Directorate and Ministry of Foreign Affairs	Yes	Basic and advanced levels of training (according to the Law on Protection and Rescue, Official Gazette of Montenegro, 13/07, 32/11 and 54/16, article 17). These trainings are conducted by the 'Rulebook for basic and specialist training of members of civil protection units; specialized protection and rescue units and voluntary protection and rescue unit'. Due to the lack of a national training centre, many training sessions are conducted through various types of projects
North Macedonia	The Ministry of Defence with the Crisis Management Centre takes over the international communication and coordination with international institutions	Yes	The Republic of North Macedonia takes part in various national, regional, and international exercises. Protection and Rescue Directorate carries out trainings of the response units, institutions and private companies. International trainings are carried out under UCPM, bilateral cooperation and international actors (NATO, International Trust Fund)
Poland	The leading civil protection authority is the National Headquarters of the State Fire Service (KG PSP) which is subordinate to the Minister of Interior and Administration.	Yes	The state fire service (PSP) embraces the network of fire service schools educating firefighters: Main School of Fire Service (SGSP) in Warsaw, Warrant Officers Schools of PSP in Częstochowa (CS PSP), Kraków (SA PSP Kraków) and Poznań (SA PSP Poznań) and Non-Commissioned Officers School of PSP in Bydgoszcz (SP PSP). Basic firefighting course provided in regional training centres and in select fire service schools. Professional firefighters

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Country	Responsible for international coordination	Bilateral agreements with other countries	Training and exercises
			<p>who have completed a basic training course can continue their education in Warrant Officers Schools. SGSP in Warsaw is the only technical academy in Poland that trains fire service officers, fire safety and civil safety engineers</p>
Portugal	<p>Ministry of internal Administration with the ANEPC (National Emergency and Civil Protection Authority)</p>	Yes	<p>Regular training exercises and conducted in Portugal at national level and with Spain on cross border events.</p> <p>The ANEPC conducts regular personnel training personnel courses on education for the fire responders forces national wide. Internationally, Portugal is also involved with EU and with other countries, on bilateral agreements, to participate in training and exercises.</p>
Republic of Croatia	<p>Ministry of the Interior with the Civil protection Headquarter.</p>	yes	<p>The National Civil Protection Training Centre prepares and carries out the education for those involved in the civil protection system. It also prepares the annual plan of exercises.</p> <p>The training is also carried out by the basic civil protection operational forces (Croatian Mountain Rescue Service and Croatian Red Cross) per their own professional expertise</p>
Republic of Cyprus	<p>Minister of Interior with a special ministerial group convenes to coordinate the measures taken to address the disaster</p>	Yes	<p>Cyprus Civil Defence conscripts follow a training programme for a year; for their second year of service, they move from the second wave of response to the first wave. Training continues for the second year and it comprises more practical matters and exercises. Subjects from the UCPM training programme have been included in the national training.</p> <p>National exercise programs are held, at national, regional, and local level.</p> <p>The responsible organisation for inter-agency civil protection (horizontal exercises) is the Cyprus Civil Defence</p>

Country	Responsible for international coordination	Bilateral agreements with other countries	Training and exercises
Romania	General Inspectorate for Emergency Situations (IGSU under the Ministry of Internal Affairs.	yes	<p>IGSU responsibilities for exercises/trainings are divided between 2 directorates: Directorate for Exercises Planning and Monitoring Emergency Situations, and Directorate for Preparedness for Intervention.</p> <p>Based on the types of risks, IGSU and subordinated units regularly carry out exercises and drills.</p> <p>There are training centres for specific intervention skills such as: fire tactics, extrication and resuscitation, search and rescue in hostile environment, urban search and rescue (Special Unit for Intervention in Emergency Situations) and divers.</p>
Slovakia	The Ministry of Interior	Yes	<p>There are no regular trainings, usually training and exercises are organised by various rescue teams. Also, firefighters, mountain rescue service providers, medical rescuers, water rescuers and related are organising their own exercises.</p> <p>There is no regular plan due to lack of professional and qualified centralised coordination and lack of budget. The district crisis managers are also supporting training. There are obligatory by law full exercises concerning mass casualties' events concerning nuclear incidents. The training involves also the public, local medical staff, NGOs, mayors, media, the crisis managers on district level, etc. Fire fighters have annual plans for exercising incidents in different facilities such as hospitals, medical centres, or floods, etc. However, there is an overall need for regular exercise training. Slovak NGOs are leading into two international modules Blue Hospitals, EURACARE and ETC. Also, the firefighters maintain a couple of national modules.</p>

Country	Responsible for international coordination	Bilateral agreements with other countries	Training and exercises
Slovenia	Administration of the Republic of Slovenia for Civil Protection and Disaster Relief (ACPDR) within the Ministry of Defence	yes	Professional fire fighters are trained at a professional firefighting school, which is part of the national training centre for civil protection and disaster relief and under ACPDR. Voluntary fire-fighters are partially trained in the professional fire-fighting school and partially by the Slovene Firefighting Association. Other voluntary organisations train their members themselves. The state and municipalities train civil protection personnel, using programmes approved by the competent ministry. National and regional exercises are organised by governmental bodies with the ACPDR as the leading authority. Table-top exercises are mostly conducted as one day or multiple-day exercises with simulations of procedures and activities. Field exercises are organised as one day or multiple days of practical or combined exercises
Spain	The Directorate General of Civil Protection and Emergencies (DGPCE)	Yes	The National Civil Protection School (ENPC) is the training branch of the DGPCE pursuant to Law 17/2015. It is a major centre for strategic management that provides specialised training for national and international staff, first responders of CP agencies, and volunteers. National exercises test the plans to cope with the different risks at local, regional and state levels and to practice emergency management and intervention tasks. Spain has coordinated major full-scale exercises and table top exercises funded by UCPM
Sweden	Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency (MSB). The responsibility for host nation support in Sweden stays	yes	MSB provides training and exercises for organisations, public authorities and individuals at both national and international level. There are national programmes for professional training in prevention and operations on different

Country	Responsible for international coordination	Bilateral agreements with other countries	Training and exercises
	with the party requesting international support		levels for personnel of the fire and rescue services. Courses are mainly conducted at the MSB College in Sandö and Revinge. Customised training is offered to local authorities and the private sector. MSB delivers international training programmes in close collaboration with the UN and the EU, both on strategic, tactical and operational level. MSB is involved in development and delivery of the EU training programme including training courses and exercises

Table 5 – Civil protection at national level within EU

Although the responsibility for cross-border cooperation lies with different bodies in the EU countries according to their internal organisation, all of them have bilateral agreements with most of their neighbouring countries and most of them are involved in the UCPM.

In most of the cases the coordination and international cooperation in case of transborder crises is the responsibility of the Ministry of Interior. There are a few examples when this responsibility is given to the Ministry of Defence, Ministry of Foreign Affairs or a specialised state agency.

There is a diversity of training and training centres within the EU, but it can be noted that civil protection training is accompanied by practical exercises and regular drills.

Most often the exercises are carried out at national level and they are separate for the firefighters, medical staff, military personnel, etc. International trainings are carried out as a practice under the UCPM and some international actors like NATO.

5.5.3.1. Bulgaria

The response to disasters is organised through the unified rescue system (URS), which includes structures of ministries, municipalities, companies, and the organisations of volunteers and the armed forces. The national operational centre (NOC) of the Fire Safety and Civil Protection Directorate of the Ministry of Interior operates as a point of coordination and information for the unified rescue system and is in constant connection with the 28 regional operational centres in the country. It acts as the National Contact Point and carries out a round-the-clock duty for forces and resources of the General Directorate for Fire Safety and Civil Protection. It maintains a continuous connection and information exchange on disaster response, fire and emergency situations as a 24/7 national operational point with ERCC.

Bulgaria has a number of bilateral agreements with neighbouring countries and participates in a number of bilateral and multilateral frameworks addressing disaster risks, like disaster preparedness and prevention initiative for southeast Europe (DPPI SEE).

The General Directorate for the Fire Safety and Civil Protection takes active part in transboundary projects, like EMERSIS I and II, ROBG-351, INTERREF-IPA CBC Bulgaria-Serbia and Bulgaria-Turkey, etc.

Bulgaria develops a host nation support plan according to EU and NATO guidelines.

The training of Fire Safety and Civil Protection (FSCP) staff is carried out in two centres, the Centre for Specialization and Professional Training in Fire Safety and Rescue in Varna, and the Centre for Professional Qualification in Montana. The training includes initial training for firefighters, specialised rescue training, and training for team commanders and head of shifts. The Centre in Montana is involved in international training and exercises within the EU framework, but also in NATO, IAEA and regional initiatives.

Under the UCPM, the FSCP directorate participates in the consortium that organises and conducts the assessment mission course and is the leading partner in the consortium that conducts the Seminar for Mechanism Experts in Sofia. The FSCP directorate participates regularly in the modules exercises and is part of a consortium.

5.5.3.2. Denmark

The Danish fire and rescue service consists of 24 municipal fire and rescue services, the municipal and national support sites, and the national, regional fire and rescue service under the Danish Emergency Management Agency (DEMA). The municipal fire and rescue services are responsible for initiating immediate emergency response, while DEMMA assists at larger or more complex incidents that require specialised equipment or personnel.

DEMA is widely engaged in cross-border, European and International cooperation in order to enhance disaster management in Denmark, in Europe, and beyond. This includes extensive cooperation with international organisations EU, UN, NATO, the Nordic countries, the Baltic Sea States, and bilateral cooperation with Germany.

Host Nation Support in Denmark follows the principle of sector responsibility. DEMMA has prepared a set of procedures to be followed in case DEMMA requires assistance from other nations within the area of disaster management and response.

The Danish Emergency Management Agency (DEMA) and other organisations offer a wide range of training courses. Currently, DEMMA's course catalogue includes 32 courses for own personnel and other sectors, ranging from courses regarding the function as on-scene incident commander to courses in crisis communication.

Ample training opportunities also exist via numerous exercises (procedure, dilemma, crisis management and full-scale). Exercises are also held regularly in the context of the National Operational Staff and the 12 local operational staff.

5.5.3.3. Greece

The basic actors in cases of emergency in Greece are Governmental Services, such as the Fire Service, the Emergency Medical Service, the Police and the Coastguard. In the occurrence of incidents with increased needs, e.g., Mass Casualty Incidents or Search and Rescue events, additional services are activated. For example, the Special Department of Disaster Medicine of the EMS, which pertains to the Ministry of Health or the Disaster Response Special Unit, called

EMAK (Eidiki Monada Antimetopisis Katastrofon) of the FS, which pertains to the Ministry for Climate Crisis and Civil Protection. Additionally, there are component units of the Coast Guard, which pertain to the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Insular Policy or even the Army.

In all major emergency events, the general coordination is the duty of the General Secretariat for Civil Protection (GSCP), according to the General Plan of Civil Protection “Xenokratis”, as it is elaborately described in the Ministerial Decision #1299/2003. The GSCP was founded in 1995 and its officials and experts act on a local, regional or national level, depending on the scale of the incident.

Apart from the EUCPM, agreements and memoranda of cooperation between Member States of the EU and countries outside of the Union have and are still being established. A significant number of bilateral and multilateral agreements and cooperation protocols have been signed between the General Secretariat for Civil Protection of Greece and civil protection authorities of other countries. These agreements are listed below:

Greece-Bulgaria: On the 23rd of April 1989, in the town of Haskovo, Bulgaria the “Ratification of the agreement between the governments of the Hellenic Republic and People’s Republic of Bulgaria for the early notification of nuclear accident and exchange of information for nuclear plants” was signed. Its content is related to the exchange of information between the two countries regarding the operation of nuclear plants and early notification in case of accidents. The agreement entered into action on 20/12/1991.

Greece-Cyprus: On the 23rd and 24th of January 1997, in Nicosia Cyprus the “Ratification of the Cooperation Protocols in the fields of Local Administration, Defense Policy and Civil Protection and Public Administration between the Ministry of Interior, Public Administration and E-Governance of the Hellenic Republic and the Ministries of Interior and Finances of the Republic of Cyprus” was signed, entering into force on 17/07/2006. This protocol is related to the general cooperation and joint actions between the two countries.

Greece-USA: On the 9th of January 2001, in Athens the “Ratification of the Intention’s Protocol between the Ministry of Interior, Public Administration and E-Governance / General Secretariat for Civil Protection of the Hellenic Republic and the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) of the USA on the cooperation in prevention and response to natural and technological disasters” was signed. The content of this agreement is cooperation between the countries in case of natural and manmade disasters, the exchange of information and expertise, training and exercise observation. It entered into force on the 4th of December 2002.

Greece-Malta: In Valletta on May 24, 2001, the “Ratification of the Agreement between the government of the Hellenic Republic and the government of Malta in the field of Civil Protection” was signed, which entered into force on 08/04/2003. The content of the Agreement is cooperation in the prevention of and response to natural and technological disasters.

Greece-Hungary: In Budapest on 12/9/2000, the “Ratification of the Agreement between the government of the Hellenic Republic and the government of the Hungarian Republic on the cooperation and mutual assistance offer in the field of prevention and elimination of the effects of natural and man-made disasters and serious accidents” was signed.

Greece-Ukraine: The “Ratification of the Agreement between the government of the Hellenic Republic and the Ministerial Council of Ukraine on the cooperation in the field of prevention of

industrial accidents, natural disasters and the elimination of its effects” was signed in Athens on the 21st of February 2000, thus establishing a protocol of cooperation between the two countries regarding prevention and response activities in case of disasters. It entered into force on 14/11/2002.

Greece-Russia: On 21/02/2000 the “Ratification of the Agreement between the government of the Hellenic Republic and the government of the Russian Federation on the cooperation in the field of prevention and response to natural and man-made disasters” was signed between Greece and Russia, the content of which is cooperation in prevention and response to disasters, as well as, joint training courses and exchange of information. It entered into force on 19/06/2002.

Greece-Turkey: On 08/11/2001 the “Ratification of the Protocol between the government of the Hellenic Republic and the government of the Turkish Republic on the establishment of the Joint Hellenic Turkish Standby Disaster Response Unit” was signed regarding the establishment, structure and operation of the Joint Hellenic Turkish Standby Disaster Response Unit. It entered into force on 20/05/2002. Moreover, the “Ratification of the Memorandum of Understanding between the United Nations, the Government of the Hellenic Republic and the Government of the Republic of Turkey on cooperation in the field of Humanitarian Emergencies” was signed in New York on the 16th of September 2002.

Greece-Israel: In 2017 a joint Declaration of Intent on Bilateral cooperation in the fields of Civil Protection, Emergency Management and Mutual Assistance, between the Ministry of Interior of the Hellenic Republic and the Ministry of Defence of the state of Israel was signed.

Greece-North Macedonia: In 2021 an MoU on cooperation in the field of civil protection between the Government of the Hellenic Republic and the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia was signed.

Greece-France: A bilateral cooperation between Greece and France exists, which is widely known with the term HE-FRA, i.e., Hellenic-French Cooperation in the Civil Protection sector. The content of this cooperation is related to the management of forest fires, which affect both countries and devastate vast forested areas annually. On the 27th of November 2007, a memorandum of mutual assistance in aerial resources (CL-145) for fire suppression was signed between the two countries. On the 27th of November 2007 the Joint Decision between the Hellenic and the French secretariats for civil protection was ratified, thus creating the “Joint Hellenic-French Civil Protection Working Group”, also known as HE-FRA / J1. On the 13th of June 2008 a Joint Minute of HE-FRA / J1 was signed and concurrently submitted to the G.S.C.P. of the two countries. This Joint Minute was fully accepted by the Civil Protection Secretariats and by the Air Forces and Fire Brigades as well.

Other existing regional and multilateral agreements

On the 15th of April 1998, in Sochi, Russia, the “Ratification of the Agreement between the Governments of the States participating in the **Black Sea Economic Cooperation** (B.S.E.C.) for cooperation in the field of emergency assistance and immediate response to natural and man-made disasters” was signed. The participating states are in alphabetical order Azerbaijan, Armenia, Bulgaria, Georgia, Greece, Moldova, Romania, Russia and Ukraine. The content of the Agreement is exchange of information, provision of assistance and coordination of response in case of disasters. Moreover, issues related to border management and border crossing are included in the Agreement.

Greece is a Member State of the **EUR-OPA Major Hazards Agreement** along with Albania, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Georgia, Greece, Lebanon, Luxembourg, Malta, Republic of Moldova, Monaco, Morocco, North Macedonia, Portugal, Romania, San Marino, Serbia, Slovak Republic and Ukraine. The Agreement was set up by the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe in 1987. It establishes and promotes collaboration between the Member and Participating States regarding prevention, preparation and protection against natural hazards affecting Europe and the Mediterranean Sea.

On the 19th of February 2008 Greece became a full member of the **“Force d’Intervention Rapide Europeenne 4”**, until then known as FIRE 4 and, since the inclusion of Greece, renamed to FIRE 5. The “FIRE 4” cross-border cooperation was already established on 19/05/2006 in Graz Austria, between Italy, France, Spain and Portugal. The content of this collaboration is the development of joint actions and assistance between the five Member States, for the management of disasters around the Mediterranean. In March 2001 an MoU between the Islamic Republic of Iran, the Republic of Armenia, and the Hellenic Republic on Issues of Risk Management of Technological and Natural Disasters, Health & Environment.

Since 1958 the Hellenic Republic has been a member state of the **International Maritime Organization**. On November the 2nd 1973, the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL) was adopted, whereas the Protocol was adopted in 1978. On October the 2nd 1983 both the Protocol and the Convention entered into force. Its content is related to the prevention, response and recovery strategies to combat accidental and/or intentional marine pollution from ships.

Greece has signed the **Convention on the Transboundary Effects of Industrial Accidents**, which entered into force on 19/04/2000. The focus of the Convention is on industrial accidents that have transboundary effects. The Convention provides measures to mitigate the effects of such disasters, as well as measures for preventing them from occurring training and exercises are undertaken at the national, regional, and local levels by competent authorities.

Current volunteer training

In Greece, volunteer training is carried out by the organization in which each volunteer is a member.

The Fire Service is the only public authority employing volunteers. In order to bring them to the position of safely and adequately conducting their duties along with the staff of the service, the FS volunteers attend the FS Academy, where newly trained volunteers are accepted twice a year. After their graduation, the new volunteers are allocated to Fire Stations in the Greek region.

In addition, NGOs ought to be operational all year round and act both locally, regionally and nationally, depending on their capacities. They can be activated either at the call of any citizen/private actor in need, according to their expertise and always reporting to the pertinent official governmental authority. Finally, any NGO can be mobilized from any official request of the GSCP or any other governmental service (e.g., the Coast Guard). In order to be in position to address these calls, the NGOs’ members attend various courses within their own NGO boundaries and receive certifications from third organizations. Apart from these courses, NGO members can attend the FS Academy special training, designated for dedicated types of incidents, such as forest fire prevention and control.

Future volunteer training

As mentioned in the respective chapter of T6.2, according to Hellenic Law 4662/2020 - OGG 27/A/7-2-2020 the framework of voluntarism in Greece is in transition. The mentioned law is in force but is not applied in its entirety yet. Nevertheless, its full application is expected in the near future as soon as all requirements foreseen in it are in place.

According to the provisions of this Law, the GSCP has the steering and coordinating role in Civil Protection training, and prepares all volunteers through courses held in the Academy of Civil Protection. The Academy may enter into Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs), employment agreements, program agreements or contracts with competent public or private bodies, national or supranational, or with other, especially authorized/recognized for this purpose, bodies and institutions, to support its educational purposes.

The Volunteering and Education Directorate of the GSCP is in charge of informing Volunteer Organizations about all types of educational programs. Each volunteer is obliged to receive supplementary training six years after his/her initial acquisition of volunteering status.

Greece also participates in the Union Civil Protection Mechanism training programme, and Greek authorities have also organised international exercises.

5.5.3.4. Italy

At European level, the Civil Protection Department (CPD) is the Italian Focal Point of the Union Civil Protection Mechanism. It is the CPD who declares the state of emergency and outlines the interventions to manage the emergency. All interventions are based on the principle of subsidiarity, according to which the actions of the EU must always be undertaken on request of and in coordination with the authorities of the affected state.

There are a charge number of international agreements and technical cooperation pacts signed by the CPD with equivalent institutions in foreign countries and international organizations.

5.5.3.5. Slovakia

The Ministry of Interior (MoI) of the Slovak Republic is responsible for civil protection, crisis management, integrated rescue system, civil emergency planning, critical infrastructure protection, economic mobilisation, civil protection inventory and supplies management, and humanitarian aid. The civil protection and humanitarian aid agenda of the Ministry of Interior is distributed between several sub-actors: the Crisis Management Section, the Intervention teams of the Firefighters Forces and Volunteer Firefighters Forces, the Mountain Rescue Services, chemical agents laboratories, eight emergency coordination centres, first responders of the integrated emergency services including private NGOs and firms delivering rescues, research and first aid services by ambulances and helicopters. These are all actors integrated under the emergency rescue coordination centre.

Figure 27 – Contact point for extraordinary events

Apart from the first responders, the MoI is responsible for the strategic crisis management and ensures evacuation, early warning, sheltering and material and non-food aid in mass disasters destroying the residential areas and access to water and supplies. The organisation of rescue and recovery activities is coordinated by district and local crisis committees and led by the district crisis management units and representatives of the local and regional self-government authorities. The Ministry of Interior is responsible, and regional/district crisis management units and eight regional coordination emergency centres cooperate with the Police forces and Firefighting and Rescue Corps. In addition, the Ministry is responsible for integrating the emergency rescue system (112), provision of assistance in emergencies, coordination of the firefighters, rescue services, first aid services, chemical labs, mountain rescue, and mines rescue services.

On the regional level, the MoI has represented 74 district crisis management units. The latter are delegated civil protection and crisis management responsibilities concerning the preparation, prevention, reaction and recovery of the designated areas/communities. Those units play a critical role in implementing civil protection actions and crisis communication at the regional, district, and local levels. In addition, the crisis managers on the regional level are involved in building concept papers, methodologies and application of practical experience to legal and regulative legislation.

The methodological coordination and liaising of actors are in the national crisis management unit's hands, which needs to be further strengthened and modernised to complete its activities better.

Those regional crisis management units are responsible for analysing risks and management of crises in each region/district. Units comprise strategic crisis managers liaising with eight regional emergency centres. The units are the main and most important actors in delivering disaster prevention and mitigation of risks, leading to plans for preparedness, emergency, response and civil protection, and handling the early warning means for communication with mayors and

citizens. The district crisis management units also promote communication with the educational and NGO sector and provide preparedness actions with intervention first responders units and mayors on a local level. Furthermore, the district crisis managers are responsible for the professional education and awareness of the mayors and local/regional crisis management committees convened in disasters and crises. In addition, they distribute material aid, coordinate evacuation, temporary sheltering of victims of disasters, and manage pandemics and others.

The district crisis management units are also responsible for coordinating the reporting and mapping of risks and hazardous events, providing expertise in risk management and rescue missions, and providing legal framework and training activities to improve prevention, preparedness, and response to disasters.

Key personnel who ensure fulfilling tasks of civil protection and crisis management are regularly trained and prepared accordingly to national plans and legislative. Several training facilities, under the Ministry of Interior, are used for specialised additional education in the field of civil protection, crisis management, and prevention. National exercise programmes are included in the annual plans of action of Section of Crisis Management of the Ministry of the Interior; these include table-top, field and full-scale exercises throughout the year. These are jointly organised with other first responders (capacities in the Integrated Rescue System), to practice common procedures and methodologies used in emergency response and disaster recovery. Field exercises are conducted on various training facilities, with the cooperation of the Ministry of Defence.

Slovakia has individual agreements and memoranda on mutual cooperation and support in case of extraordinary events with neighbouring countries. Similar documents exist also on the level of neighbouring regions (regions sharing state border). These agreements have proved effective, especially in the initial hours of the intervention and create the conditions for building mutual relations, which significantly contributes to the sustainability of such cooperation. Unfortunately, recent Corona restrictions negatively affected these efforts.

Cross-sectorial cooperation is a bit issue within Slovakia. A significant part of EMS providers is private companies. Their participation in multi-agency training and exercises, as well as research and development, is complicated, as it represents an extra expense (time of the personnel, equipment blocking, financial costs). Such activities are not directly stated in the particular law. This represents great room for improvement.

Aid Volunteerism in Slovakia

There are several organizations actively involved in this area. The most relevant are:

- Slovak Red Cross
- Association of Samaritans of SR
- Malteser aid

- Salus Vitalis
- Voluntary FRS
- Civil protection units, and others

5.5.3.6. Spain

In all emergency situations, the national level is in charge of requesting international assistance to the Union Civil Protection Mechanism and/or under the umbrella of the bilateral agreements.

The Directorate General of Civil Protection and Emergencies (DGPCE) is the point of contact for the European Civil Protection Mechanism and coordinates with other central government bodies and autonomous communities.

In addition, the National Council of Civil Protection has the role of Spanish Committee for International strategy for Disaster Reduction under the secretariat of the DGPCE. Thus, the DGPCE is also the focal point for the implementation of the Sendai Framework and works with the National Council to set up the indicators to measure progress in achieving the seven global targets. The DGPCE is also the International Search and Rescue Advisory Group (INSARAG) Policy focal point.

Spain is member of the Iberoamerican Association of governmental bodies for civil protection and civil defence since its creation in July 1996.

Spain has bilateral agreements on civil protection assistance and cooperation with Algeria, France, Morocco, Russia, Portugal, and Tunisia.

The National Civil Protection School (ENPC) is the training branch of the DGPCE pursuant to Law 17/2015. It is a major centre for strategic management that provides specialised training for national and international staff, first responders of CP agencies, and volunteers.

Each year, the ENPC approves a training plan with an average of 160 courses, 6000 students and 4000 teaching hours.

National exercises test the plans to cope with the different risks at local, regional and state levels and to practice emergency management and intervention tasks.

Concerning international exercises, Spain has coordinated five major full-scale exercises and table top exercises funded by the European Commission within the Union Civil Protection Mechanism framework since 2012.

5.5.4. EU Aid Volunteers Initiative

EU Aid Volunteers (EUAV) brings volunteers and organisations together from different countries, providing practical support to humanitarian aid projects and contributing to strengthening local capacity and resilience of disaster-affected communities.

The establishment of the EU Aid Volunteers initiative is foreseen in the Lisbon Treaty, with the objective being "to establish framework for joint contributions from young Europeans to the humanitarian aid operations of the Union" (Art 214.5 TEU).

In 2014, the regulation establishing the European Voluntary Humanitarian Aid Corps ("EU Aid Volunteers initiative") was adopted: Regulation (EU) no 375/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 3rd April 2014.

The legal basis of the Initiative can be found at:

- REGULATION N° 375/2014 (182); Establishes the European Voluntary Humanitarian Aid Corps ("EU Aid Volunteers Initiative")
- IMPLEMENTING REGULATION N° 1244/2014 (183); Establishes volunteer management procedures, training programme, certification mechanism
- DELEGATED REGULATION N° 1398/2014 (184); Establishes standards on recognition, equal opportunities, partnerships and the competence framework

5.5.4.1. Participation

The initiative is open to citizens, non-profit organisations and public institutions based in Europe or in third countries (185).

The participants are organised according to their role within the initiative in three groups:

- **Sending organizations:** EU-based organisations responsible for all the aspects of identification, selection, preparation, deployment and management of the EU Aid Volunteers.
 - Non-governmental not-for-profit organisations established in an EU Member State
 - Civilian public law bodies from a Member State;
 - The International Federation of National Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies.
 - Candidate and partner countries of the European Neighbourhood Policy and countries that are members of the European Economic Area (EEA) can participate as soon as these countries have signed agreements with the EU covering the programme.
- **Hosting organizations:** based in non-European Union countries, are responsible for the induction phase, designating mentors and ensuring the provision of adequate accommodation and working conditions throughout the deployment.
 - Non-governmental not-for profit organisations operating or established in a third country under the laws in force in that country;
 - Public law bodies of a civilian character governed by the law of a third country;
 - International agencies and organisations.
- **Volunteers:** European citizens interested in becoming involved as volunteers in humanitarian aid operations in third countries. They must comply with:
 - Be a minimum 18 years old.
 - Be a European Union citizen or long-term resident in an EU Member State.
 - Have full-time availability for the entire time specified in the vacancy notice, which can be from 1 month to 18 months.
 - Be available to participate in two-week training programme as part of the selection process.

- It is not necessary to have a humanitarian aid experience to apply to be an EU Aid Volunteer. However, they must meet the requirements of each volunteer vacancy.

The sending and hosting organisations must certify that they comply with the quality standards required for the proper management of the volunteers. The certification process is done through a self-assessment form that must be accompanied by evidence of compliance with the regulations, and the implementation of the required processes stipulated in the Delegated Regulation No 1398/2014 and the procedures laid down in Implementing Regulation No 1244/2014.

Information regarding the certification process can be found on the website of Education, Audio-visual and Culture Executive Agency (186).

Certified sending and hosting organisations shall undergo re-certification after three years following the decision of the Commission awarding the certification, or at any time in the event of substantial amendments to the standards or procedures in place for the EU Aid Volunteers initiative. The Commission may also decide to suspend or terminate certification following the rules indicated in Art. 37 of Regulation 1244/2014.

Only certified organisations can create consortia with other sending and hosting organisations to present projects for the deployment of EU Aid Volunteers.

The list of sending organizations can be find at (187).

The list of hosting organizations can be consulted at (188).

As of September 2020, a total of 76 sending and 298 hosting organisations had been certified under the EUAV Initiative.

In the new upcoming European Solidarity Corps regulation for the period 2021-2027, the European Solidarity Corps programme will take up the EU Aid Volunteers initiative as a new strand. As from January 2021, DG EAC will be responsible for young people's volunteering activities in the field of humanitarian aid.

The guidelines for the EU humanitarian partnership certificate guidance 2021-2027 is available on the Partners' website (189).

5.5.4.2. Training and development plan

The European Framework of Competences (EQF) (190) is an agreement created to facilitate the comprehension of qualifications of various European countries. The aim of EQF is encouragement of mobility and facilitation of access to permanent learning among habitants of various European countries.

The EQF is based on the results of learning, using known expressions comprehensible for the learner following the learning process. The results of learning are divided in 3 categories:

- **Knowledge:** results of assimilation of information thanks to learning, collecting of actions, principles, theories and practices related to the work field or particular studies.

- **Skills:** ability of applying knowledge and using techniques for completing tasks and resolving the problems.
- **Competences:** ability of applying knowledge, skills and personal, social, and methodological abilities into various work or study situations but also into self and professional development.

The EU Aid Volunteers initiative defines a framework of competences to facilitate the development of volunteers and has established the obligation to develop a learning plan that records the learning outcomes expected of volunteers in their missions. The framework of competences should be tailored to the different profiles of volunteers, and take into account the needs of junior and senior volunteers.

Three dimensions competences must be considered: transversal, specific and technical competences, for which see the Annex of the Delegated Regulation 1398/2014 for specific definitions and individual descriptions. In any case, such dimensions can be described as:

Transversal competences

- Developing and maintaining collaborative relationships
 - Working with others
 - Communication
- Volunteering mind-set
- Managing oneself in a pressured and changing environment
 - Self-awareness and resilience
 - Autonomy
 - Managing one's own expectations
 - Inter-cultural awareness
- Demonstrating leadership
- Achieving results
 - Achieves and communicates the immediate results of the action and the progress made in terms of capacity building
 - Accountability

Specific competences

- Understanding the humanitarian context of the EU Aid Volunteers initiative and applying humanitarian principles
- Operating safely and securely at all times
- Managing projects in humanitarian contexts
- Communication and advocacy

Technical competences

EU Aid Volunteers may have competences in the following fields:

finance and accounting; legal affairs; project management and administration; communication; logistics and transport; human resources management and learning; organisational development and capacity building; water and sanitation; food, nutrition and health; refugees

and internally displaced persons; gender issues; child protection; linking relief, rehabilitation and development; disaster risk management; resilience building; risk and vulnerability assessment; climate change adaptation; awareness-raising and education; community-based development; disaster preparedness and contingency response; medical and paramedical services; engineering; volunteer management.

The sending and hosting organisations must develop a learning and development plan, specific to each volunteer, and adapt the learning outcomes to the needs of the volunteer, at the junior or senior level, to the conditions of the vacancy, and the support actions of the organisations. This plan should be filled in on the EAUV platform (191).

The training programme is composed of mandatory and optional modules, both on-line and face-to-face units, referenced in the Implemented Regulation No1244/2014.

- **Mandatory modules**
 - Module 1: General introduction to the Union, its external relations and crisis response system (0.5 day)
 - Module 2: Introduction to humanitarian action, the Union humanitarian aid policy and the EU Aid Volunteers initiative (1.5 days)
 - Module 3: Managing personal safety, health and security (1.5 days)
 - Module 4: Project management, Introduction Level 1 (Introduction to the lifecycle of humanitarian aid missions/ projects) for Junior professionals (1.5 days)
 - Module 5: Project management, Advanced Level 2 (Introduction to the lifecycle of humanitarian aid missions/ projects and programmes) for Senior professionals (1.5 days)
 - Module 6: Inter-cultural awareness (and transversal issues) (1 day)
 - Module 7: Scenario-based exercise (3 days)
- **Optional modules**
 - Module 8: Communication and advocacy (1 day)
 - Module 9: Psychological first aid (PFA) (1 day)
 - Module 10: Training of multipliers (training the trainer) (2 days)
 - Module 11: Volunteer management (1 day)
 - Module 12: Organisational development (2 days)

5.5.4.3. Intervention

The intervention logic is based on Regulation 375/2014 establishing the EU Aid Volunteers Initiative and on the basis of analysis and lessons learned from the three EU Aid Volunteers pilot actions.

The intervention logic has five key actors or groups of actors involved and/or affected by EUAV: European Union, sending organisations, hosting organisations, volunteers and local communities.

Figure 28 - EUAV parties and their key interests

5.5.5. The United Nations Volunteers program

The United Nations Volunteers (UNV) is administered by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and reports to the UNDP/UNFPA/UNOPS Executive Board.

UNV headquarters are in Bonn, Germany. UNV has around 150 staff members at headquarters, and over 9,400 UN Volunteers deployed in the field in 2020.

At the country level, UNV Field Units interact with UN entities to strategically and meaningfully integrate volunteerism into the implementation and delivery of their mandates. As part of this process, UNV works with UN entities to identify opportunities where volunteers add specific and unique value to development programmes and peacekeeping missions. The UN Partner Toolkit is the first point of entry for partners seeking information about mobilizing and managing UNV.

UNV can be recruited in five main categories, efficiently and flexibly.

Figure 29 - UN Volunteers categories (192)

5.5.5.1. Training

UN Volunteers must complete the UN mandatory and UNV core training (193) prior to departure to the duty station. Non-compliance may lead to exclusion from future learning opportunities.

Mandatory courses:

- BSAFE: online security awareness training.
- UN course on prevention of harassment, sexual harassment and abuse of authority
- Prevention of sexual exploitation and abuse (PSEA) by UN personnel – Funds and programmes edition
- Ethics and integrity as UN volunteer
- Cultural awareness and working in cross-cultural environments
- Know your obligations and rights while volunteering
- Volunteering for the sustainable development goals
- Unified conditions of service (5 online modules)

UN Volunteer learning online portal eCampus (194).

The Volunteer Reporting Application is UNV's reporting tool aimed at providing results-based reporting from our volunteers (195).

5.5.6. The Red Cross in Europe

The Red Cross EU Office (196) is a membership office representing the 27 National Red Cross Societies in the EU, the Norwegian Red Cross, the Icelandic Red Cross and the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC).

Figure 30 – National Red Cross societies in the EU (197)

In collaboration with their national authorities as independent auxiliaries to the government in the humanitarian field, National Red Cross Societies in the EU support people in need through their networks of community-based volunteers.

As auxiliaries to their national authorities, National Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies play a key role in disaster management planning and response mechanisms. Their civil protection responsibilities vary between countries, depending on the domestic context. National Societies deliver emergency services and a wide range of humanitarian activities, including first aid, ambulances, psychosocial support, and search and rescue. They work to strengthen people's resilience by improving prevention and preparedness or reducing the effects of disasters. Upon request from the host National Society in another country, Red Cross EU Office members also deliver speedy assistance around the world. Based on this expertise, they cooperate with the European Commission Directorate General for Civil Protection and Humanitarian Operations (ECHO) to improve synergies and reduce duplications in emergency response in third countries.

Resources are pooled through the UCPM to provide coordinated assistance to victims of natural and man-made disasters both inside and outside the EU.

5.5.6.1. Bulgarian Red Cross

To give an example of a National Red Cross Society within Europe, we will focus on Bulgarian Red Cross (BRC).

The organization has both operational and supportive role throughout the whole circle of disaster management. Its operational engagement includes forest fire prevention and forest firefighting actions, urban firefighting actions, search and rescue and first aid actions. Regarding their support actions, the volunteering organization is responsible for making secure and sustain communications between government agencies. Bulgarian Red Cross is also involved in psychological support, public awareness, relief and support, as well as shelter monitoring actions. Bulgarian Red Cross is humanitarian volunteer organization, working according to its Statutes and the principles of the International Red Cross Movement, committed to providing support to vulnerable people victims of crisis and disasters in order to improve their life and dignity and relieve their suffering.

The General Assembly -Supreme organ of BRC National Council -main executive and ruling body. The organisation has full-time staff at national and regional level, which forms an administrative-executive body (the Secretariat). BRC has a four-level organizational structure:

- Association level
- Municipal level
- Regional, resp. Metropolitan level - 28 regional organisations
- National level

The BRC works for increasing the population's preparedness to act in case of disasters and together with the Civil Defence bodies prepares first aid formations and also renders first aid. In order to achieve its goals, the BRC works to increase the organization's capacity and improve coordination during disasters and accidents (crises). The BRC is included in National Disaster Plan. The organization assists the state in humanitarian activities protecting and strengthening the population's health in case of disasters and accidents (crises). BRC renders humanitarian aid in case of natural and technological disasters and accidents. The organization has regular organizational personnel, Volunteer Disaster Response Teams, Organized and spontaneous Volunteers in Disasters Situations Volunteers from other regional BRC organizations, Mountain Rescue Teams, National and Regional Water Life Saving Teams, Youth Volunteer Disaster Teams Member of refugee, and Migrant Service Professional Teams for First Psychological Aid.

For disaster response activities BRC relay on its regional organizations, disaster response teams, psychological experts, volunteers and partners. In 2007 was created a monetary fund was for assisting disaster and accident victims. The active work in methodological support to the BRC regional councils in the issue related to crisis response is permanent activity during the year and focused on the constantly changing situation and conditions. BRC participates in the National Plan for Disaster Protection and performs the following tasks:

- Creates the Volunteer Disaster Response Teams to assist the population in case of disasters
- Establishes and maintains a reserve of assets, essential for the initial support of victims;
- Maintains central and regional warehouses with a reserve of assets of victims in case of disaster
- Maintains radio - communication network (High Frequency and Very High Frequency) for use in the country and connection with neighbouring national societies and IFRC
- Performs coordination and cooperation with governmental and nongovernmental bodies involved in carrying out rescue work and support in case of disasters
- Liaises and coordinates the activities with the IFRC and others National societies to mobilize, receive and distribute international assistance and aid where it is necessary
- Collect and distribute internal and international assistance and aid for population in affected areas

6. Legal barriers and ethical concerns

Ethical legal concerns refer to two main aspects: i) data processing activities that shall be compliant with the EU regulatory framework in order to protect the availability, integrity, and confidentiality of information. Therefore, for any system a complex data protection impact assessment shall be developed and kept updated in order to identify and implement proper safeguards, including technical and organisational measures, to protect data flows and at the same time to boost their re-use to better manage the disasters; ii) the lack of common programs to develop specific competence and skills to address ethical legal compliance at any level of the first response system.

In particular, even if the technical specifications of the data management platforms and tools include appropriate safeguards implemented by design and by default, it is possible that considering the emergency situation to be managed, access to information could give beyond formal procedure. This would be lawful as long as the legal basis to process personal data is related to a given emergency. However, once that the disaster is managed and the emergency delay expires, the monitoring and compliance systems should assess whether some breach occurred (e.g., unauthorized access to datasets, loss of information, mistakes in data entry) and promptly adopt countermeasures to restore the ethical-legal compliance by design and by default. In any case, principles of data minimization, purpose, and accountability shall govern any data processing even in emergency circumstances.

In order to mitigate these risks, it is necessary to develop specific programs of awareness for first responders dedicated to data sharing and ethical legal compliance, as proposed in D6.4.

7. Conclusions

7.1. WP6 conclusion

The objective of WP6 is to implement international comparative research on the process of building a harmonisation framework for enhancing the cooperation between first aid responders with other disaster management actors.

To achieve this objective, the contributing partners worked in close cooperation over the last 10 months. The content and the process of development of the deliverables were synchronised among WP4, WP5 and WP6. The partners participated in the creation of a common methodology among the work packages WP4, WP5 and WP6. Besides, a questionnaire for data collection from First Aid Responders was developed and distributed (Annex 3).

The analyses done in the framework of WP6 and presented in the deliverable D6.5 give an opportunity to describe in details the current state of preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration opportunities for first aid response to multi-casualty disasters. The results obtained are a good basis for identification of existing gaps/capability needs, as well as harmonisation opportunities to improve collaboration between medical teams and other institutions involved in crisis management operations, as well as to enhance the effectiveness of first aid responses. Besides, the analysis in this updated version of the deliverable D6.1 identifies several areas that need improvement and formulates some ideas on possible solutions for minimising the negative consequences of the identified gaps/capabilities needs.

The following paragraphs present a summary of the achieved results in the framework of different tasks in WP6.

7.2. Tasks conclusions

7.2.1. Task 6.1 – Resource Federation and trusted information sharing

Task 6.1 focuses on studying different techniques for sharing information between different levels, both horizontally and vertically. For this, current solutions for information sharing between institutions have been studied, where information can travel between different organisations in the same country or even between different organisations in different countries. For this information sharing, the framework designed must locate the information to be used and save the locations of these so that when obtaining certain information, it is possible to request it from the corresponding application, avoiding centralisation and collapse of resources. On the other hand, a resource federation is necessary, where the different organisations share the available resources and their data. For this data sharing, different technologies are currently used for this purpose, such as OAuth or Shibboleth.

The main gaps in data federation focus on existing techniques to ensure reliable transmission of information between different participants. For this reason, current and standardised solutions that provide a robust methodology for data transmission, primarily sensitive in multiple victim scenarios, have been thoroughly analysed.

Afterwards, the existing cryptographic mechanisms have been analysed to detect gaps that allow a significant degree of improvement. In this sense, the proposed landscape addresses both symmetric, asymmetric, and quantum cryptography, comparing their performance and the degree of application they can be applied in real scenarios. It has been found that asymmetric cryptography guarantees higher robustness in data privacy at the cost of a higher computation by constrained devices. On the contrary, symmetric cryptography offers lower security at a

lower computation cost. Solutions that provide a hybrid of both or use more promising cryptographies such as quantum cryptography could provide advantages in secure resource sharing.

As previously mentioned, data integrity mechanisms have been studied to detect gaps that can provide a basis for cross-sector, cross-border and cross-hierarchy scenarios.

Finally, frameworks or complete solutions have been introduced to allow the management of federated resources, guaranteeing the gaps identified above and providing a robust implementation for application in real scenarios.

7.2.2. Task T6.2 – Education and training for first aid responses

The main gaps identified in the area and E&T for first aid responses at a national level are the lack of specific courses/training opportunities for Operational Assistants; these professionals are essential for the normal activity of an emergency service and their experience can make all the difference for both nurses and physicians in their day-to-day activities;

As previously mentioned as well, during the training of a nurse, only the Basic Life Support course is mandatory, and it is the responsibility of the nurse to further acquire knowledge through Advanced Life Support, who only does it if he/she so wishes to or has the resources.

Implementing a collaboration system between Hospitals and INEM/training entities could bridge this gap, and encourage Healthcare Professionals to seek training more often, free of personal expenditure, which in turn can and will translate in a better emergency team coordination, organization, and response to critical situations.

The focus should be on the development of common protocols and the integration of the common protocols into the IRS 112 coordination system:

- Develop robust trainings and exercise programmes
- Deliver certification for volunteers – provide different type of courses
- Deliver mapping of the common cross border committee and highlight / mainstream the topic of cross border mass casualties
- Map all project ongoing/ existing and former liaisons concerning the medicine of catastrophe in cross border regions.

Courses for first responses are not addressing data management needs. Personal and non-personal data governance and protection issues, in fact, are not part of the training and educational paths neither in Italy (see table below related to the most common courses delivered for basic/high level first responders), nor abroad, considering the results of previous analysis.

This lack could constitute a gap to be covered in terms of harmonization and standardisation of training activities in a multiple perspective:

1. Firstly, it could limit the risks of data breach (loss of data, unauthorized access, etc.) due to human behaviours and organizational procedures.
2. Secondly, it would contribute to a more effective governance and management of information, by developing knowledge and digital skills of first responders.

The table below represents some examples of existing courses.

Course	Target group	Description	Link
AWARENESS & FIRST RESPONDER LEVEL	People and Communities who live in potential flood risk areas, hydroelectric plant workers, technicians performing water measurements and surveys, firefighters and civilian protection teams in support of rescue workers.	These courses are designed for people who need to work in proximity of the river for making measurements and surveys, rescue squads in charge of logistics in a flooded area, community and people who are living in flood risk areas.	https://www.riverrescue.eu/training-courses/#tech-lvl
SWIFTWATER AND FLOOD RESCUE TECHNICIAN (SRT)	intensive training for personnel who may be required to respond to rescues in a swift water and flood environment, including emergency services personnel, mountain rescue teams, army,	The initial emphasis is on developing self-rescue skills. Other objectives include an in-depth look at subjects such as: understanding water dynamics, handling hazards and obstacles, using basic rescue equipment, setting up technical rope systems, controlling in-water contact rescues.	https://www.riverrescue.eu/training-courses/#tech-lvl
RESCUES FROM VEHICLES IN WATER (RVW)	This seminar focuses on rescue techniques applied to a vehicle fallen into a channel/river, with scenarios ranging from low to high risk. The following techniques are practiced and implemented: vehicle stabilization (car, motor home, minibus, etc.), access, evacuation of the victim/s.	This course is specific for Firefighters, professional rescuers, militaries, civil protection.	https://www.riverrescue.eu/training-courses/#tech-lvl
INFLATED FIREHOSE / RESCUE FROM BRIDGES	This intensive course is designed for firefighters and civil protection, as well as anyone susceptible to be dealing with river rescue from high access point (i.e., bridges), by using reach/throw techniques by using ropes and inflated firehose. The aim is to respond in a manner	This course is specific for Firefighters, professional rescuers, militaries, civil protection.	https://www.riverrescue.eu/training-courses/#tech-lvl

Course	Target group	Description	Link
	that allows to keep the rescuers out of the water.		
First Responder	Learn the life-saving techniques to be used in a first aid intervention, while waiting for the arrival of medical help.	anyone	http://firstresponder.it/
Bleeding First Responder” (BFR)	The BFR course does not have the presumption of creating small "Combat Life Saver" armed with tourniquets and haemostatic gauze, but only of spreading the ability to identify and, possibly, avoid the threat (prevention), get in safety (active or passive to depending on one's role and equipment), rescue or self-help as quickly as possible, alert the competent Operations Centre and do everything possible to stay alive while awaiting the arrival of health personnel.	Volunteers and assistance operators Police Who carries out control and safety work in crowded premises and / or places Anyone who wants to be able to react correctly in an emergency	https://www.salvamentoacademy.it/corsi/bleeding-first-responder-bfr/

Table 6 – Common courses delivered for basic / high level first responders

7.2.3. Task T6.3 – Raising practitioner and social awareness

The main role of T6.3 Raising practitioner and social awareness is to build and establish a contact network between practitioners and public partners. It is important to define some means of attracting public awareness and awareness of actors in the process of planning for cross-border MCI and of situational awareness. The role of first aid practitioners and social awareness in the case of cross-border, cross-sector and cross-hierarchical disaster situations is critical for success. Society's digitalization makes an opportunity to enhance the conventional strategies for raising awareness.

As it was explained at the beginning of this deliverable, the means of raising practitioner and social awareness need to be adapted to the phase of the emergency management cycle. As we focus on the incident phase, which is response, the websites, and social media accounts of first responders (EMS, firefighters, police, civil protection, etc.), NGO awareness workshops, journals, conferences, and training play a very important role for first responders to be effectively prepared and ready to respond quickly, efficiently and responsibly during the MCI accident.

7.2.4. Task T6.4 – Civil-Military Cooperation

The main role of the CIMIC is to establish contacts with representatives of the civil environment at all levels. There are a lot of similarities in CIMIC implementation and capability development

in the EU countries. This is mainly due to the influence of NATO in promoting CIMIC as a capability and the use of its doctrine by the majority of nations. Based on ambitions and capacity, there are some significant differences in the way CIMIC is part of the armed forces and used as a tool in crisis management. In this section the trends and differences that were found after analysing the various doctrines along a number of dimensions are discussed.

The comparative analysis of the disaster response systems and the normative base related to civil-military cooperation and interaction in conditions of large-scale disasters accompanied by mass casualties and destruction shows that there are significant differences in legislation, preparation, construction and principles of operation.

The state-of-the-art in the issues about civil-military cooperation among the EU Civil Protection Mechanism is not satisfied in fact. Analysis show that issues related to civil-military cooperation in the process of providing assistance to the population under the Civil Protection Mechanism are currently generally complex, with a diverse legal framework, significant differences in the organization, preparation and management of forces and means involved in search and rescue in the disaster area.

For example, in some countries there is a good legal framework and regulations for participation in various structures and organizations, including by law (Germany, Austria, Finland and Sweden). In other matters they are partially and relatively poorly regulated by by-laws - ordinances, orders or instructions of the head (Bulgaria, Slovakia).

In some countries, the distribution of responsibilities and responsibilities for planning, preparing and managing the response is centralized and raised to higher levels of administrative structures (Bulgaria, Spain, Greece, and Denmark). It can be concluded that these countries also rely more on the assistance of the armed forces in case of emergency.

While in other countries, especially those with large territories and with an administrative organization on a federal basis, these issues are decentralized and assigned to territorial authorities (Finland, Germany, and Sweden). In these countries, the army and the armed forces in general intervene only in exceptional cases, in disasters at the national or international level, as well as in threats to the security of the country from outside.

A common weakness is the fact that in a few countries special legal doctrines, ordinances, rules and procedures have been developed regulating the conditions, the order of introduction, the system of training, command and control and the order of interaction of military teams together with these in the area of the disaster or in the area of the emergency response operation.

There are also no documents regulating the participation of military formations in the planning of the reaction in case of disasters, in identifying and preparing disaster preventive options and measures. There are few countries in which training, education and joint exercises are conducted on a single idea, a common scenario and to implement common tasks. The description of this process can be used to create or correct SOP and SOI of formations and in the training of CIMIC specialists.

7.2.5. Task T6.5 – Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism

In an increasingly globalised environment where information and communication technologies are accessible and facilitate information exchange communication and thus decision-making, there has been a perceived increase in collaboration.

Sharing facilities, equipment and resources (i.e., European Civil Protection Pool) is a good example of this increment in collaboration for emergency response, cross-sector collaboration.

However, that achieving collaboration can be difficult because of include distrust, managerial complexity, cultural conflict, power imbalances, risk of dependence, and lack of incentive for collaboration (198). Institutions involved in emergency response in cross-sectorial cooperation are strongly hierarchical and centralized. Traditionally more reluctant to the idea of openness and cooperation, they are now forced by the need for change and modernization.

The methods and degree of cooperation between authorities and civil protection within the different regions of the European Union take different forms from one country to another. This variety is mainly due to legislative basis, organizational diversity and level of competence. As highlights in Table 5, different countries have different organisations, skills, roles and actors involved in civil protection mechanisms. Also, there are different “chain of command” and different chiefs. It is quite challenging to try harmonising different habits.

Major challenges in cross-border cooperation include undefined roles, responsibilities and tasks of different actors, difficulties in prioritising among tasks and a lack of legislation and routines.

This may be the minimum set for next opportunities: define the same roles and responsibilities of different actors in different countries.

From the last barometer publication about UCPM (199), a 90% of respondents say it is important that the EU helps to coordinate the response to disasters in the European Union (through its civil protection role).

According to the final report issued on July 2021 of the Ex-post evaluation of the EU Aid Volunteers Initiative, 2014-2020 (200), the following conclusions were collected:

- The EUAV Initiative has significantly improved the capacities of sending and hosting organisations and has created a pool of well-trained and highly skilled volunteers in the field of humanitarian assistance.
- The EUAV Initiative has contributed to increasing the capacity of the EU to deliver humanitarian aid by building the capacity of its partners, promoting the harmonisation of standards and fostering new partnerships and by enabling the deployment of trained EU volunteers. However, this contribution remained limited and for the most part short-term for reasons linked to the design and implementation of the Initiative.
- The EUAV Initiative contributed to strengthening the consistency and coherence of volunteering across participating sending organisations despite certain discrepancies in the implementation of standards. However, its contribution to encouraging a broader coherence across Member States was more limited.
- The EUAV Initiative prepared quality reference documents that have been useful for its implementation. But it suffered also from a heavy administrative burden and procedural

requirements that hampered its implementation and, in some cases, participation in the EUAV Initiative.

- The EUAV Initiative was underpinned by a well-designed monitoring and evaluation framework, but in practice monitoring activities remained limited.
- The EUAV Initiative was characterised by a lack of contingency planning and a rigidity of regulations that limited its capacity to adapt to changing contexts and hampered its effectiveness at times of crisis, including during the COVID-19 pandemic.
- The design of the EUAV Initiative treated volunteers, sending and hosting organisations as homogenous groups and did not sufficiently consider their differing profiles and needs. This hampered the effectiveness and efficiency of the EUAV Initiative.

At the same report, the following recommendations are exposed:

- Improve the effectiveness and efficiency of the EUAV Initiative through the development of a suitable European Commission “toolkit” of mechanisms and tools adapted to the different categories of SOs and HOs; the different levels of needs of volunteers; and the diversity of volunteer roles and operating contexts during deployments.
- Strengthen HumAid Corps localisation efforts, fostering local volunteering in particular by integrating it more systematically in the design of the Initiative.
- Enhance communication and coordination with other EU humanitarian aid and development stakeholders, as well as with peer volunteer networks such as United Nations Volunteers (UNV) and Member States schemes.
- Apply an appropriate monitoring and evaluation system and ensure adequate mechanisms are in place to promote peer learning and knowledge-sharing amongst all stakeholders.

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9. Annex B - Glossary

Acronym	Description
AA	Attribute Authority
AECID	Spanish Agency for International Development Cooperation
AEM	Emergency Medical Ambulance
ALS	Advanced Life Support
API	Application Programming Interfaces
AS	Authorization Server
B.S.E.C.	Black Sea Economic Cooperation
BLS	Basic Life Support
BRC	Bulgarian Red Cross
BSEC	Black Sea Economic Cooperation
C	Client
CBC	Cross Border Cooperation
CBO	Civil-Based Organisations
CBRN	Chemical, Biological, Radiological and Nuclear substances
CBRN-E	Chemical, Biological, Radiological and Nuclear substances and Explosives
CDP	Continuous Data Protection
CECIS	Common Emergency Communication and Information System
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CIC	Control and Information Centre
CIMIC	Civil-Military Cooperation
CMDB	Configuration Management Data Base
CODU	Urgent Patients Assistance Centre in Portugal
CPX	Command Post Exercise
DES	Data Encryption Standard
DG ECHO	Directorate General for European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations
DGPCE	Directorate General of Civil Protection and Emergencies in Spain
DiDRR	Disability-inclusive Disaster Risk Reduction
DPPI SEE	Disaster preparedness and prevention initiative for southeast Europe
DRM	Disaster Risk Management
E&T	Education and Training
ECG	Electrocardiogram
EDRIS	European Emergency Disaster Response Information System
EEA	European Economic Area
EKAB	National Centres for Emergency Care in Greece
EM	Emergency Medicine
EMC	European Medical Corps
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
EMT	Emergency Medical Teams
ENPC	National Civil Protection School in Spain
EoE	Exchange of Experts
EQF	European Framework of Competences
ERCC	Emergency Response Coordination Centre
ESI	Emergency Support Instrument

Acronym	Description
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EUAV	EU Aid Volunteers
FAR	First Aid Responders
FSCP	Fire Safety and Civil Protection in Bulgaria
FSX	Full-scale exercise
GDACS	Global Disaster and Coordination System
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GFARC	Global First Aid Reference Centre
GSM	Global System for Mobile
HAR	Health Assessment Record
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IdP	Identity Provider
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IFRC	International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies
IFRC	International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies
INEM	National Institute of Medical Emergency in Portugal
INSARAG	International Search and Rescue Advisory Group
IoT	Internet of Things
IRS	Integrated Rescue System
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
MCI	Mass Casualty Incidents
MICU	Mobile Intensive Care Units
MODEX	Module Exercise
ModFX	Modules Field Exercise
ModTTX	Modules Table-Top Exercise
MoI	Ministry of Interior
MoU	Memorandums of Understanding
MS	Member States
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organization
NGO	Non-Governmental Organizations
NOC	National Operational Centre in Bulgaria
NSA	US National Security Agency
NTC	National Training Coordinators
OCHA	United Nations Office for Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
OSOCC	On-Site Operations Coordination Centre
PGP	Pretty Good Privacy
PSEA	Prevention of sexual exploitation and abuse
QoS	Quality of Service
RAID	Redundant Array of Independent Disks
RC	Red Cross
RO	Resource Owner

Acronym	Description
RS	Resource Server
SAML	Security Assertion Mark-up Language
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SIEM	Integrated Medical Emergency System in Portugal
SIRESP	Integrated System of Emergency and Security Networks of Portugal
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
SOD	Sudden Onset Disasters
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
SP	Service Provider
SSO	Single-Sign-On
START	Spanish Technical Team for Emergency Aid and Response
TAS	Rescue Ambulance Crew in Portugal
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TEPH	Pre-Hospital Emergency Technicians in Portugal
TETRA	Terrestrial Trunked Radio
TIS	Trusted Information Sharing
ToT	Training of Trainers
TTP	Tactics, Techniques and Procedures
TTX	Table-top exercise
UC	Use Case
UCPM	EU Civil Protection Mechanism
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UIM	Unified Inventory Management
UN	United Nations
UNDAC	United Nations Disaster Assessment and Coordination
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNV	United Nations Volunteers
URS	Unified Rescue System
USAR	Urban Search and Rescue
VMER	Emergency and Resuscitation in Portugal
WAYF	Where Are You From
WHO	World Health Organization
XML	Extensible Mark-up Language

Table 7 - Glossary

10. Annex C – WP6 Questionnaire for First responders

AGENCY / ROLE NAME	
	AGENCY means the institution responsible for this task (for example in Madrid, SUMMA 112), in Italy AREU, etc.
	ROLE NAME (LOCAL LANGUAGE) is the particular name, in the local language, of the responsible of this task in this institution (for example, JEFE DEL DISPOSITIVO SANITARIO)
	ROLE NAME (ENGLISH TRANSLATION) is the role name translated to English (for example, MEDICAL INCIDENT COMMANDER)
CATEGORY	
CRISIS FIRST RESPONDERS OPERATIONS	The goal of this group of questions is to collect information about existence of emergency medical services (EMS) crisis operational procedures and unified cross-agency crisis operational procedures.
EMS ON SCENE & DEPLOYMENT	The goal of this group of questions is to collect information about the level of standardization of EMS ambulances, EMS ambulance medical equipment, EMS ambulance crew and EMS ambulance crew training.
COLLABORATION, EDUCATION AND TRAINING FOR FIRST AID RESPONSES	The goal of this group of questions is to collect information about the existing education and training courses for first aid responders, their content, planning, organisation and implementation, existing national first aid management standards, protocols/guidelines, protocols and procedures for cooperation and coordination between first aid medical teams and other first responders, etc. besides, this group of questions aims at collecting information about existing minimum competence requirements for first aid responders in the event of emergency and disaster, activities to be implemented for raising practitioners and social awareness, protocols and procedures regulating the civil-military cooperation in a case of emergency and disaster, activities implemented to improve interoperability among the first responders, etc. finally, this group of questions targets the topic of present of absent operational procedures and plans for health care in multiple casualty incidents.
REVIEW PROCEDURE:	
	Please, add your comments on the excel using COMMENTS options of Excel.
	Please, Do not delete items
	Please, add new items, if you want, in the related categories of the questionnaire, with yellow background colour
INTRODUCTION TO THE QUESTIONNAIRE	
Dear Colleagues,	
We are kindly asking for your expert support to implement in the best possible way the EU project "Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters" (VALKYRIES).	
The goals of the VALKYRIES project are:	

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Region	
Location	
Could your EMS have to intervene in a cross-border incident?	(Y/N)

	DESCRIPTOR 1	DESCRIPTOR 2	DESCRIPTOR 3	DESCRIPTOR 4
PLEASE IDENTIFY THE INVOLVED EMERGENCY AGENCY (FIRST RESPONDERS)	RESCUERS / FIREFIGHTERS / EMS / POLICE / ARMY / CIVIL PROTECTION / RED CROSS / OTHERS (DETAIL)	(MULTIPLE CHOICE)		
ARE THERE ANY EXISTING EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES (EMS) CRISIS OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES IN YOUR COUNTRY?	AVAILABLE Y/N	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	STANDARDIZED AT REGIONAL LEVEL (Y/N)	
ARE THERE ANY EXISTING UNIFIED CROSS-AGENCY CRISIS OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES IN YOUR COUNTRY?	AVAILABLE Y/N	RESCUERS / FIREFIGHTERS / EMS / POLICE / ARMY / CIVIL PROTECTION / RED CROSS / OTHERS (DETAIL)	(MULTIPLE CHOICE)	
IS THERE EMS AMBULANCES DEPLOYMENT STANDARDIZED	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	BASIC LIFE SUPPORT / ADVANCED LIFE SUPPORT	(MULTIPLE CHOICE)	
ARE THERE EMS AMBULANCE MEDICAL EQUIPMENT STANDARDIZED	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	STANDARDIZED AT REGIONAL LEVEL (Y/N)		
ARE THERE EMS AMBULANCE CREW COMPOSITION STANDARDIZED	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	STANDARDIZED AT REGIONAL LEVEL (Y/N)		
ARE THERE EMS AMBULANCE CREW TRAINING STANDARDIZED	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	PRE-UNIVERSITARY / UNIVERSITY / POST-UNIVERSITARY	(MULTIPLE CHOICE)	
ARE THERE ANY EMS APPLICATION USED	YES / NO	if yes: List APP Name entries	Description for each entry	
ARE THERE ANY EDUCATION AND TRAINING COURSES FOR FIRST AID RESPONDERS IN YOUR COUNTRY	AVAILABLE Y/N	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	TYPE (DETAIL)	STANDARDIZED AT REGIONAL LEVEL (Y/N)
FOR WHOM IS THE EDUCATION AND TRAINING COURSES DESIGNED	MEDICAL DOCTORS, NURSES/EQUIVALENT, PARAMEDICS, VOLUNTEERS, ALL MENTIONED PARTICIPATE, OTHER PLEASE SPECIFY	MULTIPLE CHOICE	TYPE (DETAIL)	

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	DESCRIPTOR 1	DESCRIPTOR 2	DESCRIPTOR 3	DESCRIPTOR 4
HOW ARE THE EDUCATION AND TRAINING COURSES FOR FIRST AID RESPONDERS ORGANISED	FOR MEDICAL TEAMS ONLY, JOINT FOR ALL FIRST RESPONDERS (E.G. FIREFIGHTERS, MEDICAL TEAMS, POLICE, MILITARY AND CIVIL PROTECTION), SEPARATE FOR THE AGENCIES, OTHER, PLEASE SPECIFY	MULTIPLE CHOICE	TYPE (DETAIL)	
WHO IS RESPONSIBLE/LEADING ORGANISATION/S PROVIDING TRAINING FOR FIRST AID RESPONDERS	CIVIL PROTECTION AGENCY, MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES/ COLLEGES, LOCAL AUTHORITIES, RED CROSS/SIMILAR ORGANISATIONS, OTHER PLEASE SPECIFY	MULTIPLE CHOICE	TYPE (DETAIL)	
ARE THERE NATIONAL STANDARDS FOR EMERGENCY MEDICAL RESPONDERS EDUCATION AND TRAINING	AVAILABLE Y/N STANDARDS; AVAILABLE Y/N PROTOCOLS; AVAILABLE Y/N GUIDELINES	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	TYPE (DETAIL)	
ARE THERE NATIONAL FIRST AID MANAGEMENT STANDARDS, PROTOCOLS/GUIDELINES	AVAILABLE Y/N STANDARDS; AVAILABLE Y/N PROTOCOLS; AVAILABLE Y/N GUIDELINES	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	TYPE (DETAIL)	
ARE THERE NATIONAL BASIC FIRST AID PROCEDURES	AVAILABLE Y/N	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	TYPE (DETAIL)	
ARE THERE DEFINED BASIC STEPS TO BE IMPLEMENTED BEFORE EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES ARRIVE	AVAILABLE Y/N	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	TYPE (DETAIL)	
ARE THERE ANY PROTOCOLS AND PROCEDURES FOR COOPERATION AND COORDINATION BETWEEN FIRST AID MEDICAL TEAMS AND OTHER FIRST RESPONDERS (E.G. FIREFIGHTERS, MEDICAL TEAMS, POLICE, MILITARY AND CIVIL PROTECTION)	AVAILABLE Y/N PROTOCOLS; AVAILABLE Y/N PROCEDURES	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	TYPE (DETAIL) FIREFIGHTERS, MEDICAL TEAMS, POLICE, AND CIVIL PROTECTION	
ARE THERE ANY EDUCATION AND TRAINING COURSES FOR FIRST RESPONDERS BETWEEN YOUR COUNTRY AND YOUR NEIGHBOURING COUNTRIES	AVAILABLE Y/N	STANDARDIZED AT THE INTERNATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	TYPE (DETAIL) WITH WHICH COUNTRY/S	
ARE THERE ANY PROTOCOLS AND PROCEDURES FOR COOPERATION BETWEEN THE FIRST AID RESPONDERS IN YOUR COUNTRY AND YOUR NEIGHBOURING COUNTRIES	AVAILABLE Y/N	STANDARDIZED AT THE INTERNATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	TYPE (DETAIL) WITH WHICH COUNTRY/S	

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	DESCRIPTOR 1	DESCRIPTOR 2	DESCRIPTOR 3	DESCRIPTOR 4
HOW WOULD YOU ASSESS THE EXISTING CAPABILITIES (TECHNOLOGICAL, MATERIAL, HUMAN, ORGANISATIONAL) FOR FIRST AID RESPONDERS IN YOUR COUNTRY	SUFFICIENT/NOT SUFFICIENT TECHNOLOGICAL; SUFFICIENT/NOT SUFFICIENT MATERIAL; SUFFICIENT/NOT SUFFICIENT HUMAN; SUFFICIENT/NOT SUFFICIENT ORGANISATIONAL		WHAT HAS TO BE IMPROVED (DETAIL) TECHNOLOGICAL, MATERIAL, HUMAN, ORGANISATIONAL	
ARE THERE ANY DEFINED EMERGENCY DEBRIEFING PRINCIPLES, GUIDELINES AND MANUALS FOLLOWING DISASTERS FOR FIRST AID RESPONDERS	AVAILABLE Y/N EMERGENCY DEBRIEFING PRINCIPLES; AVAILABLE Y/N EMERGENCY DEBRIEFING GUIDELINES; AVAILABLE Y/N EMERGENCY DEBRIEFING MANUALS	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	TYPE (DETAIL) DEBRIEFING PRINCIPLES, EMERGENCY DEBRIEFING GUIDELINES, TYPES OF DEBRIEFING FOLLOWING DISASTERS, DEBRIEFING MANUALS	
ARE THERE ANY DEFINED MINIMUM COMPETENCE REQUIREMENTS FOR FIRST AID RESPONDERS IN THE EVENT OF EMERGENCY AND DISASTER	AVAILABLE Y/N	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	TYPE (DETAIL)	
ARE THERE ANY DEFINED ACTIVITIES TO BE IMPLEMENTED FOR RAISING PRACTITIONERS AND SOCIAL AWARENESS IN A CASE OF EMERGENCY AND DISASTER	AVAILABLE Y/N	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	TYPE (DETAIL)	
ARE THERE ANY PROTOCOLS AND PROCEDURES REGULATING THE CIVIL-MILITARY COOPERATION IN THE EVENT OF EMERGENCY AND DISASTER	AVAILABLE Y/N PROTOCOLS; AVAILABLE Y/N PROCEDURES	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	TYPE (DETAIL)	
ARE THERE ANY ACTIVITIES TO IMPROVE INTEROPERABILITY AMONG THE FIRST RESPONDERS (E.G. FIREFIGHTERS, MEDICAL RESPONDERS, POLICE, MILITARY, CIVIL PROTECTION, LOCAL AUTHORITIES, ETC.)	AVAILABLE Y/N	STANDARDIZED AT NATIONAL LEVEL? (Y/N)	TYPE (DETAIL) FIREFIGHTERS, MEDICAL RESPONDERS, POLICE, MILITARY, CIVIL PROTECTION, LOCAL AUTHORITIES	
ARE THERE ANY DEFINED OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES AND PLANS FOR HEALTH CARE IN MULTIPLE CASUALTY INCIDENTS	AVAILABLE Y/N OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES; AVAILABLE Y/N OPERATIONAL PLANS			
HOW WOULD YOU ASSESS THE EXISTING LEVEL OF CIVILIAN EDUCATION WITH REGARD TO EMERGENCY RESPONSE IN YOUR COUNTRY?	SUFFICIENT/NOT SUFFICIENT QUANTITY; SUFFICIENT/NOT SUFFICIENT QUALITY		WHAT HAS TO BE IMPROVED (DETAIL)	

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	DESCRIPTOR 1	DESCRIPTOR 2	DESCRIPTOR 3	DESCRIPTOR 4											
HOW WOULD YOU ASSESS THE AMOUNT OF PUBLIC ACCESS TO FIRST AID EQUIPMENT (E.G. DEFIBRILLATORS, KITS, ETC.)	ENOUGH/NOT ENOUGH	ARE THERE ANY NATIONAL LEGISLATION ON THE AVAILABILITY OF THIS EQUIPMENT?	TYPE (DETAIL)												
Is THE Mass Casualty Incident TRAINING mandatory or optional IN YOUR COUNTRY?	MANDATORY/OPTIONAL														
How often is THE MCI course ORGANISED?	ONCE PER YEAR/ONCE PER SIX MONTHS/EACH THREE MONTHS/EACH MONTH														
Do you think that THE training with Mass Casualty Incident simulators would improve the acquisition of knowledge?	YES/NO														
How is social awareness provided in your country?	<input type="checkbox"/> leaflets <input type="checkbox"/> TV/radio advertisement, <input type="checkbox"/> newspaper/journal advertisement <input type="checkbox"/> training, practical exercises <input type="checkbox"/> messages sent by national/local authorities <input type="checkbox"/> social media posts <input type="checkbox"/> another activity... (PLEASE GIVE DETAILS)	MULTIPLE CHOICE													
How is practitioner awareness provided in your country?	<input type="checkbox"/> Practical exercises/training <input type="checkbox"/> cross-unit training <input type="checkbox"/> SW/HW of IRS <input type="checkbox"/> Debriefings <input type="checkbox"/> another activity... (PLEASE GIVE DETAILS)	MULTIPLE CHOICE													
3. What should be improved/added regarding social and practitioner awareness in your country (but also generally)?			OPEN ENDED QUESTION												
<table border="1"> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="3">(Related form item)</td> <td>Type of emergency:</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Issue/gap:</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Summary of the situation:</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="4">If the gap is based on the scientific literature or on some other reference document, please cite and attach a link if possible.</td> <td>Doc name:</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Year:</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Link:</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Justification:</td> </tr> </table>							(Related form item)	Type of emergency:	Issue/gap:	Summary of the situation:	If the gap is based on the scientific literature or on some other reference document, please cite and attach a link if possible.	Doc name:	Year:	Link:	Justification:
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	Year:														
	Link:														
	Justification:														

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	DESCRIPTOR 1	DESCRIPTOR 2	DESCRIPTOR 3	DESCRIPTOR 4

RELATED WP	CATEGORY
WP2	Terminology and Semantics
WP2	Functions and Applications
WP3	Operational procedures (national/international)
WP3	Interoperability among medical and other First Responders
WP6	Collaboration opportunities among medical and other First Responders
WP6	Education and Training planning and organization (separate for the agencies; joint)
WP6	Education and Training content (competencies to be achieved)
WP6	Education and Training target groups (medical doctors, nurses/equivalent, paramedics, etc.)
WP6	Education and Training implementation
WP6	Capabilities for First Aid Responders (technological, knowledge/competencies, legal/regulatory, material, human resources, etc.)
WP6	Unified and standardized procedures and protocols for EMS
WP6	Others
WP6	Others

11. Annex D – Analysis of the results from WP6 Survey

The WP6 survey was responded by 10 First responders (FRs) from Bulgaria, Greece, Iceland, Slovakia, Spain and Portugal. Out of them 6 come from Emergency Medical Services (EMS) and 4 are firefighters. Most often they describe their role during Multi Casualty Incident (MCI) response: as (1) Primary and secondary aid response (depending on the order of response; (2) Provision of the basic and necessary rescue work, basic first aid and transport of victims to EMS crews; (3) Coordination of the action of the health group, which is in charge of managing the necessary health resources, providing "in situ" health care, coordinating the evacuation of patients and injured people, as well as executing protection and relief measures. to the population; (4) Triage, BLS /ALS, Transport; (4) Coordination of the prehospital response, triage, treatment and transportation to hospitals of casualties. Also, the regulation of hospital response, ICU beds; (6) Control and execution of response activities, zonation, first aid, safety and security management, cooperation with other services.

Nine out of ten FRs declare that their EMS is prepared if they have to intervene in a cross-border incident.

All respondents declare that there are existing emergency medical services crisis Standard Operational procedures (SOPs) in their country among firefighters; emergency medical services; civil protection; red cross; rescuers and police, but 7 out of ten think that they are not standardized at the national level and 3 respond "Don't know". The same is the distribution of the answers regarding the standardization at the regional level.

Most of the FRs maintain that there are existing unified cross-agency crisis SOPs in their country (8 persons) and 2 respond "Don't know".

Most of the FRs (7) declare that the emergency medical services ambulances deployment in their countries is standardized for both basic life support and advanced life support at the national level and 2 think is not standardized, while 1 respond "Don't know".

Close is the distribution of the responses regarding the standardization of emergency medical services ambulance medical equipment at national level and regional level (Yes – 9; No – 1).

Most of the FRs (7) think that the emergency medical services ambulance crew composition standardized at national and regional level (2 respond No and 1 Don't know – 1).

Again, most of the FRs (7) think that the emergency medical services ambulance crew training standardized at national level (2 respond no and 1 don't know – 1). the diversity of the level of standardization is high. in some countries it is at pre-university level- 3. in other – both at pre-university and university level (2), as well as university and post-university level (2). single respondents answer that the emergency medical services ambulance crew training is standardized at post-university level (1), pre-university, university and post-university level (1) and 1 respond "don't know".

Regarding the use any emergency medical services applications the diversity in responses is also high (Yes – 3, No – 3, Don't know – 4)

Most of the FRs (9) maintain that there are different education and training courses for first aid responders in their country. Good examples are: (1) Standardized Basic and Advanced Life Support training, mainly through INEM and Red Cross in Portugal; (2) BLS courses and ILS / ALS in the ERC standards. And the specific training within different agencies in Iceland; (3) Courses

for civil and military paramedics, as well as first aid courses provided by the Red Cross and other civil organizations in Bulgaria; (4) Training of Emergency Medical Aid teams in the capital to act in the event of a possible terrorist act, or training of EMA teams to improve interoperability with other structures in MASCAL as a result of earthquakes in Bulgaria.

The training courses are designed for medical doctors; nurses/equivalent; volunteers; private entities, SAR teams; police, firefighters – paramedics, etc.

Most of the FRs (6) maintain that the courses for first aid responders are organized in joint format for all first responders (firefighters, medical teams, police, military and civil protection). In 3 cases the courses are organized separate for the agencies and 1 respond “don’t know”.

Most often for the organization of the courses are responsible civil protection agencies; medical universities/colleges; red cross/similar organizations.

According to the respondents, there is different level of standardisation of emergency medical responder’s education and training at national level: available guidelines (2); available standards (3); available basic first aid procedures (5). Good examples are: (1) In Bulgaria National certified documents, including all obligatory practical and theoretical education; (2) In Italy - Basic and advanced courses; (3) In Iceland standards coordinated by Fire protection/EMS services and the Chief MD of Icelandic out of hospital EMS; (3) In Slovakia 578 THE LAW of October 21, 2004; also 398 DECREE of Ministry of Health of the Slovak Republic of September 30, 2010 on the minimum requirements for the first aid course and the first aid instructor course .

Half of the FRs do not know about standardisation of emergency medical responder’s education and training at national level at national level (5) on the opposite opinion are 4 FRs and 1 respond “don’t know”. The standardisation is focused on stopping major bleeding, basic live function (breathing, heart activity, consciousness), secondary first-aid treatment; Civil Protection has sent out triage cards and checklist for quick triage in MCI’s and it’s used as standard nationwide for First responders.

Most of the FRs (7) are not informed about existing education and training courses for first responders organised jointly between their countries and neighbouring countries. On the opposite opinion are 2 FRs and 1 respond “don’t know”.

Regarding the existing capabilities (technological, material, human, organisational) of first aid responders in their country, the diversity of responses is very high. Only 1 FR declare that in his/her country there are sufficient technological; sufficient material; sufficient human; sufficient organisational capabilities. In all other cases there are some capabilities gaps and 3 FRs respond “don’t know”.

The recommendation for improvement of the capabilities of first aid responders are related to: (1) “All of the above, continuous improvement for optimal response”; (2) “Misusing of EMS crews for trivial health complications and missing sanctions for these misusing”; (3) “System of EMS providers in private companies - at the expense of profit saving resources necessary for response”; (4) “More people need to get the education”; (5) “The law”; (6) “Training, specific standard operation procedures”; (7) “Emergency medicine depends on the qualification of the personnel, but is inevitably connected with equipment, technologies and other logistic issues. With the development of science and technologies, there are new tools and technical improvements in the sphere of medicine and first aid organization”.

Half of the FRs maintain that there are defined minimum competence requirements for first aid responders in the event of emergency and disaster in their countries (5). On the opposite opinion are 3 FRs and 2 respond “don’t know”.

Regarding the availability of defined activities to be implemented for raising practitioners and social awareness in a case of emergency and disaster, the responses of the FRs are dispersed. Four of them respond “Yes”, 3 – No and 4 “Don’t know”.

Close is the distribution of the responses regarding the availability of protocols and procedures regulating the civil-military cooperation in the event of emergency and disaster. Three of FRs maintain that there are available procedures, 1- available protocols; available procedures - 1, “no” – 2 and “do not know” – 3.

In the same time, most of the FRs (6) declare that there are existing activities to improve interoperability among the first responders. A good example is the Spanish the joint coordination centre in every region where leaders from every participating organization come and communicate face to face. On the opposite opinion are 2 FRs and 2 respond “don’t know”.

The opinions are split regarding whether the mass casualty incident training is mandatory or optional in different countries. It is optional in Portugal, Iceland, Slovakia and Bulgaria, while the training is mandatory in Spain and Greece. 2 FRs respond “don’t know”.

Most of the FRs (9) think that the training with mass casualty incident simulators would improve the acquisition of knowledge and 1 respond “don’t know”.

The social awareness about how to act in a case of MCI is provided most often via leaflets; TV/radio advertisement; newspapers/journal advertisement; training, practical exercises; messages sent by national/local authorities and social media posts.